

Textile coloration and fragrance finishing for perfumed garments

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Keynote of Thesis

This MTech report on “combined dyeing and fragrance finishing of woven cotton fabric for garments” has a contribution of simultaneous dyeing and technical finishing with beta cyclodextrin under fragrance retention on cotton textiles after repeated washing. This technique was bulk implemented for ladies inner garments/Bra. The technical finished product was sold in different local market in Bangladesh in 2016 traded as Bangladesh Textile and Fashion. There was huge positive customer feedback, practically monitored and sold by author in his local branded showroom in Uttara, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Presently, this technology is being patented.

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Abstract

Combined dyeing and finishing offers considerable economy in operating costs because of the simplicity of the operations. Project work was proceeded to study the feasibility of combined dyeing and multifinishing (fragrance, water repellency, antcrease, crease recovery) in one step to reduce process cost like as time saving , heat energy saving, water, low vapour-gas-emission, low labour cost, environment – friendly and also worked on to develop and optimize durable fragrance finishing for cotton textiles which may be an alternative invention of artificial application of perfume on textile substrate named as cosmetic finishing. **By spectrophotometer analysis**, combined combined dyed and finished cotton fabric showed deeper color yield for reactive dyeing of monochlorotriazine group using beta cyclodextrin, citric acid and sodium hypophosphite although cotton fabric was treated with dextrin & DMDHEU both in double stage and combined method. Beta cyclodextrin, Dextrin and DMDHEU were applied for monochlorotriazine group of reactive dyeing and Fragrance finishing of cotton fabric in conventional double stage exhaust and combined pad-dry-cure method where combined method of dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin showed higher K/S value, dry crease recovery angle, tensile strength than using double stage method. **Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) spectra** confirmed that crosslinking successfully formed among the carboxyl group of acids, the hydroxyl groups of cellulose and beta cyclodextrin due to the esterification reaction. As fragrance chemical: synthetic fragrance (Jasmine), Rose oil and Pachouli oil were used with beta cyclodextrin and without beta cyclodextrin. Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine) with beta cyclodextrin showed high level of fragrance intensity in combined dyeing and finishing than double stage method. **Human sensory evaluation** testing showed that fragrance intensity became gradually weaker with respect to time and washing cycle. Fragrance intensity was tested by human sensorial evaluation was found 10% after 70 days without washing and 30% retained after five time washing. **By Gas chromatography testing**, the intensity of Jasmine fragrance was found 15.88% after five time washing and the intensity of fragrance was retained 39.5% in the cotton fabric after 100 days without washing.

Introduction

Textile science of chemical processing encompass diverse disciplines and areas of expertise. In the present scenario of industrial consciousness, integration in all aspects of textile wet processing is commercial ultimatum where everyone is repeatedly querying to textile scientist. The present research on combined dyeing and finishing is prime of them. β -cyclodextrin is the aromatherapeutic textile as host molecule, because it exhibits qualities which are beneficial for the human body. β -cyclodextrins molecules are capable of forming inclusion compounds with fragrances that fit into the cone-shaped hydrophobic cavity. As a result, the release-fragrance rates are greatly decreased. There are many possibilities for the development of new textile products with advanced properties based on β -cyclodextrin. Microencapsulation technology is an effective technique used to control the release properties of active ingredients that prolong the functionality of cosmetic textiles. Focusing on the field of cosmetic textiles, the major interest in microencapsulation is currently in the application of attractive fragrances, vitamins, essential oils, skin moisturizing agents, skin cooling agents etc. The investigation⁽¹²⁸⁾ of US retail sales of home fragrance shows that sales increased 9.7 percent, from \$1.35 billion in 1995 to \$1.96 billion in 1999. Pleasure and enjoyment⁽¹²⁹⁾ on the one hand, is about daring to be different, but also about forgetting stress. Excitement and active wear is a form of communication.⁽¹³⁰⁾ The scents of lavender, rose, citrus or vanilla were encapsulated into cotton fabrics⁽¹¹⁴⁾, which proved a good way to meet important psychological and emotional needs, as well as those of a purely physical and sensorial nature aromatherapy was coined in the late 1920s by the French cosmetic chemist R.M. Gattefosse, who noticed the excellent antiseptic properties and skin permeability of essential oils. Dr. Charles Tomasino⁽¹⁰⁴⁾ reviewed that natural starches are not very soluble in cold water and Dextrin⁽¹¹²⁾ has OH group and Cyclodextrins^(113, 114) are cyclic oligosaccharides containing six, seven eight, nine ten, eleven, twelve, thirteen 1,4-linked glycopyranose units with a hydrophilic hydroxyl group on their outer surface and a hydrophobic cavity in the center. The general features of β -cyclodextrin⁽¹¹¹⁾ that β -cyclodextrin can act as a host for various guest molecules and Devinderkaur and Neelam Grewal⁽¹¹⁰⁾ reviewed that the cyclodextrin capacity to form inclusion complexes is known for a long time. Cyclodextrins^(131,118) clamped on cellulose do not affect the cellulose's properties and fragrance was capsulated with beta cyclodextrin and perfume retention onto the fabric although fragrance compound⁽¹³⁷⁾ and the essential oil are volatile substances and the mechanism of microencapsulation⁽¹²⁴⁾ was core material +wall shell= controlled release. J. Kotch⁽¹³²⁾ reviewed that Complexed with cyclodextrin, perfumes are stable and B. Martel and et.al.⁽¹³³⁾ reviewed that Permanent fixation of cyclodextrins onto textiles. J.-P. Moldenhauer⁽¹³⁴⁾ found that β -cyclodextrin is a reactive cyclodextrin derivative that can be covalently fixed to nucleophilic substrates by a substitution reaction carried out by the usual finishing procedure. Both alkaline and acidic methods⁽¹³⁵⁾ for MCT- β -cyclodextrin finishes have been developed to suit customers. Underwear, gloves, socks⁽¹³⁶⁾ can be loaded with the necessary antifungal, antihistaminic, and anti-inflammatory agents. Flowers, leaves and fruit used as ingredients^(116, 117, 118) of perfume and Only a few molecules⁽¹¹⁶⁾ are necessary for us to experience or identify scents, and characteristically, the worse a smell is, the less it takes to notice it. The most commonly used microencapsulation processes⁽¹²³⁾, including Complex Coacervation, Polymer-Polymer Incompatibility, Interfacial Polymerisation and In Situ Polymerisation, Spray Drying, Centrifugal Extrusion, Air Suspension Coating, Pan Coating, and Emulsion Hardening Process and⁽¹³⁸⁾SEM (Scanning electron microscopy), Infra-Red (IR) Spectroscopy, Thin Layer chromatography, TLCX-ray diffractometry and Single crystal X-ray structure analysis are the important testing of microencapsulation. For micro-encapsulation⁽¹⁴⁰⁾ cyclodextrins are the best regarding safety to the human body, because β -cyclodextrin has no skin irritation, no skin sensibilisation and no mutagenic effect. Detailed studies of toxicology⁽¹¹²⁾, mutagenicity,

teratogenity and carcinogenity were indicated that the cyclodextrin can affect the human organism only at extremely high concentrations. Successful example of using cyclodextrin for aroma finishing ⁽¹³⁹⁾ with Sensorial evaluation of scent intensity with cyclodextrin. Monochlorotriazinyl functional group ⁽¹¹⁴⁾ of reactive dye reacts with beta cyclodextrin and cotton fibre in same bath. Cotton fabric ⁽¹⁴²⁾ was modified with beta cyclodextrin and crosslinked with citric acid and highly increased K/S value and strength. Simultaneous dyeing and finishing ⁽⁴⁸⁾ of jute carpet backing cloth was found in dye fixation, crease recovery and reduction in moisture regain. Innovations resulting from technological advancements represent the best strategy for success in the increasingly competitive textile industry. Fragrance finishing of textile materials has been greatly expanded and used in recent years. Fragrance finishing can be done effectively using exhaust method than any other methods. Recently, fragrances have become available that can be readily formulated into fabrics. Properly designed textiles containing effective, long-lasting fragrances would provide a significant contribution to the textile industry. The proposed research will investigate new fragrance technologies. The fragrance finished fabrics can be used in home textile applications such as wall hangings, table covers, carpets and sofa covers. Fragrance finishing of textiles is one of the processes which enhance the value of the product by adding various odours to it. The world marketplace is constantly changing and so the demand of consumers is also increased. Everyone desires for continuous change .i.e. something different and unique. This increase in demand, as well as tremendous competition in the market, opens up opportunities for value addition to all forms of textile materials. The effective change has to be implemented in the market. By this extensive analysis, fragrance finishing is considered as emerging area and which has tumble-down the textile industry with lively value added finish by incorporating different fragrances into fabrics, leading to the production of fragranced fabrics. This proved a good way to meet important emotional and emotional needs, as well as those of a pure and sensorial nature. The aim of this research is to explore the application of cyclodextrin for the purpose of incorporating fragrance oil into cotton fabrics which will create film forming ability and inherent antimicrobial attributes. 100% cotton fabrics will be used in this study, as 100% cotton is predominant fibre used for underwear and socks producing textiles where fragrance finishing has a great value. In my literature review, the use of beta cyclodextrin as a binder for the application of microencapsulated fragrance oil results in high fragrance retention in 100% cotton fabrics. Therefore, beta cyclodextrin with microencapsulated fragrance oil can be utilised to develop textiles to achieve the necessary antiodour finishing.

Introduction on cotton fibre

Cotton Fibre

Cotton is the oldest fibre used for textile purpose¹. The cotton plant (shrubs) belongs to the family, *Gossypium* and the different species of this family constitutes the different varieties of cotton e.g. ordinary American Cotton is *Gossypium Hirsutum*, Asiatic Indian Cotton is *Gossypium Herbaccum* and *Gosypium Arboretum*, while Sea-Island, Egyptian and Peruvian Cotton are *Gosypium Barbadosense*. There is little evidence regarding when or where cotton first grew. However, some evidence supports the theory that cotton was grown in Egypt about 12,000 B.C. and it was also grown in India at about 3000 B.C. Most authorities agree that India was the principal country in which cotton was widely used before 2500 B.C. Between 1500 B.C. to 1500 A.D. India was one of the important business centre of the world's cotton industry.

Cotton is still a natural fibre of agro-origin that is used most in the world. About 46% of all fibre produced in the world is cotton. Even today cotton is the backbone of the world's textile

trade. The cotton fibre presents many exceptional features like great flexibility, cohesive property, very small thickness, but high strength and wear resistance². Owing to these properties it is possible to process cotton fibres into yarns with greater diversity; from thick yarn for manufacturing coarse and different upholstery / furnishing as well as denim type apparel fabrics to very fine yarns for manufacturing thin and refined fabrics such as Batiste, Marquisette, Muslin, etc. Cotton fibre is widely used for making all types of apparels as well as all types of furnishing fabrics. In textile applications this biodegradable³, environment friendly⁴ and renewable⁵⁻⁸ fibre has some distinct advantages such as moderate dry and wet tensile strength⁹⁻¹³, appreciable moisture regain¹⁴⁻¹⁸, agreeable feel, moderate extensibility¹⁴, varied dyeability and appreciable UV-light stability¹⁹. However, the major disadvantages of cotton lie in its dimensional instability as revealed by wash shrinkage²⁰, poor wrinkle recovery²¹⁻²⁴ and ready susceptibility to microbial degradation²⁵.

The dimension of the cotton fibre varies from source to source; the length varies between 25 to 50 mm or from 0.70 to 1.87 inch, while the width varies from 0.00064 to 0.00089 inch³. The fibre has a linear density about 166 - 220 m.tex. A cotton fibre consists of a single cell closed at one end and appears as a narrow flat ribbon with a low degree of spiral twists (convolution). Chemically, cotton textiles is natural cellulosic textiles containing almost 97% pure cellulose, 1.0% fats and waxes, 0.2% ash, 0.3% nitrogenous matter and about 1.5% pectinacious and other matters. It is free from lignin and hemicellulose in contrast to the composition of jute.

Fig-1.1: Cotton fibre

Physical Structure and Properties of Cotton

The cotton plant grows to a height of 3 to 6 feet with flowers, which develop into capsules, about the size of a walnut. These capsules contain 4 to 8 seeds, from the epidermis of which two kinds of fibres are obtained, i.e. lint fibres (longer and spinnable) and linters (shorter stuffs). After the seeds of the cotton fibre are ripened, the seeds with a covering of fibre (hairs) are put through a cotton ginning operation to separate the longer cotton lint fibres. From 100% of a certain mass of seed cotton received in the ginnery, 30 - 40% is the short cotton fibre (linter), 3 - 5% is the lint, 55 - 65% is cleaned seeds and 1 - 2% is the fibrous waste, Further, the different impurities stuck to cotton fibres have to be removed in order to obtain a good textile grade cleaner cotton fibre. The quality of cotton fibre is based on its breaking strength, maturity, length (or staple length), fineness (linear density), foreign impurities / trash content, cleanliness and colour, if not specified otherwise. Usually the longer fibres are finer and stronger and hence easier to spin giving a smoother and stronger yarn. Depending on the breaking strength and maturity, cotton is divided into seven grades: select (0), the first grade (I), second grade (II) and

so on up to the VII grade⁹¹. However, commercial grading of cotton fibre also depends on the variety of plant species and area of cultivation / origin.

Cotton plant is grown commercially in different regions of the world having stable hot climate, under a varying range of favourable growing conditions. Differences in soil, climate, elevation of land, method of cultivation, and species of cotton cultivated, etc., accounts for differences in different grades and qualities of cotton, which vary widely in their properties and characteristics. There are long, medium and short staple cotton as well as fine, medium and coarse cotton varieties, and hence a careful selection of the fibres is important for different types of yarns and ultimate fabrics to be made.

The cotton fibre is a single cell with an oval or bean shaped cross-section and has a collapsed lumen. However, like all plant cells, cotton also has a distinct cuticle, well developed primary and secondary cell walls with a lumen. The cuticle is the 'very outside' or skin of the cotton fibre. It is composed of waxy layer and is only a few molecules thick. Kier boiling and bleaching during cotton finishing removes much of this cuticle. This enables cotton to absorb moisture more quickly.

The primary cell wall, which is immediately underneath the cuticle, is about 200 nm thick. It is composed of very fine threads of cellulose called fibrils. The fibrils spiral at about 70° to the fibre axis. This spiralling imparts strength to the primary cell wall and hence to the fibre (**Fig-1.2**).

Fig-1.2: Schematic Structure of Cotton Fibre

Beneath the primary cell wall lie the secondary cell wall, which form the bulk of the fibre. Concentric layers of spiralling cellulosic fibrils, not unlike the growth ring of trees, make up the secondary wall. Near the primary cell wall, the fibrils of the secondary wall spiral at about 20° to 30° to the fibre axis. This spiral angle widens to about 20° to 45° (Herman's angle of orientation) for the fibrillar layers nearer to the lumen. Much of the strength and stability of the cotton fibre and hence of the yarns and fabrics may be attributed to these spiralling fibrils. The hollow canal running the length of the fibre is called the lumen. The innermost concentric layers of spirals of the secondary cell wall form its walls. It was earlier full of cell sap, which evaporated when on maturing and since the pressure inside the fibre becomes less than the atmospheric pressure, it collapses inward, resulting in the characteristic bean or kidney shaped cross section. Under the microscope, the cotton fibre looks like a twisted flat ribbon or a collapsed and twisted tube; these twists or convolutions identify the cotton fibre under the microscope.

Cotton is a linear, polymer of 2,500 – 5,000 cellulose units, which consists of two glucose units joined by a glycosidic linkage. The most important chemical and functional groups in the cotton

polymer are the primary and secondary hydroxyl groups (-OH groups). The polarity of these hydroxyl groups gives rise to formation of hydrogen bonds between the -OH groups of adjacent cotton polymers. Van-der waals forces are of little significance. The cotton fibre is about 60 to 70% crystalline and correspondingly about 30 to 40% non-crystalline. The cotton fibre to some extent is chemically resistant towards solutions of very weak acids and alkalis. Its wet tensile strength is higher than its dry tensile strength. It can withstand the action of water and light for a long period of time. However, concentrated solutions of mineral acids and direct sun-rays cause some damage to the cotton fibres. It is surprising that concentrated HCl attacks cotton more easily than H₂SO₄ and thus damage to cotton in concentrated HCl is more rapid ²⁶. The fluidity of cotton for HCl produced hydro-cellulose reaches its maximum after 40 hrs, whereas that for hydro-cellulose produced by H₂SO₄ requires about 300 hours. Treatment of cotton with 18 - 23% (w/w) concentration of NaOH solution under tension causes an increase in the tensile strength and produces a gloss, making the cross section round due to swelling along with removal of convolutions, which is known as mercerization of cotton. Cotton fibre is more susceptible to microbial attack under humid conditions, than that of jute.

Cotton fibre can be bleached to achieve a super white appearance by treatment with 1-2 volume of H₂O₂ at 80-85° C for 1-1.5h in presence of alkali at pH – 10 to 11. However, bleaching of cotton can also be achieved at room temperature by treatment with combination of H₂O₂ and K₂S₂O₈ as dual oxidisers at pH around 9-10 for 4h duration⁹³. Cotton fibre possesses some exceptional features with respect to its use for textile purpose, which include high flexibility and cohesiveness, medium to high strength, good wear resistance, good moisture absorption, easy dyeability, sufficient regularity in length, etc. owing to which cotton yarns of great diversity (thick yarns for making upholstery / furnishing fabrics to very fine yarns for apparel fabrics) can be manufactured easily. Important textile related property profile of cotton fibre is given below in **Table -1.1**.

Table-1.1: Important Physical Properties of Cotton Fibre

Sl. No.	Properties	Range
1	Length of Fibre (Single Cell Staple Fibre) ² (mm) -----	-- -- 25 – 50 28 -34 <i>(specifically for Indian cotton)</i>
2	Diameter / Width of the Fibre ⁹⁴ (inch) (mm)	0.00064 – 0.00089 11 - 22
3	Aspect Ratio	1300

4	Fibre Fineness (Linear Density)	(tex) *	0.16 – 0.22
		(den) **	1.6 - 2.0 (sometimes up to 3.5 den)
5	Specific Gravity ²⁷ / Density (g/cm ³)	-----	1.50 - 1.55
6	Tenacity	(cN/tex)	24 – 27
		g/den	3.0 – 3.8
7	Breaking Extension ² (%)	-----	7 - 8
8	Work of Rupture (g/tex)	-----	1.4
9	Modulus of Torsional Rigidity ²⁸ (dyne/cm ²) × 10 ¹⁰	-----	0.8 – 1.2
10	Initial Modulus (g/den) (Modulus at a 0.1% Extension)	-----	55.5
11	Young's Modulus (dyne/cm ²) × 10 ¹¹	-----	7.2
12	Moisture Regain (%) at 65% RH. and at 27°C ⁹⁴	---	7.8 - 8.5
13	Refractive Index ²⁹	(a) (Parallel to fibre axis)	----- ----- 1.578
		(b) (Perpendicular to fibre axis)	----- ----- 1.532
		(c) Bi-refringence (Double refraction)	----- ----- + 0.046
14	Swelling in Water ²⁸	(a) Longitudinal (%)	----- ----- 1.1
		(b) Cross sectional (%)	----- ----- 21
		(c) Volumetric (%)	----- ----- 40

15	Stiffness index ²⁸	g/den	44
		g/tex	394
16	Specific Heat ²⁸ (cal/g/ ⁰ C)	-----	0.319
17	Dielectric Constant ²⁸ (at 2KHz), 65% R.H	-----	4.7
18	Thermal Conductivity ²⁸ (cal/sec/cm ² / ⁰ C/cm)	-----	1.67×10^{-4}
19	Electrical Resistance (ohm)	-----	5.6×10^7
20	Coefficient of Friction ²⁸ (<i>inclined plane method</i>)	-----	0.22
21	Crystallinity (%)	-----	60 - 70
22	Herman's Angle of Orientation	-----	33 - 44
23	Degree of Polymerization	-----	2,500 – 5,000

* tex = weight in g of 1000 m of fibre

* den = weight in g of 9000 m of fibre

Chemical Composition and Structure of Cotton Fibres:

Cellulose is a condensation polymer consisting of D- anhydro glucopyranose units joined together in the chain molecule by 1-4-β glycosidic bonds. It is a polymer of good degree of crystallinity³⁰. Native cotton is purest form of cellulose. Although the chief component of cotton fibre is cellulose, any of the constituents commonly found in plant cells may be present in small amounts. These are frequently called impurities, but their influence on the processing and usefulness of the fibre necessitates their consideration. General chemical composition of cotton is already shown. The composition of typical mature cotton fibre varies to a limited extent according to the source; however as per one particular estimate, typical chemical composition of purified cotton fibre is given in below.

Average Chemical Composition (in Percentage of Bone Dry Weight of the Fibre) of Cotton Fibres ^{2, 1,31}

Constituents

Amount (%)

Cellulose	94.0
Proteins or Nitrogenous Matter etc. (% Nitrogen × 6.25)	1.3
Hemicellulose	0.3
Pectins	0.9
Mineral matter (Ash)	1.2
Fats and Wax	0.6
Malic, Citric, and Other Organic Acids	0.8
Total Sugars	0.3
Pigment	Trace
Pectin	0.9
Others	0.9

Cotton Cellulose

Native mature cotton fibre contains maximum amount of cellulose in its purest form. The cellulose content of raw mature cotton fibres ranges from 94 to 97% of the bone dry weight. Scoured, bleached, and dried cotton fibre is approximately 99% cellulose. The variation in the cellulose content of raw cotton fibre is due to soil, climate, variety of cotton and other factors which prematurely interrupt its growth. Carbon (44.4%), hydrogen (6.2%) and oxygen (49.4%) are the three elements found in cellulose³².

Cellulose is composed of glucose molecules and is a polymer of cellulose unit arranged in manner as shown earlier for jute-cellulose. The degree of polymerization of cotton-cellulose is within 2,500 – 5,000. Cotton cellulose contains about 5,000 to 10,000 residues in its macromolecule. The molecular weight of the cellulose present in cotton is approximately 2 million¹.

Low cellulose content usually indicates a high proportion of thin-walled immature fibres, which contain a high proportion of non-cellulosic substances.

Repeat Unit of Cellulose:

The basic material of cotton is cellulose, having an empirical formula $(C_6H_{10}O_5)_n$ and the chemical structure is shown:

Fig-1.3: Structure of cellulose

Fats and Waxes in Cotton

The crude material extracted from raw cotton fibre by chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, or other organic solvents is usually called fats and waxes. It is a complex substance of high molecular weight and is composed of alcohols [n- triacontanol, (C₃₀H₆₁OH)], acid [tetracosanoic acid, (C₂₄H₄₈O₂)], small amounts of fatty acids [palmitic, (C₁₆H₃₂O₂), stearic acid, (C₁₈H₃₆O₂), and oleic acid (C₁₈H₃₄O₂)] and small amounts of sitosterol and its glucoside, sitosterolin. Other constituents reported to be present include glycerol, resinuous material, amyirin (C₃₀H₅₀O), and hydrocarbons, including a solid, probably heptacosane. The waxes are located mainly in the cuticle and primary wall of the cotton fibre¹. Because of the waxes, it is difficult to wet raw cotton. However, they have desirable lubricating properties for spinning, but may interfere with the fullest development of strength in yarns and fabrics, by contributing to fibre-slip. Conversely, increase of as much as 25% in tensile strength have been reported when yarn made of raw cotton was extracted with solvents such as benzene, or subjected to other processes to remove wax³³. The melting point of waxes varies between 68°C to 80°C and they are readily converted into soaps during scouring treatment with alkali solution¹.

Pectins in Cotton

The typical, mature cotton fibre contains from 0.6 to 1.2% pectin; most of it is localized in the primary cell wall. These are primarily calcium, magnesium and iron pectates with some free pectic acid and methyl pectate. These are carbohydrates similar to cellulose and their esterified form is soluble in water. The free acid and its calcium and magnesium salts are not soluble in water but they will be converted into soluble product by alkali hydroxides or soda ash. So these can be removed during alkali boiling or scouring of the cotton material.

Protein and Nitrogenous Matters in Cotton

The total nitrogen content of Egyptian cotton is 0.30% and it varies in other variety of cotton. The proteins in cotton fibre are polypeptides and amino acids¹. This protein occurs chiefly in the

primary cell-wall and the central cavity or lumen of the fibre. The nitrogen is readily removed from cotton in the bleaching process; however no important change in the nitrogen content is observed subsequent to a mild alkali boil. The brown colouring matter of cotton and the dark brown colour of kier liquors are associated with proteins. Leucine or tyrosine was reported in this material and histamine has been isolated in crystalline form in extremely small quantities from the cotton dust collected from card rooms.

Ash (Mineral Matter) in Cotton

Cotton contains about 0.7 – 1.6% mineral matter which is left as ash after cotton is burnt ¹. Raw cotton contains about 1.2% of ash, which is composed of oxides of potassium, calcium, magnesium, iron, sodium, aluminium, silica, sulphur, phosphorus, chlorine, carbon, among others. The ash content of cotton after scouring and bleaching is usually negligible. Washing of cotton with water removes most of the soluble potassium and sodium salts.

Pigment in Cotton

This is responsible for the creamy colour of raw cotton.

Other Minor Constituents in Cotton

Raw cotton fibre contains about 0.8% of organic acids, exclusive of pectic acid.

Chemical properties of cotton fibre

- ❖ Effect of acid- Cotton is weakened and destroyed by the effect of acids; hydrolyse the glucoside linkage of oxygen atom. Concentrated nitric acid, for short time, causes some shrinkage and increase and increase strength and disability.
- ❖ Effect alkali- Normally resistant, when boiled in presence of O₂, oxycellulose form. Treatment with 20% NaOH increase strength and dye ability. Liquid ammonias treatment increase strength, elongation, etc. Both of solution is used as mercerizing liquor.
- ❖ Effect of bleach- All kinds of bleaching agents have its action on cotton. NaOCl and Na-perborate are common. H₂O₂ is least harmful.
- ❖ Effect of organic solvent- Cotton is resistant to organic solvent. So dry wash is possible.
- ❖ Effect of heat- Conducting ironing temperature -150 C. Decompose at 240 C. Ignition temperature 390 C.
- ❖ Effect of sunlight- Affected by infrared cause deteriorates colour becomes yellow.
- ❖ Dye ability- Azoic, Direct, reactive, sulphur and vat dyes arte applicable to cotton substrates.
- ❖ Attack by moth- NO.
- ❖ Attack by mildew- Untreated not starches and gums increase activity.

Introduction on Dyeing and Reactive dyeing

Dyeing

Archaeological evidence shows that, particularly in India and the Middle East, dyeing has been carried out for over 5000 years. Dyeing is a method which imparts beauty to the textile by applying various colours and their shades on to a fabric. Dyeing can be done at any stage of the manufacturing of textile fiber, yarn, fabric or a finished textile product including garments and apparels. The property of colour fastness depends upon two factors namely selection of proper dye according to the textile material to be dyed and selection of the method for dyeing the fiber, yarn or fabric.

Dyeing is the application of colour on fibre in such a manner that colour is uniformly applied and material should possess some resistance to the removal of dyes by water. The fibres should be dyed uniformly throughout their thickness. A method of applying dyes to cellulosic fibres involves the dissolution of the dye in water, entering the fibre material in the dye solution of the dye in water, entering the fibre material in the dye solution and slowly heating the system when the dye dissolved in water is gradually transferred to the fibre because of higher affinity of the dye for the fibre than for the water. The solubility of the dye in water, so very useful in dyeing it on cellulosic fibre, has a disadvantage after dyeing. When the dyed fabric is entered into hot water, some of the dye present on fabric comes out and dissolves in the water. The textile dyeing is not as simple as it seems, it consists of following steps because different components have influence on the process.

1. Dissociation – Association
2. Relative movement of textile and liquor
3. Adsorption of molecules to fiber surface
4. Penetration into the fibre (dye- molecule and water)
5. Diffusion in the fibre
6. Immobilization

Mechanism of Dyeing

In all dyeing processes, the first stage consists in the localization of the dye on the surface of the fibre or transfer of the dye from the aqueous solution or dispersion onto the surface of the fibre. All fibres are composed of macromolecules having linear structure and are characterized by chains having crystalline & amorphous region existing side by side³⁴. The crystalline regions behave mechanically as a rigid wall preventing the chains to move apart, but the amorphous regions permit absorption of moisture and absorption of dyes and contribute to chemical reactivity and swelling of fibres. Dyes reduce the surface tension at a water interface and this implies that there are more of the solute molecules at the interface than in the solution.

The second important stage viz. absorption of the dye or its diffusion into the fibre must take place so that the dye enters the internal structure of the fibre before it is fixed. The absorbed dye molecules enter the fibre structure and gradually penetrate or diffuse into the pores in the structure. Diffusion or penetration of dye in the fibre account for almost whole of the dyeing time. The greater

The penetration of dye into the fibre, the brighter and better is the dyeing. The hydrophilic fibres like cotton and wool swell on wetting with water and the solution of the dye diffuses into the amorphous regions in the fibre molecules and thus gets absorbed. By increasing the temperature of the solution, the dye molecules diffuse faster into the fibre structure. In the case of hydrophobic fibres like cellulose acetate and polyester, water does not swell the fibres and the dye molecules do not easily penetrate the fibre because of the compact structure of the fibres. Water insoluble dyes are used for dyeing these fibres from an aqueous dispersion.

Dyes for Cellulosic and Ligno-cellulosic Fibres

Among different classes of dyes, cellulosic and ligno-cellulosic fibres are mostly dyed with direct, reactive, azoic, sulphur and vat dyes. However, unlike cotton, jute being ligno cellulosic, it additionally takes acid, pre-metallised and basic dyes also. For the sake of understanding the dyeing of jute textiles, it is considered worthwhile to make a comparison of chemical nature / resistance and dyeing characteristics of jute, cotton and wool as depicted in below:

Table –1.2: Chemical Nature, Dyeability and Chemical Resistance of Jute, Cotton and Wool Fibres

Fibre Properties	Jute	Cotton	Wool
Chemical constituent	Ligno-cellulose	Cellulose	Protein (Keratin)
Hygroscopicity	Good (12-13%)	Fair (6-8%)	Very Good (14-16%)
Strength on wetting	Dry > Wet	Wet > Dry	Dry > Wet
Effect of Acids	Little	Reduction in Strength	Little (Resistant to weak acid)
Effect of Alkalis	Adverse (woolenization occur)	Nil (Mercerization occur)	Adverse (Dissolving in 5% KOH/NaOH)
Resistance to Mildew growth	Fair (Mildew is formed on jute goods when stored in moist condition)	Low (susceptible to mildew attack)	Fair (Mildew is formed on wool when stored in soiled condition)
Effect of Sunlight	Colour rapidly changes to yellow or brown	Slight discolouration on prolonged exposure	Colour changes to yellowish white
Dyeability	Very Good All classes of dyestuff as used for cotton, indyestuffs	Good Selected classes of dyestuffs like Direct,	Medium to Good (Selected classes of dyestuff like Acid, Pre-metallised&

	addition to basic and acid dyes.	Sulphur, Napthol, Reactive & Vat.	Reactive)
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Table-1.3: General Dyeing Characteristics of Jute, Cotton & Wool

Class of Dyestuff	Jute	Cotton	Wool
Acid	√	×	√√
Basic	√	×	√
Pre-metallised	√	×	√√
Direct	√√	√√	√
Sulphur	√	√	×
Reactive	√√	√√	√
Vat	√	√√	×
Napthol(Azoic)	√	√√	×
Pigment	√	√	√

√√ -- Most Applicable, √ -- Applicable , × -- Not Applicable .

Dyes are colouring material consisting two chemical groups auxochrome which is responsible for its solubility and chromophore for showing colour and they are generally applied in aqueous medium. Thus, selective dyes are either chemically synthesized or obtained from natural sources may be applied on jute following distinctive colouring methods for different types of dyes applicable for jute and other ligno-cellulosic fibres. However, synthetic dyes are cheap and easily available, though some of the synthetic dyes may have chemical hazards and are not eco-friendly in their manufacturing steps. While, most of the natural dyes are eco-friendly except a few, but is difficult to collect (sourcing), extract and apply and also has shade limitations. A brief introduction on characteristics of relevant synthetic dyes and natural dyes suitable for jute will be helpful to understand this issue.

Dyes

A dye can generally be described as a coloured substance that has an affinity to the substrate to which it is being applied. The dye is usually used as an aqueous solution and may require a mordant to improve the fastness of the dye on the fiber. Dyes are used for colouring the fabrics. Dyes are molecules which absorb and reflect light at specific wavelengths to give human eyes the sense of colour.

Classification of Dyes

There are two major types of dyes - natural and synthetic dyes. The natural dyes are extracted from natural substances such as plants, animals, or minerals. Synthetic dyes are made in a

laboratory. Chemicals are synthesized for making synthetic dyes. Some of the synthetic dyes contain metals too.

Natural dyes

The natural dyes are obtained from animal, vegetable or mineral origin with no or very little processing. The greatest source of dyes has been the plant kingdom, notably roots, berries, barks, leaves and wood, but only a few have ever been used on a commercial scale.

Synthetic dyes

The first man-made organic dye, mauveine, was discovered by William Henry Perkin in 1856. Many thousands of dyes have since been prepared and because of vastly improved properties imparted upon the dyed materials quickly replaced the traditional natural dyes (Buchanan and Rita 1995). The global market for textile dye stuffs is dominated by the disperse (35%), and reactive (28%) dyestuff ranges, together with acid (12%), direct (7%), Vat and indigo (8%), Sulphur (6%) and azoic and other dyestuffs (4%) (Lan Holme 2008).

Synthetic dyes used in the textile industry are broadly classified as follows

Direct dyes

These are soluble in water and have direct affinity for all cellulose fibers. Some will also dye silk and wool. As these dyes, when dyed without additives, do not exhaust well, an addition of salt is required to improve the yield of the dye and to obtain deeper shades. Generally, the wash fastness of these dyes is inferior, but there are a number of after treatments available to improve the wash fastness of the dyeing. Direct dyes dye all cellulosic fibers, including viscose rayon, and most of them also dye wool and silk (Buchanan and Rita 1995).

Vat dyes: Indigo, probably the oldest dye known to man is one of the most important members of this group (Barker 2004). These dyes, which are insoluble in water, can be converted into alkali soluble leuco compounds (colourless), when reduced with sodium hydrosulphite. After introducing into the fabrics, the dye will be oxidized on exposure to air and will become insoluble in water again (Shenai 1999). Previously, the reduction process of the dye was carried out in wooden vats, hence the name vat dyes. These dyes are used to colour cotton fibers. Indigo (plant source : *Indigofera tinctoria*) is a good example for vat dye which is water insoluble and blue in colour when reduced, convert into indigo white which is colourless and water soluble.

Reactive dyes: This is a new class of dye introduced in the market in 1956. They react chemically with the fiber being dyed, and if correctly applied, it cannot be removed by washing or boiling. The main feature of the dyestuff is its low affinity to cellulose. Therefore, large amount of salt is required to force its deposition on the fabric. After this has been achieved, addition of alkali causes the deposited dyes to react with the fiber. Only a successfully concluded reaction guarantees a fast dyeing. Basically there are two types of reactive dyes: the cold dyeing and hot dyeing types (Shenai 1997).

Azoic dyes: The word 'Azoic' is the distinguishing name given to insoluble azo dyes that are not applied directly as dyes, but are actually produced within the fiber itself. This is done with impregnating the fiber with one component of the dye, followed by treatment in another

component, thus forming the dye within the fiber (Shenai 1997). The formation of this insoluble dye within the fabric makes it very fast to washing. The deposition of the free pigment on the surface of the dyed fabric produces poor rub fastness, but once the loose pigment is removed by boiling the fabric in soap, the dyeing becomes one of the fastest available.

Sulphur dyes: The first Sulphur dye was discovered in France in 1873, and further work done by Raymond Videl enabled the manufacture of 'Videl black'. Its outstanding fastness to light, washing and boiling far surpassed any cotton black known at that time. The general disadvantage of the Sulphur dyes is that they produce dull shades and lack red colour. The main advantage lays in their cheapness, ease of application and good wash-fastness (Shenai 1997). In their normal state Sulphur dyes are insoluble in water, but they are readily soluble in the solution of Sodium Sulphide. In this form they have high affinity to all the cellulose fibers.

Mordant dyes: As the name suggests, these dyes require a mordant. This improves the fastness of the dye on the fiber such as water, light and perspiration fastness (Barker 2004). The choice of mordant is very important as different mordants can change the final colour significantly. Most natural dyes are mordant dyes and there is, therefore, a large literature base describing dyeing techniques (Shenai 1997). The most important mordant dyes are the synthetic mordant dyes (chrome dyes) used for wool. These comprise some 30% of dyes used for wool and they are especially useful for black and navy shades. The mordant potassium dichromate is applied as an after-treatment.

Acid dyes: Water soluble anionic dyes are applied to fibers such as silk, wool, nylon and modified acrylic fibers from neutral to acid dye baths. Attachment to the fiber is attributed, at least partly, to salt formation between anionic groups in the dyes and cationic groups in the fiber. Acid dyes are not substantive to cellulosic fibers (Barker 2004).

Disperse dyes: The introduction of a new regenerated cellulose acetate fiber in 1920 led to the necessity of developing an entirely new range of dyes. It was found that cellulose acetate (or Celanese) fiber had hardly any affinity for water-soluble dyes. So a new dyeing principle was introduced. Dyeing with water dispersed coloured organic substances. These finely colored particles are applied in aqueous dispersion to the acetate material and actually dissolved in the fibers (Buchanan and Rita 1995).

Oxidation dyes: These are not dyestuffs in the same sense as other soluble or disperse dyes, but because of their exceptional fastness to light and washing they are of great importance. The most important member of this group is produced by oxidation of aniline and it is used much in the dyeing of fur and leather goods (Buchanan and Rita 1995).

Mineral and pigment dyes: Although it is preferable to use water soluble dyes in textile dyeing for two reasons, ease of application and greater softness of the fabric, there are two processes where pigment colouration is used (Shenai 1997). Mineral khaki Cotton army equipment, where it is used because of its cheapness and because it also renders fabric resistant to rotting and attack by insects in damp conditions.

Synthetic resin printing: The introduction of heat setting synthetic resins has opened new fields in textile printing. Mineral and organic pigments, as used in paint manufacture, can now be applied to any fabric and rendered wash fast after heat treatment.

Reactive Dyes

History of Reactive dyes

Reactive dyes were conceived and introduced by Stephen and Rattee (I.C.I., U.K) in 1956-57 for cotton dyeing. Reactive dyes are so called because they react chemically with the fibre to form a covalent bond between dye and fibre³⁴. The energy required to break this bond is similar to that required to degrade the substrate itself, thus accounting for the high wet fastness of these dyes. Natural cellulosic (cotton), protein (wool and silk) and synthetic (Nylon) fibres can be dyed with reactive dyes.

Based on the application temperature, reactive dyes are classified into two groups. One is termed as “Cold Brand Reactive Dye” as it is applied at normal ambient temperature (30°C) and the other is termed as “Hot Brand Reactive Dye” as it is applied at a temperature of 80-85°C. Cold and hot brand reactive dyes are marketed in India by different reputed companies including Atic Industries Ltd., Gujarat under the trade name of ‘Procion-M’ and ‘Procion-H’ respectively. In addition to the above two brands, “High Exhaustion Reactive Dye” is also popular in the market under the trade name of ‘Procion-HE’. The application process of these ‘Procion-HE’ dyes is similar to that ‘Procion-H’ dye. Procion-‘M’ and H, both are reactive dyes containing chloro-triazine based reactive group. But there are some cold brand reactive dyes having vinyl-sulphone reactive groups under the brand name of ‘Remazol dyes’. Recently, fluoro-triazine based reactive dyes are also gaining popularity for high exhaustion. Cibacron-S/SW reactive dyes from CIBA are also claimed to have higher light fastness and are especially suitable for cotton and jute products. It is observed that though jute can be dyed with any of the M, H and HE brand of reactive dyes, some dichloro-triazine dyes show relatively poor light fastness on jute, while better overall fastness properties of bi-functional HE or ME brand reactive dyes on jute is also observed. Hence, HE brand dyes should be preferred for obtaining fast shade on jute from an ecological view point.

The first fibre-reactive dyes were designed for cellulose fibres, and they are still used mostly in this way. There are also commercially available fibre-reactive dyes for protein and polyamide fibres. In theory, fibre-reactive dyes have been developed for other fibres, but these are not yet practical commercially³⁴.

The first fibre-reactive dyes contained the 1,3-5-triazinyl group, and were shown by Rattee and Stephen to react with cellulose in mild alkali solution. No significant fibre degradation occurred. ICI launched a range of dyes based on this chemistry, called the Procion dyes. This new range was superior in every way to vat and direct dyes, having excellent wash fastness and a wide range of brilliant colours. Procion dyes could also be applied in batches, or continuously.

Reactive dyes first appeared commercially in 1956, after their invention in 1954 by Rattee and Stephens at the ICI Dyestuffs Division site in Blackley, Manchester, UK.

Different Components of the Reactive dye

Fig-1.4: Schematic structure of reactive dye

Fig-1.5: Structure of reactive dye

- The chromogen is as mentioned before (azo, carbonyl or phthalocyanine class).
- The water solubilising group (ionic groups, often sulphonate salts), which has the expected effect of improving the solubility, since reactive dyes must be in solution for application to fibres.
- The bridging group links the chromogen and the fibre-reactive group. Frequently the bridging group is an amino, -NH-, group. This is usually for convenience rather than for any specific purpose.

Fig-1.6: Reaction between reactive dye and cellulose

Properties of Reactive Dyes

Physical/ chemical Properties

- ❖ Chemical Structure Mostly triazinyl and vinyl sulfone derivatives of monoazo and acid chlorid compounds, characteristically small and simple molecular structures. Anionic in electrostatic nature.
- ❖ Physical state used as solutions. Depends on base compounds.

- ❖ **Molecular Weight** Low generally, ranges 69-211 g/mole. The higher the MW the more costly the dyeing because more dye has to be used to produce the same shade.
- ❖ **Water Solubility** Generally very good. Sometimes modified to lower solubility.
- ❖ **Hydrolysis** Dye-fiber bond is hydrolyzed by strong acids or bases the more reactive dichloro and trichloro phirimidine are especially hydrolysis prone. During the application of conventional reactive dyes. 15-40% of the dye is hydrolyzed.
- ❖ **Spectra** Have very bright shades owing to their very narrow and high absorption bands which result from their simple structures.
- ❖ **Bonding Types** Covalent bond to fiber substrate. Vinyl sulfones form amino bonds with silk, wool and ether bonds to cellulose. Acid chlorides form amide bonds with wool and ester bonds with cellulose's.

Application Properties of Reactive Dyes

- ✚ Leveling Very good.
- ✚ Exhaustion Good
- ✚ Migration Extremely good
- ✚ Acid fastness Dye-fiber is hydrolyzed
- ✚ Alkali fastness Fair to good. Index 3-5.
- ✚ Light fastness Very good. Index 5-6.
- ✚ Coloring fastness Limited.
- ✚ Wash fastness Very good. Index 4-5.
- ✚ Perspiration fastness Good. Index 4-5.
- ✚ Useful colors Full range of colors from extremely light to heavy darks. No fluorescent shades.
- ✚ Rate of dyeing Very rapid.
- ✚ Dyeing process Exhaust.
- ✚ After treatment Soaping and rinsing to remove hydrolyzed dyestuffs

Reactive groups

Following are the reactive groups found in reactive dyes:

Name	General structure
Mono chloro-s-triazine dyes	
Dichloro-s-triazinyl dyes	

Trichloro Pyrimidyl dyes.	
Tri fluoro pyrimidyl dyes	
Fluro chloro pyrimidyl dyes	
Pyrimidyl dyes	
Phthalazine dyes	
Bifunctional dyes Monochloro triazine - Vinyl sulphone dyes	
Vinyl sulphone dyes	$DSO_2 - CH = CH_2$
Acrylamide dyes	$D - NH - CO - CH = CH_2$

Characteristics of reactive group of reactive dye

The characteristics of reactive group of reactive dyes are mentioned below:

- 1) The reactive system doesn't contribute to the color of the dye which is determined by the chromogenic part of the reactive dye.
- 2) The reactivity of the reactive dyes determined by the presence of reactive groups such as halogens, vinyl sulphone, vinyl-acrylamide and vinyl sulphonamides. Reactivity also depends on the no of N atom on the reactive group bearing heterocyclic part.
- 3) The fluoride radical has the least reactivity as its bond energy 102 Kcal/gm. So drastic conditions are required for bringing about the reaction.
- 4) Iodide radicals are most reactive among the halides. But Iodo and Bromo reactive dyes are so reactive that they hydrolysed very rapidly in aqueous solutions.
- 5) The chloro group is preferred commercially as its price is low and its reactivity lies midway between that of other groups.

6) The reactivity of the dye may be considerably increased by attaching chloro group to monochlorotriazine ring. Thus the dichloro reactive dyes are known as cold dyeing reactive dyes.

7) The reactivity of the monochlorotriazine dyes may further increased by replacing the chloro group by a quaternary ammonium radical.

8) When the chloro group is replaced by the sulphonate ($-SO_3 Na$) group both solubility and reactivity of the dye are increased.

9) When thio sulphate group ($-S-SO_3 Na$) is attached affinity decreases and become unsuitable for application in exhaustion method. But suitable for pad-cold fixation technique.

10) The molecular weight of reactive dyes varies between 69 and 211. The molecular weight of the reactive systems contiguities the cost of the dye.

12) By replacing one of the nitrogen atoms of the triazine by a carbon atom the reactivity of the reactive group decreases.

Criteria of cellulose for attaching reactive dyes:

The chemical structure of cellulose macro molecule is given below:

In cellulose macro molecule glucose units are linked through oxygen bridges formed between C1 position of glucose and C4 position of adjacent glucose unit. Each glucose unit contains one primary hydroxyl group at C6 position and two at second hydroxyl group at $-CHOH$ position at C2 and C3 positions. Now the following things are considered:

Primary hydroxyl group is supposed to be more acidic than C3 hydroxyl group under suitable alkaline condition and hence more reactive.

C2 hydroxyl group is more active while the additional hydroxyl group of C4 position is the least reactive.

The reaction between reactive group and cellulose takes place predominantly with primary hydroxyl group and that with secondary hydroxyl group to some extent.

Longer carbon chain lowers the rate of reaction.

In case of monochlorotriazine dyes this reaction takes place 15 times more frequently with C6 hydroxyl group at C2 position.

The fibre-reactive group is the only part of the molecule able to react with the fibre. The different types of fibre-reactive group will be discussed below.

Fibre reactive dyes utilise a chromophore containing a substituent that is capable, when activated, of directly reacting with the fibre substrate. The covalent bonds that attach reactive dyes to the

fibres' amine or hydroxyl groups make them among the most permanent of dyes.

The dyes contain a reactive group, either a halo-heterocycle or an activated double bond, that, when applied to a fibre in a weakly alkaline dye bath, forms a chemical bond with a hydroxyl group on the cellulosic fibre.

Fig. Trichlorotriazine is a common reactive group

Its three chlorine atoms can readily form HCl with a hydrogen from -OH or -NH₂, leaving the O or N attached to the triazine ring in place of the amorphous region.

Fig : Chemical structure of Reactive Blue 4

Fig: Chemical structure of a typical fibre reactive dyes

There are different classes of reactive dye :

- i) **Bi-Functional Dyes** are reactive dyes containing mono-chloro triazinyl and vinyl sulphone group as a reactive radical and useful for dyeing of cellulosic fibres. These colours are suitable for exhaust dyeing, continuous dyeing and printing.

- ii) **Vinylsulphonic Dyes** are reactive dyes containing vinylsulphone groups as a reactive radical . REACTOBOND colours are suitable for exhaust dyeing , continuous dyeing and printing.

iii) **H-E dyes** are reactive dyes containing monochlorotriazinyl group as a reactive radical and high fixation on dyeing fabric blends on polyester/cotton .These colours are suitable for exhaust dyeing of medium/heavy colours as high colour yield.

iv) **H-Dyes** are reactive dyes containing monochlorotriazinyl group as a reactive radical.Those are useful for the printing of cellulosic fibres and viscose rayon. REACTOBOND H-type colours are applied to steaming at 100-105°C.

v) **Dichloro Triazine Type dyestuffs** are reactive dyes containing dichloro triazinyl as reactive group. These colours are suitable for exhaust dyeing and also can be applied to cellulosic fibre at room temperature.

2.1: Scope and Benefit of the present project work:

To study the feasibility of combined dyeing and multi-finishing comparing with conventional double stage dyeing and finishing

To develop and optimize durable fragrance finishing for cotton textiles which may be an alternative invention of artificial perfume.

To study the effective use of beta cyclodextrin as dyeing bath auxiliaries as well as fragrance finishing also.

Advantages of combined dyeing and finishing instead of double stage dyeing and finishing:

One stage reducing

Time saving

Water saving

Heat energy saving

Low vapour -gas -emission

Low labour cost

Environment -friendly

Very low effluent treatment cost

Needs of Fragrance finishing on cotton fabric:

Relaxation

Sensuality

Exhilaration

Happiness

Well being

Stress reducing

High blood pressure reducing

Psychological & emotional improvement

Dyeing and finishing in individual bath is a well-established procedure to the production concern of textile mill. But presently scientist are trying to develop single bath dyeing and finishing where there is great difficulties with proper matching of dyes and finishing chemical although production concern are knocking to the textile scientist for developing method of combined dyeing and finishing. Similarly demand range of aesthetic properties are increasing day by day to the consumer of textile. Once a time people used textile only for covering the body. But now people are more civilized and modern who are greatly addicted to various types of special finishing of fabric such as water repellent finishing, Fragrance finishing and herbal finishing etc. Production concern of textile dyeing and finishing are always searching such type of single stage dyeing and finishing. Because of following reason, dyeing and finishing industry are always suffering to manage the huge processing cost:

1. Huge energy cost
2. Cost of WTP (Water Treatment Plant)
3. ETP (Effluent Treatment Plant) cost
4. Larger production cycle of dyeing and finishing which is involved to worker's salary also.

Present project work will not only minimize the production time of conventional production cycle, but also it will directly minimize the unit cost of the textile end product of any clothing industry. Following successful key point are described below, from where I can propose that there is a great opportunity of the research work of combined dyeing and finishing and it can be established in the textile mill and presently this type of new technique is the urgent demand of textile industry. There is a vast application opportunity in the field of textile industry. Since I have done my research work on cotton fabric and reactive dye, But there is a opportunity of research field by using another natural and synthetic fibre and dyestuff which may create a revolutionary change in the field of textile chemistry

Fahim uddin reviewed⁽³⁵⁾ on benefits of combined dyeing and finishing for water and energy conservation: Mattioli *et al.* investigated the use of water in textile processing in ten selected textile processing industries and identified preparation, dyeing, printing and fabric washing as

the major water consuming processes.³ Water and energy conservation in textile processing are deemed important. It is known that an energy saving of up to 10 percent has been achieved in the textile industry through basic house-keeping enhancement, including energy management and auditing.¹ Textile dyeing and finishing is the major energy-consuming sector. Starting from fiber production to clothing manufacturing, 25 percent of the total energy is consumed in dyeing and finishing. Typical examples for the consumption of energy in the textile industry can be observed in the figures produced for each specialized section of the Japanese textile industry, shown in Table. The energy consumption is different in dry and wet processing, increased energy being consumed in wet processing. The energy consumed in dry processes, such as knitting and weaving, has been found to be of 1.2 kWh/kg, and 6.2 kWh/kg, respectively. However, for finishing, it rises to 17.9 kWh/kg.² Steaming, drying, curing and other heating operations in finishing consume a significant amount of energy. The Asian continent houses a significant number of traditional textile processing industries working as commissioned processing agents for brand producers. Significant opportunities exist in processing at reduced energy and water levels. Research and innovation are used for minimizing water and energy consumption in the design and manufacturing of machines and in the development of finishing and dyeing processes.

A number of approaches are being investigated in textile finishing for developing processes that would consume reduced levels of water and energy. These approaches are based on combining the dyeing or printing with finishing, and combining the two or more preparatory or special finishing processes.⁴ For example, combining dyeing and easy-care finishing has been investigated for cellulose fibers using acid, direct, vat and reactive dye types with dimethylethyleneurea, melamineformaldehyde, ureaformaldehyde, cyclic urea derivatives and nitrogen methylolated finishing agents.⁴ In preparatory processes, oxidative desizing provided combined desizing and scouring using hydrogen peroxide or persulphate. The continuous textile finishing processes are accompanied by drying and curing stages at increased temperature, resulting in emissions of gases and vapors harmful to the environment. Such gas and vapor emissions would be possibly reduced in combined finishing operation. For example, with increasing industrial development, China has become one of the major countries producing higher carbon dioxide emissions than the United States. Realizing the significance of energy and emission reduction, the eleventh five-year plan of China was targeting to reduce energy consumption per unit of gross domestic product by 20 percent, and to cut total emissions by 10 percent for major pollutants by 2010.² Obviously, the idea of performing combined finishing processes attracted interest in textile processing industries for reducing expenses of water and energy and introducing an enhanced environment-friendly technology, provided the desired effects of finishes in fibers were achievable. The possible advantages are summarized .

Table-2.1: Energy consumption (in million Yen*) in the Japanese textile industry¹:

S. no.	Specialized section	Fuel	Electricity	Total	Percentage share in total
1.	Fiber production	32551	21498	54049	21.0
2.	Spinning	3224	44262	47480	18.4

3.	Twisting	219	1660	1879	0.7
4.	Textured yarn production	120	1543	1663	0.6
5.	Weaving	4467	24848	29315	11.4
6.	Knitting	4059	11709	15858	6.1
7.	Dyeing and finishing (knitted and woven)	37661	28412	66073	25.0
8.	Clothing manufacturing	8240	15420	23660	9.2
9.	Others	5959	12000	17959	7.0
	Total	96500	161442	257942	100.0

*1 JPY = 0.0111203780929 USD, exchange rate as on February 12, 2010 (Source: <http://www.bestcalculator.org>)

Table-2.2: Possible Saving in combined Dyeing and finishing operation comparing with double stage dyeing and finishing:

SL. no.	Possible saving Area in combined dyeing and finishing method.	
1	Time	Finish bath preparation
		Overall processing time
		Drying
2	Heat energy	Curing/Fixation
		Washing
		Drying
3	Water	Water in liquor bath preparation
		Water consumed in washing
4	Gaseous Emissions	Curing
		Drying
5	Labor	Overall process performance

A number of cotton articles produced are required to exhibit easy-care and flame-retardant properties. This paper identifies and describes the possibility of combining easy-care and flame-retardant finishing of cotton fabric using combined finish bath containing the finishes and any desired auxiliary. The fabric can be finished through the pad-dry-cure processing sequence. Important finishing agents used in easy-care and flame-retardant finishing of cotton and their effects on the desired properties of cotton are described. Possible objectives in this area may be: To improve the desired effects on the fabric, to reduce energy/water consumption, To reduce the process cost. Any similarity in the finish bath composition, application and processing conditions used would be interesting in developing combined finish processing. Such similarity could be possibly achieved in easy-care finishing and flame-retardant finishing of cotton fabric (Table 3). The cotton fabric might be padded through finish liquor containing the reagents used in easy-care and flame-retardant finishing followed by drying and fixation steps. The important finishing

reagents used in easy-care and flame-retardant finishing of cotton are described in the following sections. Subsequently, studies addressing the possibility of combining the flame-retardant and easy-care finishing are discussed.

Combining the two finishing processes may offer the advantages of reduction in energy consumption, process cost, time and labor provided the desired effects achieved in the finish and fabric performance are similar or enhanced relative to the two processes performed separately. The approach of combining two or more finishing processes was primarily supported by some level of similarity in the type of reagents, and the conditions used in the finishing process. Both the flame-retardant and easy-care finishes of cotton fibers generally require a cross-linking agent, and selected chemicals and auxiliaries. The finish application may be performed through padding followed by drying and curing. Cross-linking agents are used to enhance the binding and laundering durability of the flame-retardant finish. Beside these insightful objectives the project also targeted to reach the following side objectives: To minimize the wastage of dyes, to simplify the dyeing condition, To point out the exact time of fixation of dye stuff for desirable shade.

Achwal W.B reviewed ⁽³⁶⁾ on water repellent finishing fiber quality, yarn formation, fabric construction, textile wet processes, used dyestuff, multi-finishing chemical and consumer practices can all have an influence on the performance characteristics of a fabric. I think Fluorochemical (13) is a unique chemical which confer both oil and water repellency to fabrics by minimizing the surface free energy of cotton fabric. For fabrics to be water repellent, the Surface free energy is very important factor. Pure water has a surface tension of 72 mN/m and solid Surface Free energy of cotton is 44 mN/m. For water repellency, surface free energy of fibre's surface must be lowered to about 24 to 30 mN/m and oil repellency requires that the fibre surface be lowered to 13 mN/m. Regarding this technical issue of surface free energy, using fluorochemical has provided successful benefit.

Fragrance finish for production of cosmetic textiles: In recent years, textile materials have been found in applications in the cosmetics field. A new sector of cosmetic textiles is introduced and several commercial cosmetic textile products are currently available in the market. On contact with human body and skin, cosmetic textiles are designed to transfer an active substance for cosmetic purposes. The principle is achieved by simply imparting the cosmetic and pharmaceutical ingredients into the fabric of clothing so that with the natural movement of the body, the skin is slowly freshened and revitalised. Microencapsulation technology is an effective technique used to control the release properties of active ingredients that prolong the functionality of cosmetic textiles.

Anti-odour and fragrance finishes: The human sense of smell registers not only the quality of different odours but also combines it automatically and often unconsciously with feelings ranging from agreeable to unpleasant. This connection is used in many ways. Perfumed people and merchandise become more attractive and stink bombs are used to the opposite effect. Textiles have a very large specific surface (for example 0.1 to 1 m² g⁻¹). Therefore they attract, adsorb and store various gaseous or volatile substances from their surroundings. This high adsorption capacity can become a problem with unpleasant smelling

substances under desorption conditions. Desorption is accelerated by temperature, time and the possibility of gaseous exchange, for example airing.

Application aspects: Combined dyeing and finishing is one of the most important expected method of a dyeing industry. As cotton dyeing and finishing is mostly in our country by individual bath, these are conveniently used and consumption of chemical and water of different steps is highest in dyeing industries. So judgment of applicability of combined dyeing and finishing is the most interest not only to dyeing industries but also to machine and chemical sellers and students of apprentices who are studying wet processing. In following paragraphs we will discuss the aspects of this project:

Dye sellers are supposed to match the chemical and dyestuff for combination dyeing and finishing of textile goods. It has been found that dyes and finishing chemical of same functional groups are the perfect combination. The reason is that, they have same of nearly same temperature point of exhaustion and fixation. By this project we will establish this phenomenon by experimentation. So discussing the behavior of exhaustion and fixation dyestuff and finishing chemical sellers can suggest the dyeing industries to use the best combination.

Without considering the reactive functional groups of reactive dyes combination, shade matching, dyeing intermediate addition of particular shade becomes complicated. For this reason understanding the behavior of reactive functional group as well as functional group of finishing chemical is essential for dyers in dyeing industries.

Study of behavior of functional groups of reactive dyes is essential for students and apprentices of wet processing. The only window to understand dyes such as reactive dyes is to study the functional groups. The chemistry of the dye is totally depended on the functional group of the dye and functional group determines the exhaustion and fixation behavior of reactive dyes. The application of dyes to substrate also guides by the exhaustion and fixation behavior of the dyes and students must be aware of such projects.

2.2: Literature review on simultaneous dyeing and finishing:

For production of finished cotton fabric various steps are followed. This multistep process requires a lot of energy, time, manpower, chemicals, machinery, water, floor space, etc. To reduce the number of steps and to make the process economic, several attempts have been made by different researchers to generate a technology on simultaneous operation of different processes. Some work has been done on simultaneous dyeing-finishing of jute fabric, but very little has been done in case of cotton fabric.

Pan et al⁽³⁷⁾ have carried out on simultaneous dyeing –finishing of jute fabric using acid dye-DMDHEU resin combinations. Acid dyeing and finishing of acid dyed jute fabric have been carried out by two different process sequences, namely conventional two step dyeing –finishing and simultaneous dyeing –finishing. The colour strength and dye fixation value of dyed finished samples are evaluated by using a colour matching system. Dye fixation value of the sample

produced by simultaneous processes slightly less but K/S value is higher for simultaneous dyeing and finishing. This may be due to some dye reacted with resin on the surface of the fabric. Dyes are held in the fibre by covalent linkages as there was no bleeding after soaping and subsequent treatment with dimethyl formamide. The loss in tensile strength is higher in the case of the conventional process as compared to the simultaneous process.

Direct dyeing ⁴⁶ and anti-crease finishing of jute fabrics were carried out in a single step process under acidic conditions with a view to economise dyeing and finishing. The properties of the finished fabric viz colour strength, crease recovery and wash fastness were comparable to those of the fabrics dyed and finished by the conventional double – step process. Work on optimising the process parameters viz catalyst concentration and curing temperature, was also carried out. The duration of curing was kept constant in all the experiments. Incorporation of acrylamide in the padding bath of single –step process improved the colour yield.

Pandey et al ⁴⁷ studied about single bath dyeing of jute fabric with Sodium Chlorite – 1:2 Metal Complex Dye Combinations. Sodium Chlorite bleaching and 1:2 Metal Complex dyeing of jute fabric has been carried out by three different process sequences, namely conventional two step bleaching –dyeing, single bath bleaching –dyeing and single bath bleaching dyeing with intermediate addition of sodium bisulphite. Computerised evaluation of colour strength and K/S value of dyed samples obtained by the three different processes with several 1:2 metal complex dyes were carried out. It is found that the colour yield and wash fastness characteristics of dyed samples produced by all the three processes are satisfactory. In single bath dyeing process, colour yield depends on nature of dye and the resistance of the dye towards chlorite bleach. Single bath bleaching –dyeing process is simple and economic as it requires less labour, time, energy, chemicals, water, machinery etc. Moreover this process is environmentally friendly.

Simultaneous dyeing and finishing of desized, scoured and peroxide bleached jute carpet backing cloth have been carried out ⁽⁴⁸⁾ using various reactive dyes and crosslinking agents based on dimethylol-dihydroxy-ethylene-urea (DMDHEU) like Fixapret CPN, Fixapret ECOs of BASF and Indosol E-50 Powder (Sandoz) along with some catalysts ($MgCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$) and softening agent employing dry crosslinking method. Various physical properties, such as crease recovery, reduction in moisture content, moisture regain, tensile strength, flexural rigidity and dimensional stability of the crosslinked dyed fabrics are evaluated. It is observed that there exists a direct relationship between resin add-on to the fabrics and significant improvement in dye fixation, crease recovery and reduction in moisture regain. Regarding all dyeing and physical properties Indosol E-50 powder along with various reactive dyes give highly satisfactory results. Fixapret CPN (low formaldehyde DMDHEU based) is found as effective as Indosol E-50(DMDHEU based) Powder.

In a report of Samanta & Singhee ⁽⁸¹¹⁾, ordinary H_2O_2 bleached jute fabric has been dyed with a selective acid dye (1%) and finished with different concentrations of n-methylol acrylamide (NMA) resin and DMDHEU-resin, separately by both conventional two step sequential process and single step or simultaneous process following two techniques of application, namely, pad-dry-cure and pad-steam-cure. Single –step application of DMDHEU or NMA – resin along with 1% acid

dye on H₂O₂ bleached jute fabric shows an improvement in the surface colour strength compared to that of ordinary H₂O₂ bleached jute fabric dyed with 1% dye. Irrespective of the technique followed, the surface colour strength of simultaneous dyed and resin finished jute fabric is found to increase with an increase in the percentage of application of both the resins from 2% - 12% (owf) and beyond which it tends to level off. However the increase in the surface strength is relatively higher in case of single step or simultaneous dyeing and resin finishing by pad steam cure process, for both DMDHEU and NMA-resins than those obtained by pad-dry-cure process. However the improvement in the total crease recovery angle is found to be some degree lower in case of pad-steam-cure process as compared to that obtained by pad-dry-cure process for both DMDHEU and NMA-resins simultaneously applied in combination with the acid dye. There is appreciable improvement in washing, rubbing and light fastness behaviour in case of simultaneous application of both resins and acid dye by pad-steam-cure process for higher percentage of resin application. The mechanism of dye fixation on cotton fabric using single step fixation of reactive printing and crease resistance finishing⁽⁹⁹⁾ has been examined in this review. Monochlorotriazine based reactive dyes can chemically combine with hydroxyl groups of cellulose fabric by a nucleophilic substitution reaction and as a result an ether linkage is formed. In contrast, modified DMDHEU mainly contains N-alkoxymethyl groups and during the finishing process, the most preferable reaction of N- methylol anions is with hydroxyl groups of the cellulose. The developed reaction mechanism indicates that MCT based reactive dyes can be chemically combined with hydroxyl groups of cellulose as well as modified DMDHEU that is cross linked with cellulose fabric in a single step fixation of reactive printing and crease resistance finishing.

Reviewed⁽¹⁰⁰⁾ and discussed the potential of process optimization for simultaneous fixation of reactive printing and crease resistant finishing with the help of desirability function. A single step process for reactive printing and crease resistant finishing of cotton fabric is described. The idea is a model based approach due to the complexity of the chemical and physical operational sequence of the combo process. The optimum conditions, including concentration of dye and crease resistant, fixation method and temperature were also investigated. Evaluations of the process were made with respect to K/S, dry and wet crease recovery, tensile and tear strength, fastness to washing, light & rubbing, resistance to abrasion and pilling. An E-Control fixation at a temperature of 135 °C was proved to be efficient for imparting single-step reactive print fixation and crease resistant finishing to cotton fabric.

Investigation carried out⁽¹²⁷⁾ on bleached 100% cotton fabric using acid-fixing phosphoric and carboxylic acid reactive dyes in the presence of ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate and dicyandiamide show that the dye fixation process results in substantial tendering of the cotton fabric, increasing the degradation with increase in the concentration of the acid catalyst. This study further reveals the feasibility of combined dyeing and resin finishing, the acid fixation

According to Khatri ⁽³⁸⁾ the textile colouration and finishing industry is one of the major contributors to environmental pollution^(39,40). This is mainly due to the discharge of non biodegradable inorganic salts, alkalis, other processing aids and organic matter such as dyes to the effluent. The effluent treatment can play a significant role in reducing discharge pollution.

However, these treatments are expensive and produce highly concentrated solid wastes⁽⁴¹⁾ Therefore, the better approach would be to improve the textile processing technologies and chemistry for reducing the discharge pollution.

Reactive dyes have become a default choice for colouration of cotton textiles, because they provide a wide range of inexpensive bright colours with excellent washing fastness⁽⁴²⁾. The excellent washing fastness is due to the covalent bonding between the fibre polymers and the dye molecules under alkaline pH conditions⁽⁴³⁾. The inorganic salt, such as sodium chloride or sodium sulphate, for dye transfer to and penetration into the fibre and inorganic alkali, such as sodium bicarbonate, sodium carbonate or sodium hydroxide, for dye-fibre reaction are required in substantial quantities to accomplish the dyeing process. Irrespective of the dyeing method using reactive dyes, just about all the salt and alkali is drained to effluent. Such effluents are characterized by high levels of dissolved solids which is environmentally undesirable^(40, 43-45). A number of developments have been proposed for reducing the effluent pollution by cotton dyeing systems with reactive dyes.

Unlike cotton, jute absorbs many classes of synthetic dyes due to its compositional differences with cotton. Hence jute and cotton much differs as dye receptor. For dyeing of unmodified jute with different classes of synthetic dyes has been studied by many workers⁽⁴⁹⁻⁵⁷⁾, specifically to mention some of them are studies on application of direct dyes⁽⁵¹⁾ acid dyes⁽⁵⁰⁾, reactive dye⁽⁵²⁾, sulphur dyes^(58,58) and vat dyes^(58,59) in general including development of eco friendly processes of dyeing with vat dyes . There are some recent studies on development of single bath dyeing processes including single bath bleaching and dyeing⁽⁶⁰⁾, simultaneous dyeing and finishing^(61,62). Minimum application technique for reactive dyeing has also been studied by Chattopadhyay et al⁽⁶³⁾. However, these studies are mostly on either raw /bleached or alkali pre-treated jute material. Many workers have studied the dyeability of chemically modified jute substrate. It includes oxidative treatments⁽⁶⁴⁾, and treatments with hydrazine hydrate/ phenol and treatments with vinyl monomers grafted on jute prior to dyeing with selective synthetic dyes.

Harper⁽⁶⁵⁾ showed a way out for developing the method of obtaining post-dyeable cellulosic materials after the crease resistant finish by cationising cotton textiles using a mixture of reactive quaternary compound having hydroxyl/ chloride moieties and methylolated resins (N-methylol acrylamide or Dimethylol di-hydroxy ethylene urea or their derivatives) for simultaneous cross-linking and cationising, so that it can absorb dye even after this finish. The same may also achieved by modifying pre-oxidised jute/cotton material by further treatment with diamine or hydrazine-hydrate type of compounds, which when is used along with application of methylol-resins simultaneously. These treatments thus produce a cationic fabric with easy care performance and enhanced dyeability for developing post-dyeable (after crease resistant finish) fabrics. This approach finds better appreciation than even simultaneous dyeing and finishing^(66,67) of jute and cotton textiles studied earlier using different types of synthetic dyes. Chattopadhyay⁽⁶³⁾ studied a newer technique of cationising cotton for subsequent dyeing with reactive dyes with less salt or without salt by treatment of cotton with 1,2 dichloroethane followed by methylamine and reported satisfactory reactive dye uptake without the use of salt.

Improvement of the dyeability of cotton with reactive dyes has been reported by Guo⁽⁶⁸⁾ and Gongyi⁽⁶⁸⁾. Guo⁽⁶⁸⁾ studied alkali pretreatment followed by further treatment with DMAC (1,1-Demethyl-3-Hydroxyazetidinium chloride) for the same objectives. Gongyi⁽⁶⁸⁾ reported use of a quaternary ammonium compound (methyltrialkyl ammonium chloride) to chemically modify cotton yarns for improving their dyeability with reactive dyes. Yousef⁽⁷⁰⁾ studied the pre-treatment of cotton fabric with mono and bis-reactive cationic agents and reported that dyeing of such modified cotton textiles can be carried with direct dyes under neutral conditions in absence of salt. Jang⁷¹, Lei⁽⁷²⁾, Burkinshaw^(73,74) and Evans⁽⁷⁵⁾ have also studied and reported chemical modification of cotton with different cationising⁽⁷⁶⁾ agents thereby improving their dyeability^(77,78). Chattopadhyay⁽⁷⁹⁾ have concisely reviewed the work on cationisation of cotton textiles upto 1998 and he has reported an easy method of cationising cotton fabric for low-salt or salt free dyeing with reactive dyes on such modified (cationised) cotton fabric.

Acid catalyzed grafting, polycondensation and crosslinking of acrylamide-formaldehyde (AMF) and simultaneous free radical graft copolymerization of the resin moieties on jute fabric have been studied⁽⁸⁰⁾ by Ghosh, Samanta et al using a combination of $MgCl_2$ and $K_2S_2O_8$ respectively as the (dual) catalyst system. Resin application and finish on jute fabric are accomplished by padding at room temperature, drying at 80°C and polymerization and curing at 150°C. Dyeing of bleached and AMF resin treated jute fabrics with an acid dye and a reactive dye is accomplished following standard procedures using a liquor ratio of 1:100 in each case and colour strength (K/S) value is determined. It is observed that dye ability data in K/S value for different percentages of AMF resin application indicate an lowering in the K/S value or surface dye uptake for up to 6-8% AMF resin application in case of both reactive dye and acid dye. Above 8% AMF resin application, the surface dye uptake follows an increasing trend that finally tends to level off at or just beyond 10-12% AMF resin application. The lowering of both surface and bulk dye uptake by the fabrics with increase in AMF resin application is probably due to higher degree of cross-linking of AMF resin, higher degree of grafting of AMF resin to jute constituents and higher degree of masking of the fiber surfaces consequent to higher extents of film formation on the fiber due to polymerization/ cross linkings effects, all impairing penetration of dye within the fibers.

Investigation has been carried out by Hebeish et al⁽⁸²⁾ to study the technical feasibility of using non-polluting compounds to improve the exhaustion characteristics of reactive dyes. The compounds used in the study are chitosan and a poly acrylamide –dextrin hybrid. The study also designed to determine the optimal conditions for the application of these compounds by a detailed examination of the main factors influencing their use. The dye tests are carried out on 100% bleached cotton using a number of reactive dyes. The factors studied are the concentration of fixing compound, post treatment temperature and time, the concentration of alkalis and dyeing temperature. It is observed that the use of the non polluting compounds improved colour fixation. The extent of the improvement depends on three groups of factors: those influencing the dyeing process: that influencing post treatment: and the nature of the dye. General description of dyeing methods for jute has been reported initially by Rukhana⁽⁸²⁾ and Patro⁽⁸³⁾.

Environment friendly dyeing of cotton with reactive dyes has been critically reviewed⁽⁸⁴⁾. Major developments are in terms of innovations in dyes and dyeing processes for high dye bath exhaustion and fixation with a view to reduce the total quantity of colour in the effluent. The use of bi-functional reactive dyes having high exhaustion and fixation properties, use of low-salt reactive dyes, machinery developments for dyeing at low liquor ratio, pad troughs with reduced volumes, replacement of urea with dicyandiamide, control process etc are some of the approaches for eco-friendly colouration of cotton with reactive dyes. The uses of environment friendly reducing systems for dyeing of cotton with vat and sulphur dyes are also briefly suggested.

Studies have been made⁸⁵ to reduce the amount salt and water, as required in conventional methods, by fixing 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropyltrimethyl ammonium chloride to cotton. Cationic cotton prepared in this way can be dyed without salt and requires less rinsing to remove unfixed dye. The effect of the cationic pre-treatment on dye uptake for three direct dyes are determined using a flow injection analysis dye bath monitoring system. Other properties such as dyeing capacity and binding constant for the direct dyes on cationic and untreated cotton were also determined by selected dyes at equilibrium.

Salt free reactive dyeing of cationized cotton has been evaluated by Montazer, Malek & Rahimi⁽⁸⁶⁾. In this study 3-chloro-2-hydroxypropyltrimethylammonium chloride was used as a cationic agent to cationize cotton fabric by a pad-batch process. The cationized cotton samples were dyed with different reactive dyes containing various reactive groups. The dyeability of the cationized cotton samples with reactive dyes without salt was significantly improved due to an increase in the ionic attraction between the dye and cationized cotton. The results showed that the wash and dry rubbing fastness of the cationized cotton dyed with different reactive dyes are similar to those of the untreated cotton. However, the light fastness of some of the cationized fabric samples was improved.

Salt free reactive dyeing of cotton fabric is studied by many other workers^(87, 88-92) as an effective alternative of electrolytes in dyeing process with a view to lower environmental load/effluent load of a process house. Many compounds containing quaternary ammonium groups or amino groups have been used for physical and chemical modifications of cotton employing both monomer and polymer. Epoxy compound⁽⁹³⁻⁹⁴⁾, chlorotriazine⁽⁹⁵⁾N-methylolacrylamide⁽⁹⁶⁾, choline chloride⁽⁹⁷⁻⁹⁸⁾ etc. are the monomers commonly used in modification of cotton fibre. Due to smaller molecular size, these compounds present good penetrability in fibre and the exhaustion and fixation of reactive dyes on the modified fibre have improved. However, monomers showed low substantivity to fibre, so large amounts of them are applied. Again, some compounds are unstable under the treated conditions and amines with small molecular weight are usually toxic in nature, which restrain their application.

2.3: Literature Review on Water Repellent Finishing

John W. Rowen and Domenick Gagliardi ⁽¹⁰¹⁾ reviewed that an analysis of the theory of water repellency of textile fabrics have been made. The physicochemical basis underlying the wettability, or water repellency, of treated fabrics is discussed. A survey of the laboratory test methods for evaluating water repellency of textile fabrics is presented. A study was made of 'the water-repellent proper- ties of 11 commercial raincoat and 4 mili tary fabric". For this study two of the more recent test methods were examined, the drop-penetration and the contact-angle tests. Two other, and older, test methods were also studied, the spray-rating and the hydrostatic- pressure tests. Several exploratory observations were made in an attempt to determine the mechanism by which water-repellent fabrics lose their repellency when exposed to rain.

Water Repellency ⁽¹⁰²⁾ is more difficult to define because various static and dynamic tests are used to measure water repellency. Generally speaking water repellent fabrics are those which resist being wetted by water, water drops will roll off the fabric. A fabric's resistance to water will depend on the nature of the fiber surface, the porosity of the fabric and the dynamic force behind the impacting water spray. The conditions of the test must be stated when specifying water repellency. It is important to distinguish between water-repellent and water-proof fabrics. Water Repellent Fabrics have open pores and are permeable to air and water vapor. Water-repellent fabrics will permit the passage of liquid water once hydro-static pressure is high enough.

Oil Repellency ⁽¹⁰²⁾ is tested by placing a drop of oil on the fabric and observing whether the drop resides on top the fabric or whether it penetrates. A homologous series of hydrocarbons decreasing in surface tension is used to rate the fabric's oil repellency. The hydrocarbon with the lowest surface tension to remain on top and not penetrate is indicative of the fabric's repellency. The lower the surface tension of the liquid, the better the fabric's resistance to oily stains

Water-Proof Fabrics ⁽¹⁰²⁾ are resistant to the penetration of water under much higher hydrostatic pressure than are water-repellent fabrics. These fabrics have fewer open pores and are less permeable to the passage of air and water vapor. The more waterproof a fabric, the less able it is to permit the passage of air or water vapor. Waterproof is an overstatement, a more descriptive term is impermeable to water. A fabric is made water-repellent by depositing a hydrophobic material on the fiber's surface; however. waterproofing requires filling the pores as well.

Physical Chemistry of Wetting:⁽¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁴⁾ Howard L. Needles & Edward S. Olson reviewed that when a drop of liquid on a solid surface does not spread, the drop will assume a shape that appears constant and exhibits an angle, called the contact angle. The angle is characteristic of the particular liquid/solid interaction; therefore, the equilibrium contact angle serves as an indication of wettability of the solid by the liquid. The interfacial forces between the liquid and vapor, liquid and solid and solid and vapor all come into play when determining whether a liquid will spread or not on a smooth solid surface. The equilibrium established between these forces determine the contact angle θ .

The contact angles observed on ideal, smooth surfaces do not correspond to those found in real systems. Nearly all surfaces exhibit a degree of roughness and textiles, in particular, deviate from

the ideal system. The degree of roughness will strongly change the observed contact angles on real systems. Those finishes that yield when on smooth surfaces will result in much higher contact angles on textiles. Those finishes producing contact angles less than 90° will allow the liquid drop to quickly penetrate into the fabric. This phenomenon is put to good use in repellent fabric treatments since the repellency of textile products appear to be better than the wetting characteristics of corresponding flat films.

For fabrics to be water repellent, the critical surface tension of the fiber's surface must be lowered to about 24 to 30 dynes/cm. Pure water has a surface tension of 72 dynes/cm so these values are sufficient for water repellency. This section will be devoted to describing materials that are used mainly as water repellent finishes. In a later section, it will be shown that some of these can be combined with fluorochemical finishes to enhance both water and oil repellency. Oil repellency requires that the fiber surface be lowered to 13 dynes /cm. Only fluorochemicals are able to function as oil repellents so whatever is mixed with them must not interfere with how they are deposited.

The oldest and most economical way to make a fabric water repellent is to coat it with paraffin wax. Solvent solutions, molten coatings and wax emulsions are ways of applying wax to fabrics. Of these, wax emulsions are the most convenient products for finishing fabrics. An important consideration in making water repellent wax emulsion is that the emulsifying system not detract from the hydrophobic character of paraffin. Either non-rewetting emulsifiers or some means of deactivating the hydrophilic group after the fabric is impregnated with the finish must be used.

Paraffin wax melts and wicks into the fabric when the fabric is heated. This will cause most of the fibers to be covered with a thin layer of wax, especially those that are exposed to water, and the fabric will have excellent water repellent properties. The major disadvantage of wax water repellents is poor durability. Wax is easily abraded by mechanical action and wax dissolves in dry cleaning fluids. It is also removed by laundry processes.

A typical wax emulsion consists of paraffin wax as the hydrophobe, an emulsifying agent, an emulsion stabilizer (protective colloid) and an aluminum or zirconium salt to deactivate the emulsifying agent when the fabric is heated.

Fluorochemical Repellents: ⁽¹⁰²⁻¹⁰⁴⁾ Dr. Charles Tomasino reviewed that fluorochemical repellents are unique in that they confer both oil and water repellency to fabrics. The ability of fluorochemicals to repel oils is related to their low surface energy which depends on the structure of the fluorocarbon segment, the non- fluorinated segment of the molecule, the orientation of the fluorocarbon tail and the distribution and amount of fluorocarbon moiety on fibers. Low surface energy can be described in critical surface tension terms. The relationship between and structure of the fluorocarbon can be seen in the figure 54. The data was obtained by adsorbing monolayers of carboxylic acids onto a smooth surface.

Commercial fluorochemical repellents are fluorine-containing vinyl or acrylic polymers. This is a convenient method of affixing perfluoro side chains to fiber surfaces that can orient air-ward and give a reasonably close packed surface of -CF₂- and -CF₃ groups. For example, acrylic acid can be reacted with a perfluoro alcohol to form the corresponding acrylate ester. The acrylate monomer will polymerize to form a high molecular weight polymer that can be converted to an emulsion. The

emulsion dries to a continuous film, covering the fiber surface. The perfluoro segment is there as a side chain attached to the polymer backbone. Being nonpolar, it will want to orient away from polar forces, thus forcing itself toward the air interface. Heat facilitates the orientation by increasing molecular motion.

The oil and water repellent features of fluorochemical polymers lead to finishes applicable in two consumer product areas, durable rainwear fabrics and stain/soil resistant products. For rainwear products, superior durability to repeated laundering and drycleaning is the major advantage. For stain and soil resistance, the plus features are the fluorochemical's ability to prevent oils from penetrating into the fabric or from soils sticking to the fiber surface. Most fabric stains are caused by liquids depositing coloring matter on the fabric. Water borne stains can be held out by silicone water repellents; however, oil based stains can only be repelled by the low surface energy of closely packed fluorocarbon tails. For textiles that cannot be laundered, e.g. upholstery fabrics and carpets, stain and soil repellency is an important consumer plus. For fabrics that can be laundered or dry cleaned, stain removal is more important than stain prevention. Finishes designed to facilitate soil removal by laundering will be discussed in a later section.

A typical formulation for polyester-cotton rainwear which finish is applied by padding the formulation onto fabric, drying at 120°C and curing 1-3 minutes at 150-182°C. The fabric will give a 100 spray rating initially and an 80 rating after 5 home laundering-tumble drying cycles. An 80 spray rating is expected after one dry cleaning cycle. In addition, oil repellency rating of 5 initially and 4 after laundering or dry cleaning is expected.

One area where fluorocarbon finishes have met with consumer acceptance is soil retardant finishes for carpets. In this application, oil repellency per se is not what brings about the improvement, it is the fluorocarbon's extremely low surface energy which prevents soil particles from sticking to the fibers. The finish provides an anti-adhesive coating to the fiber. To function properly, the fluoropolymer must provide low critical surface tensions and at the same time be hard enough not to deform when soil particles are pressed into it. Carpet soiling is mainly hard particulate matter tracked onto the face yarns by foot traffic, the soil transfers from the shoe sole and is ground into the carpet. Polyacrylic fluoroesters tend to be soft and rubbery. While they provide the needed low surface energy, they in fact worsen carpets soiling because they deform under pressure trapping the soil particle like fly paper traps flies. This makes it even more difficult to clean the carpet. Fluorocarbon finishes that work well as carpet soil retardants have been modified to overcome the flypaper effect. Some are fluoroesters of pyromellitic acid. These products can melt at curing temperature and efficiently spread over the carpet's face yarn. At room temperature they solidify into hard, flexible low energy coatings. The way these finishes work improve carpet soiling are: 1. They reduce the transfer of soil from the shoe sole onto the carpet's face yarn. This is a function of the fluoropolymer's low surface energy. 2. They reduce the work of adhesion between the soil particle and the fiber surface. The particle tends to fall to the carpet backing and not be as visible. Reduced adhesion allows the particle to be more easily removed by vacuuming. 3. Oil repellency prevents oily surfactants from wicking up onto the face yarns from the carpet backing. Oily films on the face yarns speed up the entrapment of foot soil and the carpet will appear to be soiled much

sooner than if the surfactant was not there. Shampooed rugs will appear dirty much sooner than the original unless care is taken to flush out the residual detergent. Fluorochemical treatments improve this tendency.

Surface tension is defined as the interfacial tension between a liquid and its vapor. A very simple method of measuring surface tensions is with a du Noy tensiometer. This technique measures the force necessary to pull a platinum ring away from a liquid. For pure water, the force is 72 dynes/cm. Several classes of chemical agents exist that impart water and/or oil repellency when applied to textile substrates. Some finishes give water repellency only, whereas other finishes impart both water and oil repellency. Water repellent finishes are those which permit the fabric to continue to breathe after treatment, whereas water-proof treatments completely seal the spaces between individual yarns, as in 200 Textile Fibers, Dyes, Finishes, and Processes the case of rubberized or unsaturated fatty acid-cured fabrics (oil cloths). Older water repellent treatments used derivatives of soaps and fatty acids to impart water repellency. Owing to their hydrocarbon nature they exhibit no oil repellency and actually are somewhat oleophilic (oil seeking). Soaps combined with zirconium, aluminum, or rare earth salts and methylol or pyridium salt derivatives of fatty acids were the major water repellent finishes used prior to World War II. With the development of organosilicon polymers after World War II, the methylated polysiloxanes were introduced as water repellent finishes. Also, fluorocarbon finishes generally are preformed organic polymers that have fluorine groups substituted on the side chains. It is important that the fluorine constituents be present at the end of the polymer side chains, with terminal trifluoro-methyl (CF₃-) groupings being most effective. The unique properties of fluorine that enable fluorocarbon polymers to repel water, oil, and water-borne soils have contributed greatly to their extensive use on consumer goods under trade names such as Scotchgard and Zepel. A wide range of oil and water repellent finishes are available for cellulose and are described earlier in this chapter.

Successfully used fluorochemicals ¹⁰⁵ for surface treatment of fabric/upholstery Protector (High molecular weight [MW] polymers), Carpet Protector (High MW polymers), Leather Protector (High MW Polymers), Paper and Packaging Protector (High MW phosphate esters or high MW polymers).

Fluoro-treatments¹⁰⁶ consist of phenolic resins and other copolymer blends such as acrylic (no PFOS: perfluorooctanyl sulfonates) that are applied to carpets during the manufacturing process to protect the fibers from dry and wet soils, as well as water-based and oil-based contaminants. Fluorochemicals work by reducing surface tension of carpet fibers, which causes them to repel soils as well as suspend spills on the fiber tips longer in order to help assist in spot cleaning as well as minimizing the spreading of spills.

2.4: Literature Review On Crease Resistance Finishing:

M A Wei, Z shu-fen and Y Jin-jong reviewed that ⁽³⁶⁾functional fluorinated products are a group of products that express various functions by substituting the site to which a hydrogen atom is usually bonded with a fluorine atom. As can be expected from its position in the periodical table, a fluorine

atom has various unique properties. It has a good track record in development of products by utilizing a perfluoroalkyl-containing structure, the structure wherein all of the hydrogen atoms in the alkyl chain are substituted with fluorine atoms. Fluorochemicals can supply fluorinated surfactants having a hydrophobic group of a generally used surfactant substituted with the perfluoroalkyl group, fluorinated coating material having the alkyl chain part of an acrylic polymer substituted with the perfluoroalkyl group, and so on.

Dr. Charles Tomasi¹⁰⁴ reviewed that woven and knitted goods are 3-dimensional arrays of crimped yarns. Fabric forming processes take straight lengths of yarns and force them into 2-dimensional crimped lengths. The degree of crimp is a function of the yarn size and fabric construction. When fabric is completely relaxed, the crossing yarns will move around in relation to each other until a stable configuration is reached. This stable arrangement, the point where the relaxed fabric no longer shrinks in width and length, is also related to yarn sizes and fabric construction. When stretching tensions are applied to the fabric, the crimped amplitude decreases and the fabric grows in the direction of the stress. Later when the tensions are relieved and the fabric allowed

In polymer chemistry, it is well known that certain types of polymers must be cross-linked before they develop elastic properties. Elastomers are materials that readily recover from deformation stresses. Since the case has been made that chain slippage under moist conditions is responsible for wrinkling, it is logical to reason that cross-linking adjacent cellulose chains should be a way of improving crease recovery. Time has shown that this theory does indeed work so the mechanism for improving cotton's resilience is to cross-link cellulose chains with appropriate reactants.

The hydroxyl groups on the anhydroglucose units of the cellulose polymer backbone are functional groups that can undergo typical reactions involving alcohols. Organic acids, isocyanates, epoxy and aldehydes all react with hydroxyl groups to form their corresponding reaction products. Over the years nearly all known reactions involving alcohols have been investigated as possible cellulose crosslinkers. Formaldehyde and formaldehyde derivatives were among the earliest ones discovered and have stood the test of time in terms of effectiveness and cost. They are still the mainstay of today's chemistry.

History of Crease Recovery: Howard L. Needles & Edward S. Olson¹⁰³ reviewed that in the mid 1920's, the managing director of Tootal, Broadhurst and Lee challenged his research chemists to make cotton fabric as wrinkle resistant as silk. It was known that formaldehyde would react with cellulose, however formaldehyde is not a pleasant material to work with as it irritates mucous membranes, causes runny noses and watery eyes. The chemists discovered that phenol/formaldehyde condensates would also cross link cotton and at the same time reduce the formaldehyde risks. Unfortunately the phenol/formaldehyde resins caused the cotton fabrics to become severely discolored and excessively boardy. Soon thereafter, they discovered that urea/formaldehyde resins also improved crease recovery and did so without discoloring the fabric. While not completely free of formaldehyde odor, these resins could be handled on commercial equipment. From the 1930's until 1961, cotton fabrics were crosslinked with a number of N-methylol compounds to give fabrics that were classified as Wash & Wear or Easy Care fabrics. Several

other names were associated with these fabrics e.g. Crease Resistant, No Iron, CRF etc. The performance of these fabrics were pretty good. As will be made more clear in ensuing discussions, the best balance of improved ease of care properties to fabric strength loss was struck. All of the fabrics were treated at the mill in the flat state.

In 1961, The Koret Company marketed garments with permanent creases. This was revolutionary at that time because the activation of the cross-links was delayed until after the garment was made and the creases pressed in. What Koret did was to impregnate the fabric with the chemicals, carefully dry without activating the cross-links, make, press and then hang the garments in an oven to activate the cross-links. The consumer's reaction to these garments was double edged. They complained about the fact that the cuffs fell off and holes appeared in the sharp creased areas when the garments were worn and laundered, yet turned around and wanted more. The consumer had been freed from the tedious task of ironing their garments. signalling the birth of the Permanent Press era. From the chemist's point of view, the lack of abrasion resistance and weakened fabric was expected since the original garments were made from 100 % cotton. It was well understood at that time that creases set into the fabric prior to curing would be permanent and that excessive chemicals, curing times and temperatures would severely weaken the fabric and drastically reduce abrasion resistance. Nonetheless the industry, sensing a new marketable product, immediately launched into development programs to overcome the deficiencies and still maintain the permanent press qualities. The solution came about quickly. Serviceable garments were made from nylon blended with cotton. Soon thereafter, polyester blended with cotton also provided serviceable garments. At that point in history, polyester was relatively new, expensive and not a truly commercial item. Yarn spinners found that polyester was easier to blend with cotton than nylon, so it became the preferred fiber for permanent press fabrics. The original blend was 35 % polyester, 65 cotton. This amount of polyester provided the strength without interfering with cotton's contribution to shape retention. It can be said that the commercial success of Permanent Press (Durable Press) is largely, responsible for today's position enjoyed by polyester manufacturers. It provided the initial need for volume production which lead to the polymer's more competitive pricing structures, opening up more and more markets.

When fibers are bent or deformed under various environmental conditions and then allowed to recover, the degree of recovery will depend on the morphology and inherent structure of the fiber. Most synthetic fibers show reasonable recovery from such deformation, whereas the cellulose and, to a lesser extent, the protein fibers have poor recoveries, particularly under moist conditions. Crease resistant finishes for cotton and rayon have been developed that give much improved wrinkle recovery properties, whereas crease resistant finishes for wool are still under development, since the process is complicated by felting shrinkage. Crease resistant finishes for cellulose are chemical crosslinking agents and include wash-and-wear and durable press finishes. The wash-and-wear finishes are generally urea-formaldehyde or melamine-formaldehyde resins and are cured on cellulose as flat goods in the mill, whereas durable press treatments consist of cyclic urea-aldehyde derivatives which are partially cured at the mill, after which curing is completed after the fabric is made into a garment in apparel manufacture. Other difunctional finishes, including epoxides, isocyanates, vinylsulfones, and aziridines, have been introduced as crease resistant finishes for

cellulose. These have met with only limited success owing to their higher cost and other deficiencies. Since wool is already heavily crosslinked, a different approach to crease resistant finishing must be taken. The disulfide crosslinks in the textile structures must be chemically reduced followed by a setting treatment with bifunctional reagents such as capped diisocyanate derivatives. Chemical treatments for setting of thermoplastic man-made Finishes and Finishing fibers are generally not used, since heat setting of these thermoplastic fabrics is an effective technique for imparting crease resistance. Urea-formaldehyde resins also are often used on cellulose to impart dimensional stability to the textile structure and to prevent yarn slippage within the structure. Finishes capable of causing interfiber bonding can act as effective stabilizing finishes, although they may stiffen the overall structure.

Cellulose characteristic- ally do not recover well from bending deformation, particularly in the presence of moisture, and crease resistant finishes have been developed for cellulose to improve the wrinkle recovery of the cellulosic fabrics in the wet and/or dry states. Such finishes also stabilize cellulose against relaxation shrinkage induced by mechanical forces during fabric formation. The crease resistant finishes used for cellulose are for the most part derivatives of urea and various aldehydes. These resins chem- ically crosslink adjacent cellulose chains and provide a chemical memory within the cellulose which aids in recovery from bending deformation or wrinkling. The degree of dry and wet wrinkle recovery of the resin-treated cellulose will differ depending on whether curing to achieve crosslinking was conducted in the dry state or in the swollen wet state.

Although crease resistant finishes for cellulose were developed shortly after World War I, it was not until after World War II that they appeared extensively on consumer goods. The finishes introduced in the late 1940s were generally referred to as drip dry or wash-and-wear fin- ishes. The resin-treated cellulose were cured flat while they were still moist at the mill. This required that the treated fabric be permitted to drip dry to achieve the maximum desired recovery effect. Since the fabric was cured in the flat state before being made into a finished textile, the garment did not retain creases placed in the finished garment. Flat set items such as sheets and table cloths can be effectively made crease resis- tant by this process, however. In the early 1960s durable press finishes were introduced. After resin application and partial curing at the textile mill, the treated fabrics were sent to the apparel manufacturer. The apparel manufacturer fabricated the treated fabric into garments which were then fully cured in their finished state to give a textile product that retained its creases and recovered to its finished form after washing and tumble drying. Although it is difficult to make a clear distinction between the resins used for the wash-and-wear and for durable press, certain general-izations can be made. Both types of resins are urea-aldehyde derivatives used in conjunction with possible other coreactants. The reactive func-tional groups in the resins are multiple β -methylol groups which undergo acid catalyzed reaction with hydroxyl groups in adjacent cellulose molecular chains to form bridging crossl inks to its unwrinkled state.

Representatives of the major types of crease resistant resins for cellulose are shown below:

DIMETHYLOL UREA

DIMETHYLOL-N -M ETHYL- TRIAZONE

DIMETHYLOLETHYLENEUREA (DMEU)

TRIMETHYLOL MELAMINE

DIMETHYLOLETHYL - CARBAMATE

DIMETHYLOLDIHYDROXY-ETHYLENEUREA (DMDHEU)

The above resin shows very good reaction for crosslinking with cotton fabric. But such type of resin has formaldehyde release problem. For this reason percentage of application has to be limited for crosslinking & percentage of formaldehyde release has to be limited for ecofriendly finishing. In general, urea-formaldehyde condensates, methylolmelamines, and triazone-formaldehyde resins are used in wash-and-wear finishing. All suffer to varying degrees from chlorine retention and yellowing when in contact with sodium hypochlorite bleaches, which can cause damage to the cellulosic, In addition, the triazone resins give off a fishy odor under moist conditions. The ethyleneurea resins and the carbamates are used extensively in durable press treatments. In general, these resins are less susceptible to chlorine retention and undergo partial cure readily followed by a final cure. Latent or mild acid catalysts including inorganic and Lewis acid metal salts are added to the resin solution to achieve curing of all of these resins applied to cellulose. A gaseous formaldehyde-sulfur dioxide vapor treatment for 100%cellulose has been developed as well as a radiation curing treatment using N-methylolacrylamide. These resin treatments tend to lower the strength and overall abrasion resistance of the cellulosic fibers. Careful control of curing conditions and selection of catalysts as well as addition of softeners to the finishing solution can reduce this effect to some degree. Nevertheless, it has been necessary to blend thermoplastic heat settable fibers such as polyester with the treated cellulose to achieve acceptable wear characteristics. As a result poly- ester-cellulosic blends have made large inroads into markets where 100% cellulosic constructions were found previously. Soil retention on poly- ester-cellulosic blends treated with crease resistant resins has been a problem, and a series of polar hydrophilic soil release finishes have been developed to meet this need, as outlined before in this chapter. In recent years, low free formaldehyde durable press finishes have become important to protect workers from exposure to unreacted formaldehyde. In these formulations the methylol groups are capped with methyl groups, or a formaldehyde scavenger is added to the finishing solution.

(a). Dimethylolethylene Urea (DMEU): The starting material for making dimethylolethylene urea (DMEU) is ethylene urea. a 5 membered heterocyclic, nitrogen compound (imidazolidone-2). It is made by reacting ethylene diamine with urea. Ethylene urea contains 2 N-H groups capable of reacting with formaldehyde and forms a difunctional product. Since there are no other active hydrogen sites, the N-methylolated product cannot self-condense.

(b). Dimethylol-4,5-Dihydroxyethylene Urea (DMDHEU): DMDHEU is the workhorse durable press finish. It and some of its modified versions account for over 85% of all crease resistant chemicals consumed today. DMDHEU achieved this prominent role in 1961 when delay cure processing came into being. In the trade, DMDHEU is often referred to as the Glyoxal resin. This jargon came as a way to distinguish it from DMEU, in that glyoxal was used to make the starting monomer. The starting heterocycle is made by reacting stoichiometric amounts of urea and glyoxal. The reaction is straightforward and can be carried out in regular laboratory glassware. The methylation step is

also straightforward. While the synthesis is shown in two steps, commercially DMDHEU is made directly in one step. Urea, formaldehyde and glyoxal are all combined together and heated. The extent of reaction is followed by monitoring the free formaldehyde content. The product is sold as a 46% solution.

Cellulose crosslinkers can be divided into two categories, those that predominately crosslink cellulose, also known as cellulose reactants, and those that self-polymerize as well as crosslink cellulose (aminoplasts). Both types involve the reaction chemistry of formaldehyde so a review of pertinent formaldehyde chemistry will help in understanding how these auxiliaries work. Formaldehyde is capable of reacting with many active hydrogen compounds, e.g -OH, -NH and activated -CH. The reaction of an amide -N-H with HCHO to form a -NCH₂OH is often termed Methylation because the reaction product is called an N-methylol group. Accordingly urea can be methylolated with up to 4 moles of formaldehyde and the reaction products used as crease resistant finishes. When 2 moles of HCHO is reacted with one mole of urea, dimethylol urea is formed. Being difunctional, it is capable of serving as a crosslinking agent.

Important Features

1. The condensate has an extremely short shelf life. It must be used within a few days after its been made. When formulated with catalyst, the finish bath must be used within a few hours. The solution has high free formaldehyde and will readily liberate formaldehyde into the work place.
2. It is easy to cure on fabrics and imparts outstanding crease recovery. Fabric hand becomes stiffer which is usually undesirable for many cotton fabrics. Most rayon fabrics are very limp compared to cotton so the added firmness is desirable.
3. Finished fabrics have poor durability to repeated laundry. Crease recovery is lost because the crosslinks have poor stability to hydrolysis.
4. The finish adversely affect the light fastness of direct and fiber reactive dyes.
5. The finish reacts with hypochlorite bleaches to form a reaction product which decomposes with heat to form HCl. Acid degradation of the cellulose scorches the fabric and causes it to become very much weaker (tender).
6. Finished fabric is prone to liberate formaldehyde odor. Released formaldehyde is high. Overcured fabrics also develop an unpleasant fish odor.

The commercial product has low free formaldehyde which makes it easy to handle in a finishing plant. It does not liberate formaldehyde from the reverse reaction as rapidly as do other reagents. The product has extremely good shelf life and even finish baths with catalyst present are stable for prolong periods of time. Fabric temperatures exceeding 1300 C are needed before the cross-linking reaction takes place. This feature is responsible for why it has become the dominate DP finish. The reactant does not crosslink on storage so fabrics can be left in a sensitized state (uncured) for over six months before post curing. Hydrolysis resistance of the cellulose crosslinks are much better than DMEU so durability to laundering is very acceptable. Resistance to chlorine bleach is also acceptable. While this finish reduces the light fastness of direct and fiber reactive dyes, it is better than DMEU.

Release Formaldehyde problem of such resin treated in Fabrics

1. Free Formaldehyde: Free formaldehyde is defined as the uncombined monomeric formaldehyde that exist in finish solutions. Usually, its sources are stoichiometric excesses that may have been included in the resin manufacturing step to drive the reaction and/or the amount arising from the equilibrium established by the particular reactants. Free formaldehyde is determined by suitable analytical titration procedures.

2. Formaldehyde Release: Formaldehyde release, not to be confused with free formaldehyde, is the amount of formaldehyde that escapes from a fabric into the atmosphere. It is determined by the mason jar method, AATCC Test Method 112. The method calls for suspending 1 gram of fabric in a sealed quart mason jar containing distilled water in the bottom. The jar is incubated for 20 hours at 49.0 C. The formaldehyde that collects in the water is analyzed and the results are reported in ppm or $\mu\text{g/g}$ fabric. There are other fabric test methods used for determining formaldehyde in fabric. For example, the Japanese method calls for titrating the free formaldehyde in the fabric by a cold procedure. The box below shows a comparison of the results obtained on the same piece of fabric tested by the different analytical procedures. The results obtained by the mason jar method are much higher than the Japanese method so the reader is cautioned to be sure of the details of what is being reported before jumping to conclusions.

Linkages Responsible for HCHO Release: There are three major types of formaldehyde linkages that are responsible for released formaldehyde. The most labile linkage is cellulose hemiformal. Cellulose readily picks up formaldehyde from the atmosphere and give a positive reading by the jar test. Free formaldehyde in solutions and formaldehyde made available from the N-methylol equilibrium are also sources. A second linkage that can be a source of gaseous formaldehyde is uncured resin or pendant N-methylol groups. These linkages are rather labile and easily revert back to their starting materials. It is difficult to cure 100% of the resin that is applied and make sure there are no pendant N-methylol groups left. Therefore, all fabrics will have some, and the amount will depend on how well the fabric was cured. The third source of released formaldehyde is the crosslink itself. The finish will decompose under the jar test conditions and liberate CH_2O .

Methods of reducing Formaldehyde Release: A number of approaches have been tried to reduce HCHO release. These approaches range from afterwashing the cured fabric to developing non-formaldehyde reactants. The section that follows will review some of the more important developments.

Scavengers are defined as materials capable of reacting with monomeric formaldehyde and tying it up. Scavengers are added to the finish formulation and can be grouped into two categories, nitrogenous compounds and alcohols. The two groups control HCHO by different mechanisms. The nitrogenous additives not only react with HCHO to form N-methylols, but also react with the pendent N-methylols to form methylene bridges. Essentially they compete with the cellulose and when enough additive is present to lower HCHO release, cellulose cross links are reduced resulting in lower DP performance. Additional N-H groups are in the fabric further affecting chlorine damage and reduced lightfastness. Effective nitrogenous scavengers are urea, ethylene urea and carbonyldiurea.

High boiling alcohols also act as scavengers and lower HCHO release. Their mechanism involves capping pendent N-methylol groups. The capped end-groups are more stable than the

hydroxymethyl so the equilibrium of the reverse reactions is shifted. These additives also compete with crosslinking so DP ratings are somewhat diminished. Not having N-H groups, however, mitigates against chlorine resistance and lightfastness problems. Effective alcohol scavengers are nitroalcohols, ethylene glycol, diethylene glycol and sorbitol.

B. Modified DMDHEU: Modifying DMDHEU has been the most successful approach for reducing HCHO release. Among the first modified versions were those made from purer starting materials and rigidly controlling the stoichiometry. Later versions led to alkylated DMDHEU and two types have become commercially important products, methylated and glycolated DMDHEU.

Methylated DMDHEU: DMDHEU has 4 reactive hydroxyls. The 4,5-ring hydroxyls are as reactive to alkylation as are the pendant N-methylols. Alkylating with methanol can replace anywhere from 1 to 4 -OH groups with -OCH₃. Partially methylated DMDHEU refers to products where an average of two methoxy groups are attached. Fully methylated refers to products where all four have been reacted. To accomplish the latter, the reaction must be driven to completion by removing water of reaction. This involves a distillation step making the fully methylated product more expensive.

Glycolated DMDHEU is made by reacting 2 moles of diethylene glycol, (DEG), with 1 mole of DMDHEU. It is often referred to as a ULF (ultra low formaldehyde) reactant. This product evolved from the successful experiences noted when DEG was added to the finish formulation. Precapping before it is applied insures that there are no pendent N-methylol groups so the HCHO release is even lower. The DEG still functions as a leaving group during cure so crosslinking with cellulose is not severely impaired.

Non formaldehyde DP finishes: Impending OSHA regulations and several state regulations require that products manufactured with formaldehyde containing components be labeled with a warning label. Even though the use of formaldehyde will not be completely banned, compliance with the safety aspect requires a lot of effort and expense, e.g. work place monitoring and worker medical surveillance. Industry management would prefer to manufacture their products without HCHO rather than put up with the hassle of dealing with the regulations. Several countries such as Japan and Germany have even more stringent HCHO requirements than the USA. Because of this, there has been and continues to be interest in non-formaldehyde DP finishes. The section that follows describes two products that fit the description "non-formaldehyde" finishes.

Dimethyl-4,5, Dihydroxyethylene UREA (DMeDHEU), DMeEU is the reaction product of dimethyl urea and glyoxal. The -4,5- ring hydroxyls are reactive with cellulose and form the same ether links as do the N- methylol groups. Even though the electronic configuration around the ring hydroxyls are the same as the pendant N-methylol groups, the reaction is much more sluggish because of steric hindrance and therefor require harder cures and more and stronger catalyst. Even with all this, the DP results are not near as good as the more conventional reactants. The product is more expensive; however, the fabric can truthfully be labeled as formaldehyde-free.

P Bajaj reviewed that ⁽¹⁰⁸⁾ N, N-1,3 dimethylol-4,5 dihydroxyethylene urea (DMDHEU), using magnesium chloride as the acid catalyst to initiate chemical crosslinking of cellulose chain molecules. Crosslinking occurred within the accessible regions (i.e. the amorphous resion).

Fig-2.1: Structure of DMDHEU

MONA VERMA¹, KRISHNA KHAMBRA², NIRMAL YADAV³ & RAJVIR SINGH⁴ reviewed ⁽¹⁰⁹⁾ that the Indian Cotton Textiles Industry has an overwhelming presence in the economic life of the country. It provides direct employment to over 35 million people. Workers who work in textile finishing sectors daily come in direct or indirect contact with hazardous chemicals released by the finishing process such as formaldehyde finish applied to the cotton fabric for improving the wrinkle resistance of the fabric. In many countries, cotton is one of the primary economic bases, providing employment and income for millions of people involved in its production, processing and marketing. Cotton has many qualities which make it suitable for apparel purpose such as absorbency, strength, easily spinnable, washability, good conductor of heat which leads to comfort in wear during hot weather. Free formaldehyde is released during wrinkle resistant finishing process, is carcinogenic in nature as well as irritates the skin of wearer. There is need of such type of finish which is free from formaldehyde and ecofriendly in nature for minimizing the health hazards occur during the finishing process. It is found that chitosan citrate is a non-formaldehyde durable press finish to produce wrinkle resistance. Chitosan has many biological properties such as biocompatible in terms of natural polymer, biodegradable, safe and non-toxic. It is a step toward ecofriendly textile because it is the demand of the day.

U.D. Akpabio reviewed on Cellulosic ⁽¹⁰⁷⁾ (cotton) fabric was treated by immersion in 50.8% solid urea-formaldehyde (U-F) resin synthesized at 25°C, 40°C, 50°C, 60°C, 70°C, 80°C and 100°C. The resin retention and its effects on the water absorbent capacity of the treated fabric at these temperatures and one atmosphere were studied. The results showed that the retention of the U-F resin on cotton fabric increased with the synthesis temperature until a maximum retention of 1.93% at 70°C. The water absorbent capacity decreased as the synthesis temperature increased. For U-F resin synthesized at 70°C with the same solid content, it was observed that the water absorbent capacity decreased as the time of immersion of the treated fabric in water increased. It was then concluded that U-F resin finish synthesized at 70°C at 50.8% solid content and used in treating cotton fabric at the same temperature for a minimum of 25 seconds effectively decreased the water absorbent capacity of the hydrophilic cellulosic fabric, thereby improving its water repellency

2.5: Literature Review on Aroma Finishing

Uses of Dextrin and Cyclodextrin for microencapsulation

Dr. Charles Tomasino¹⁰⁴ reviewed that natural starches are not very soluble in cold water. Cooking is necessary to get the starch granules to form a homogenous solution. Typically the starch granules are stirred in cold water and kept suspended by high speed mixing. As the temperature is raised, water penetrates through the amylopectin membrane solubilizing amylose. The granules swell as more and more water diffuses in enlarging to many times their original dimensions. The viscosity of the solution increases as the granules swell, reaching a maximum at the point where the swollen granules are crowding against each other. Prolonged heating and mechanical shearing cause the swollen granule membrane to rupture allowing the solubilized amylose to spill into the bulk of the solution. At this point the viscosity begins to fall off, finds a stabilized level and remains there. The starch solution can be considered as solubilized amylose molecules intermingled with ruptured swollen fragments of the amylopectin membrane. Dextrins are made by heating dry starch with a mineral acid. White dextrin is made by heating at moderate temperatures and yellow dextrin is made by heating at higher temperatures with less acid. The degree of hydrolysis is higher than for thin boiling starch so dextrin solutions have lower viscosities.

Fig-2.2: Structure of Dextrin⁽¹¹²⁾

M. Sundrarajan and Rukmani reviewed¹⁰⁴ that Cyclodextrins are a group of structurally related natural products formed during bacterial digestion of cellulose. These cyclic oligosaccharides consist of (α -1,4)-linked α -D-glucopyranose units and contain a somewhat lipophilic central cavity and a hydrophilic outer surface. Due to the chair conformation of the glucopyranose units, the cyclodextrins are shaped like a truncated cone rather than perfect cylinders. The hydroxyl functions are orientated to the cone exterior with the primary hydroxyl groups of the sugar residues at the narrow edge of the cone and the secondary hydroxyl groups at the wider edge. The central cavity is lined by the skeletal carbons and ethereal oxygens of the glucose residues, which gives it a lipophilic character. The polarity of the cavity has been estimated to be similar to that of an aqueous ethanolic solution. The natural α -, β - and γ -cyclodextrin consist of six, seven, and eight glucopyranose units, respectively.

The natural cyclodextrins, in particular β -cyclodextrin, are of limited aqueous solubility meaning that complexes resulting from interaction of lipophiles with these cyclodextrin can be of limited solubility resulting in precipitation of solid cyclodextrin complexes from water and other aqueous systems. In fact, the aqueous solubility of the natural cyclodextrins is much lower than that of comparable acyclic saccharides.

This is thought to be due to relatively strong intermolecular hydrogen bonding in the crystal state. Substitution of any of the hydrogen bond forming hydroxyl groups, even by lipophilic methoxy functions, results in dramatic improvement in their aqueous solubility. Cyclodextrin derivatives of pharmaceutical interest include the hydroxypropyl derivatives of β - and γ -cyclodextrin, the randomly methylated β -cyclodextrin, sulfobutylether β -cyclodextrin, and the so-called branched cyclodextrins such as glucosyl- β - cyclodextrin.

Devinderkaur and Neelam Grewal⁽¹¹⁰⁾ reviewed that the cyclodextrin capacity to form inclusion complexes is known for a long time, this property being used in textile industry to obtain products with applications in increasing wear comfort and realization of medical textiles. Yet, there is always the possibility to find new applications of these complexes, either by their permanent fixation on textiles, or by making them environmentally friendly and increasing the performances of some processes from the textile industry or waste water treatment. What concerns the increase of wear comfort, the cyclodextrins serve to improve the wettability and antistatic properties, by catching the smells and perspiration, or to release for a long time the previously encapsulated perfumes. In the medical area, with a view to obtain a slow release of the antibiotics and based on the cyclodextrins capacity to form reversible inclusion complexes with them, operational vascular prostheses were created, which diminish the hazard of post- surgery infections. Based on the same principles, transdermal treatments were carried out, for example the realization of a bandage able to release natrium diclophenac as an anti- inflammatory medicine. The cyclodextrins are also used to release disinfecting or cicatrizing substances at the place were bandages are applied to cure various injuries, and for the realization of textiles with anti- microbial activity which resists to a number of washings. In the field of textile chemical technology optimization, the cyclodextrins are used to remove the surfactants from the material or to inactivate them in liquid phase, to intensify the enzyme processes or as balancers in dyeing with reactive pigments.

Fig-2.3: Structure of cyclodextrin⁽¹¹²⁾

The general features of β -cyclodextrin⁽¹¹¹⁾ and their applications in the textile industry have been reviewed. The use of β -cyclodextrin in the textile industry is of great significance due to its wide range of application. One of the key aspects is the attachment technique of β -cyclodextrin to the textile's surface. This review deals with this in depth. Some quantification and characterization methods of Textile- β -cyclodextrin are discussed. In the last few years, the new direction in textile research is the functionalisation of textile systems. It is believed that β -cyclodextrin will play a very important role in these new developments. β -cyclodextrin can act as a host for various guest molecules. This enables the development of fabrics that release chemical compounds such as fragrances and antimicrobial agents. It is concluded that there are many possibilities for the development of new textile products with advanced properties based on β -cyclodextrin.

The technical production of cyclodextrins⁽¹¹²⁾ can be divided into four key phases:

1. Cultivation of the micro-organism that produces the CGTase.
2. Isolation of the enzyme, concentration and purification.
3. Enzymatic degradation of starch to cyclodextrins by the CGTases.
4. Separation of the cyclodextrins, purification and crystallization.

The reaction takes place in a 30% starch suspension. Since this starch suspension is highly viscous and the yield would be low, the suspension is initially treated with α amylase, which partially hydrolyzes the starch. The treatment is optimized to obtain the greatest possible yield of cyclodextrins. The partial degradation of the starch alters its solubility and viscosity. When the optimum degree of starch hydrolysis has been reached, the reaction is terminated by heating, which thermally decomposes the enzyme α -amylase.

Fig-2.4: Corn is the raw material that provides the starch for cyclodextrin production

Fig-2.5: Specific enzymes facilitate the production of pure cyclodextrins

Detailed studies of toxicology⁽¹¹²⁾, mutagenicity, teratogenicity and carcinogenicity were indicated that the cyclodextrin can affect the human organism only at extremely high concentrations. According to OECD (Organization for economic co-operation and development) test, these cyclodextrin derivatives have no irritating or sensitization effects and it was also proved by the clinical test of T-shirt. Cyclodextrins^(113,114) are cyclic oligosaccharides containing six, seven, eight, nine, ten, eleven, twelve, thirteen 1,4-linked glycopyranose units with a hydrophilic hydroxyl group on their outer surface and a hydrophobic cavity in the center.

Pharmaceutical industries are successfully using cyclodextrin for drug molecules capsulation. Similarly in textile, there are many possibilities for the development of new textile products with advanced properties based on cyclodextrin.

Table-2.3: Properties of beta cyclodextrin

Physicochemical properties	Alfa	Beta	Gama	Lamda
No of glycopyranose units	6	7	8	9
Central cavity diameter	4.7-5.3	6.0-6.5	7.5-8.3	10.3-11.2
Water solubility at 25°c	14.5	1.85	23.2	8.19
Molecular weight	972	1135	1297	1459

Scent/Fragrance aesthetics: ⁽¹¹⁶⁾ When notice a smell, sensory organs unlock in you a subjective dimension, a memory, perhaps, or a feeling – a sensory experience inside the body. This doesn't happen if only *looking* at something. If we consider *smell* a roast turkey, for example, rather than just see it, all your memories of roast turkeys are activated – an instantaneous accessing of relevant information and memory. Smells can thus both create a sense of anticipation and a memory of the past – and gaining access to hidden or forgotten parts of our own history is a gift indeed. It is not yet known exactly how the sense of smell works. It might be the size, shape, spin, wave length or vibration of particular molecules matching or interlocking with special receptors in the nose that cause us to react or recognize a smell. Only a few molecules are necessary for us to experience or identify scents, and characteristically, the worse a smell is, the less it takes to notice it. Our sense of smell is – or used to be – so important, that unlike other nerve cells, the olfactory neurons constantly replace themselves. Smells are for us clearly culturally rather than physiologically defined. One system of categories assigns seven basic qualities to smells: ethereal, prickly, floral, minty, camphor, musk, and rotten, although other systems include such elements as garlic-like, aromatic, burnt, animal, and billy-goat.

Figure: *The word perfume comes from (Fr.) per fumar meaning pleasant-smelling or literally, from the smoke: the oldest way of imparting a smell. Fragrances were once considered to be the souls of objects, and thus spiritual and sacred in themselves. Incense is used in religious ceremonies all over the world, and its fragrance is often noticeable on church vestments. Pope Benedict XVI blesses the altar on his visit to Brazil, May 2007. Photo: Boston Catholic Journal.*

Perfuming history: Perfumes are substances whose fragrance gratifies the sense of smell. Perfume is generally made of the volatile oils of a large variety of plants, grasses, spices, herbs, woods, and flowers, the most important of which are bitter orange blossoms, jasmine, and rose. The Arabian philosopher and doctor Avicenna (980-1037) is usually credited with developing the technique of distilling aromatic oils from flowers, producing attar or otto. The process is also described in the Indian Ayur-Veda, one of the world's oldest medicinal systems, practiced for the last 5000 years. Before distillation was mastered, only fragrant resins from bark were used, generally burned to create fragrant smoke or used in the form of perfumed oils and salves. Perfume and incense were widely used in ancient Egypt 4000 years ago. Arabian perfume arts were highly developed, using ingredients from China, India and Africa. In classical Italy and Greece perfume was also important, but its use disappeared with the decline of the empire. In 1190 perfumers in Paris were granted a charter, and the first modern perfume, called Hungary Water (based on rosemary), was made there in 1370 for Queen Elizabeth of Hungary. With her marriage in 1533 Catherine de Medici introduced perfume to France, which quickly became the European center of perfumes, and cultivating flowers for perfume became a major French industry. By the early 1800s so much perfume was being produced that it was accessible for everyone, and no longer reserved for the nobility.

Examples of historical scented textiles: Where to look for perfumed objects? Every culture, at every time, seems to have had perfumed textiles. Perfumes were used not only in sacred and occult applications, but also medicinally long before they became popular for private use. Look for gloves, linens, underclothes, leather goods and hides, wigs, furs, ink, book bindings, furniture, chests, paper, shoe polish, and firewood. Cleopatra's ship of gold had purple, *perfumed* sails!

Ingredients of perfume: ^(116,117,118) Traditional and still familiar, perfumed oils such as patchouli, jasmine, cloves, bergamot, vetiver, cinnamon, sandalwood and balsam have all been used for centuries. Each ingredient has its own history of production, trade and use. For example, frangipani, often linked with perfumed leather gloves, stems from the 16th century Italian marquis Muzio Frangipane. The scent comes from the red jasmine's flower, often supplemented with heliotrope, citronella, rose, coumarin, cinnamon, sandalwood and musk. Gloves scented with frangipani were very exclusive and extremely expensive.

Table- 2.4, Natural Perfumes oil

Perfumed oils are found in:	
flowers	cloves, hyacinth, mimosa, jasmine, orange blossom, roses, reseda, heliotrope
petals and leaves	lavender, rosemary, peppermint
leaves and stems	geranium, cinnamon, patchouli
bark	cinnamon
roots	angelica, sassafras, vetiver
tubers	ginger, iris
fruits	bergamot, lemon, lime, orange
seeds	bitter almonds, anise, nutmeg
resin	myrrh, Peru balsam, styrax

Table-2.5: Sources of natural essential oils for perfumes (from Encyclopaedia Britannica).

Aroma Category	Aroma Compound / Aroma Chemical
Citrus: Lemon Orange	Citral, Citronellal Mandarin Oil, Decyl acetate
Floral: Carnation Gardenia Geranium Lilac Lily Rose Violet	Phenethyl salicylate Nonyl acetate Citronellal Anisyl acetate Hydroxy citronellal Rose absolute Costus oil, Methyl-2-nonenolate
Fruity: Apple Apricot Banana Grape Peach Strawberry	Benzyl acetate Allyl butyrate Amyl acetate Isobutyl isobutyrate Allyl butyrate Benzyl benzoate
Herbaceous: Clove Minty	Eugenyl acetate l-carveol, l-carvone, l-menthol
Sweet: Anise Cinnamon Honey Sweet Vanilla	Ethyl acetate, methyl sorbate Cinnamonaldehyde Allyl phenoxyacetate Acetanisole Anisyl acetate

Perfuming is a logical finishing step for dyeing processes that are especially smelly. Silk dyed black in the 18th century needed “sweetening” with a final bath of soap and anise, while woolen cloth had to be washed with linseed and soap and lavender boiled with weld, the plant universally used for yellow dyes (Roquero 1999, 38).

Banupriya J and Maheshwari reviewed on effects of Aromal Finish by Herbal and Conventional Methods on ⁽¹¹⁹⁾ Woven Fabrics i.e Cotton is the king of fibers, is one of the important commercial fiber crops, which is infested by wide range of insect pests at various stages of crop growth compared to any other crop. To remove the impurities from grey cotton textiles, some basic pre-treatments are prescribed. For instance, scouring (boiling) and bleaching are the most important chemical treatments prior to all the main treatments like coloration and finishing. Dyeing is the process that contributes substantially to textile wastes. A woven cloth consists of two sets of yarn, namely, warp and weft. An herb is a plant or plant part valued for its medicinal, aromatic or savory qualities.

Fragrance finishing of textiles is one such immaculate magnanimous entry into any textile culture. Aromatic not only can improve the environmental smell, be comfortable but also has sterilization, refreshing and many kinds of psychological and physical health care functions. Fragrance finishing of textiles is the process of enhancing the value of the product by adding some in lenses.

Assessment of the Highest Aroma Effect of Herbal Extracts :

Aroma or fragrance is a chemical compound that has a pleasant smell or odor. According to research of World health organization, human stress is a problem that reduces quality of life for a large proportion of world’s citizens & scientifically it was proved fragrance reduces stress has both long term and short term health benefit.

Table-2.6: The sedative effects/or emotion of essential oils:

Emotion	Essential Oils with the Sedative Effects
Anxiety	Benzoin, Lemon, Chamomile. Rose, Cardamom, Clove, Jasmine
Lament	Rose
Stimulation	Camphor, Balm oil
Anger	Chamomile, Balm oil. Rose, Ylangylang

Wretchedness	Basil, Cypress, Mint, Patchouli
Allergy	Chamomile, Jasmine, Balm oil
Distrustfulness	Lavender
Tension	Camphor, Cypress, Vanilla, Jasmine, Balm oil, Lavender, Sandalwood
Melancholy	Basil, Lemon, Chamomile, Vanilla, Jasmine, Lavender, Mint, Rose
Hysteria	Chamomile, Balm oil, Lavender, Jasmine
Mania	Basil, Jasmine, Pine
Irritability	Chamomile, Camphor, Cypress, Lavender
Desolation	Jasmine, Pine, Patchouli, Rosemary

Cerempei Angela, Clobanu Luminita, Emil Muresan, Malutan, Corina and Romen Batnaru reviewed on natural fibre for aromatherapy: ⁽¹²⁰⁾ and their properties (good sorption, softness and good vapour permeability) the natural fibres are well suited for medical and cosmetic textile with aromatherapy. Using field of aroma textile: ⁽¹¹⁾ Bed sheet, Pillow cover, Intimate garments, Sportswear, Socks, Sports shoes, Fabric for hospital and spa

Aromachology and its Application in the Textile Field: ⁽¹¹⁸⁾ Used as finishing chemical Beta cyclodextrin inclusion compound.

Uses of beta cyclodextrin for fragrance finishing:

7. Successful medical application
8. It has cone shaped hydrophobic cavity which released fragrance rates are greatly decreased.
9. Finishing with cyclodextrin on cotton textiles (8,10):
10. Fragrance was capsulated with beta cyclodextrin and perfume retention onto the fabric after number of washing and exposure to sunlight.

Fixation Technique of Beta cyclodextrin¹¹⁵

11. Crosslinking
12. Grafting
13. Reactive fixation
14. Disperse dyeing method
15. Electrospinning
16. Sol gel process
17. Enzymatic coupling
18. Polymer extrusion
19. Fragrance release property
20. There were several different sections to the cyclodextrin's molecular encapsulation compared

with other widely-used encapsulation processes. The enclosed substance was totally or partially included in the cyclodextrin cavity. This system was reversible and was not sealed completely. The key to aromatherapeutic textile is how to make microcapsules of fragrance compounds and essential oils without omitting any ingredient in order to ensure its pharmaceutical effects. In addition, using a low-temperature polymer binder to attach a perfumed microcapsule to the fabric. Hence, silver nanoparticles have emerged up with diverse medical applications.

Graph-2.1: The rate of fragrance-release from microcapsules.

Easy method of application, Conventional padding.

Fragrance finishing with DMDHEU¹²¹

Rose oil fragrance was stable upto 3 month.

Ayurvedic scouring, bleaching, dyeing & finishing ¹²²:

Camel/Buffalo/Cow/Sheep dung is used for both scouring and bleaching the grey cloth.

Dyeing of green color (Neem, Pomegranate, Indigo, Tumeric

Finishing is done by pure water.

Finishing with microencapsulation

Micro encapsulation technology¹¹⁵ has its vast application in various fields including textile wet processing. It is a technology, in which very small particles of liquids, solids and gases are trapped within a very thin coating of polymeric material(s). For textile wet processing applications core materials includes dyes, pigments, essential oils, vitamins, anti-bacterial agents, anti UV agents etc. The microcapsules obtained in slurry or free flowing powder form is applied to fabric to achieve various effects. In today's life customer needs differ from that of conventional needs, where micro encapsulation technology plays a significant role to meet today's market demand by providing multiple advantage using one single product. So textile is a product, which can easily fulfill for fashion and also protection at the same time.

Micro encapsulation has different purposes like;

- Protection of enclosed material and improved storage life
- Conversion of liquid component to dry solid system
- Ensuring separation of incompatible components
- Odour masking
- Dust and pH control
- Controlled diffusion of active components, through the shell wall
- Change of weight or volume

So, we can say this is a significant development in the finishing sector in which microencapsulated product with particular functions having deodorizing agent, anti- bacterial and fungal agent, skin beautifying and aromatherapy etc can be incorporated separately or together in a single fabric. Although, this is not a new technology, but its adoption to the textile wet processing started very late. Microcapsules are first formed by National Cash Register in 1954 to produce pressure sensitive carbonless copy paper and leuco dye was the first thing to be used in it. Till now it is still bounded by the periphery of softeners and fragrances. Most of its other uses, which are very attractive for industrial applications, suffer from different problems^{1, 13}.

Materials for micro encapsulation

Core materials can be liquid, Semi-Solid, Solid, Dispersion and water-insoluble, very poorly water soluble or water-soluble type. The core and coat agents are taken in a particular view of the method. It is always to be noted that a microcapsule having organic core should be coated with one or more than one inorganic coating polymer and while an inorganic materials should be coated organic polymers. It is also to be noted that a particular core to coat ratio only provides the optimum efficiency and better properties to microcapsules, which can be judge by studying its properties like shape, size, surface roughness and release characteristics. In textile core materials are numerous in number that is they start from dye, pigment, surfactant, softener, anti- microbial agent, skin moisturizing agent, fragrances etc. A wide variety of polymers, either natural or synthetic polymers, may be used as film forming material for Micro encapsulation.

Effect of Ecofriendly Microencapsulated Textile Products In Joint Pain and Aesthematic Respondents

¹²³: The study was conducted to develop aromtherapeutic textile products for joint pains/ asthma. Fabric treated with eco-friendly microcapsules of eucalyptus, jasmine, lemon and pine oil respectively were used for the treatment of respondents. Knee caps, gloves, Pillow covers and handkerchieves were made joint & ashtetic respectively for the respondents out of cotton fabric. Respondents suffering were undergone for the wear trail of two months. To get the results through interview schedule data collected. The results showed that the developed products had a positive effect on the emotional state of the respondents (87%), improved in quality of night sleep (95%),

outdoor activities (67%) and reduced medicine in take (50%). The results also showed soothing effect on the skin of the respondents after using these aromatherapeutic textiles.

Many different manufacturing approaches have been adopted for microencapsulation. The most commonly used microencapsulation processes, including

23. Complex Coacervation,
24. Polymer-Polymer Incompatibility,
25. Interfacial Polymerisation and In Situ Polymerisation,
26. Spray Drying,
27. Centrifugal Extrusion,
28. Air Suspension Coating,
29. Pan Coating, and
30. Emulsion Hardening Process

The microcapsules are produced by depositing a thin polymer coating on small solid Microencapsulation Technology and Its particles or liquid droplets, or on dispersions of Advantages solids in liquids. The core contents are released under controlled conditions to suit a specific Currently, microencapsulation technology is purpose (Mei, 1995; Nelson, 2001; Simon, 2006), rapidly developing in the field of chemical finishing because of its versatility and flexibility Scanning electron microscope microcapsule which generally consists of two (SEM) image of microcapsules. One major major component: advantage of using microencapsulation technology is its ability to protect the active ingredients from 1. Active ingredient hazardous environments, i.e. oxidation, heat, acidity, alkalinity, moisture or evaporation. An active ingredient is the substance that may be in a liquid or solid form. It also refers to It also simultaneously, protects the ingredients the core contents, internal phases, from interacting with other compounds in the encapsulations, payloads or fillers. system, which may result in degradation or polymerization. Another important advantage of 2. Wall Shell this versatile technology is its controlled release properties that seem to be the best choice for A polymer coating that surrounds the active increasing efficiency and minimising ingredients which may also be called the wall, environmental damage (Anon, 2005; Holme, 2004; shell, external phase, membrane or matrix. It Milmo, 2006; Nelson, 2001). may be natural, semi-synthetic or synthetic polymer.

Used Chemical: Beta cyclodextrin

Development of Fragrance finishing for production of Cosmetic Textiles: Using Microencapsulation Technology ¹²

Fig-2.6: Structure and process of Microencapsulation: ¹²⁴

Fig-2.7: Impregnation of microencapsulated fragrance finishing: ¹²³

In cosmetic textiles, the major interest in microencapsulation is currently in the application Copete Vidal et al. invented chitosan-based of vitamins, essential oils, skin moisturizing agents, microcapsules containing various active skin cooling agents, anti-aging agents etc. components and investigated their durability with Focusing on the field of cosmetic textiles.

The release mechanisms of the core contents vary depending on the selection of wall materials and more importantly, its specific end uses. Table 1 demonstrates the relationship between the textiles end uses and their release mechanisms. The core content may be released by friction, pressure, change of temperature, diffusion through the polymer wall, dissolution of the polymer wall coating, biodegradation etc (Anon, 2005; Holme, 2003; Sudha, et al., 2005).

Textile materials have been found in applications in the cosmetics field. ¹²⁴ A new sector of cosmetic textiles is introduced and several commercial cosmetic textile products are currently available in the market. On contact with human body and skin, cosmetic textiles are designed to transfer an active substance for cosmetic purposes. The principle is achieved by simply imparting the cosmetic and pharmaceutical ingredients into the fabric of clothing so that with the natural movement of the body, the skin is slowly freshened and revitalized. Microencapsulation technology is an effective technique used to control the release properties of active ingredients that prolong the functionality of cosmetic textiles.

2.6: Multiple Finishing

Anjali, Karolia and Snehal Mendapara reviewed on Imparting antimicrobial and fragrance finish on cotton using chitosan with silicon softener ¹²⁵ and Chitosan has been used in combination with citric acid and silicon softener to impart antimicrobial and fragrance finish with two different application techniques. It is observed that the finish provides better functionality to the fabric as it shows good performance and improvement in physical properties. The finish shows good fastness to washing as well as perspiration. The use of carboxylic acid also improves the affinity of chitosan for cellulose. Necessity to meet the growing demand of petrolatum and various silicon-based materials. consumers led to the revolution in functional finishes Aly et al.3 observed that chitosan citrate imparts worldwide. Cotton is widely used for apparel due to

higher wrinkle recovery and antimicrobial properties its comfort property, but it has two main drawbacks, to the fabric as compared to chitosan alone. It is also susceptible to creasing and bacterial degradation. Human sweat provides a suitable shelter for bacterial encapsulation of fragrance than cationic and non-ionic growth, containing 1.4 million bacteria per gram softeners and improves the wrinkle recovery of the which increases to 9000 million at 50% moisture fabric.⁴ Therefore, the present work was carried out level with an objective to study the effect of silicon softener Chemical compounds are used as antimicrobial and chitosan with lavender fragrance on certain agents but they also influence the natural flora of the physical and performance properties of cotton fabric. Human skin. Studies have shown that chitosan, a The effect of application techniques on the fabric natural biopolymer, is antibacterial, antifungal, properties was also studied. antiviral, non-toxic, non-allergic and biocompatible.

Durability of Antimicrobial and Fragrance Finish to Perspiration Finishing was analyzed for its performance against acidic higher functionality to the fabric. as well as alkaline perspiration. It is observed that the 4.2 Chitosan and silicon softener applied by perspiration treatment causes significant reduction in padding show better performance, as shown below, antimicrobial property. Finish applied by padding against laundry and perspiration as compared to that shows better antimicrobial activity than that applied by exhaustion: by exhaustion method. Reaction between alkaline – Finish shows 79% antibacterial property even after 3 wash cycles. of Baroda, for providing support and laboratory facilities received during the work for conducting the tests. Finished fabric possesses better antimicrobial activity against acidic perspiration as compared

Combined antimicrobial and aroma finishing treatment for cotton ¹²⁶ the methanolic extract of geranium, *Pelargonium graveolens* L' Herit. ex Ait. leaves was used to impart antimicrobial and aroma finishing to the cotton fabric. The extract was microencapsulated using two different methods namely coacervation-spray drying and direct spray drying techniques. The results indicated that the direct spray drying method produced smaller capsules with 5 μ size in powder form and 12.5 μ in aqueous form compared to the 7.5 μ and 17.5 μ respective capsule sizes produced by coacervation-spray drying method. The microencapsulated geranium leaves extract treated cotton fabrics showed antimicrobial efficacy against both *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*. However, the Gram positive *Staphylococcus aureus* was more susceptible to geranium extract compared to *Escherichia coli*. The microcapsule treated fabric retained 50-60% aroma after 10 washes compared to the nil retention property of pure geranium extract treated fabric.

Microcapsules on the fabric, a post treatment with micro encapsulation of geranium extract was done 10% citric acid was given, keeping material-to-liquor by two methods using gum acacia as a wall material ratio of 1:20, at 50°C for 5 min. The treated fabric In the first method, the geranium extract was samples were then dried at 80°C and cured at 140°C encapsulated by coacervation technique followed by for 2 min. A control cotton fabric was produced by spray drying in to powder. In the second method, the padding with pure geranium extract as per the above core and wall materials were spray dried to get the procedure followed by fixing with 10% citric acid.

3.1: Materials

Plain weave 100% cotton fabric was purchased from Khadi silk imporium, Dakshinapan market, Kolkata, India

Bleached type: 4% H₂O₂

Fabric ends/decimeter: 13.75

Fabric pick/decimeter: 14.73

Fabric GSM: 54

3.1.1: List of Used Chemical & Sourcing for the Experiment of Combined dyeing and finishing as well as double stage dyeing and finishing:

Chemical used	Sourcing/Company Name
Reactive dye- Lemon Yellow-CN	Dyechem international, Kolkata
Beta Cyclodextrin	TCI Chemical Ltd. India
Dextrin	Laboratory grade
Dimethyl dihydroxyethylene urea (DMDHEU)	Clariant, India
Polyethylene Glycol	Laboratory grade
Sodium hypophosphite	Laboratory grade
Sodium carbonate	Laboratory grade
Sodium chloride	Laboratory grade
Citric acid	Laboratory grade
Citric acid	Laboratory grade

Fragrance Chemical used	Sourcing/Company Name
Synthetic fragrance chemical	LN chemical industries ltd, Mumbai, India
Rose Oil	Chemical supplier, kolkata, India
Patchouli oil	Govt. Emitine factory, Darjeeling, West Bengal, India

3.1.2: Chemical Selection for present work has been proceeded by getting some idea of literature review according to Reference (139, 125, 113, 141) for various types of experimental works of reactive dyeing and fragrance finishing

Polyethylene Glycol-400 and Distilled water in ratio 1:3 was used as solvent¹³⁹ for both combined dyeing and finishing as well as finishing bath of double stage dyeing and finishing

Citric acid-6%¹²⁵ was used as crosslinking agent for both combined dyeing and finishing as well as finishing bath of double stage dyeing and finishing.

Sodium hypophosphite -6%¹²⁵ was used as catalyst for both combined dyeing and finishing as well as finishing bath of double stage dyeing and finishing for both combined dyeing and finishing as well as double stage dyeing and finishing

Beta Cyclodextrin 5%, 10% & 15 % were used as difunctional chemical (Microencapsulation & Dyeing auxiliaries) in the padding solution¹¹³ as the agent of microencapsulation of fragrance chemical like as Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine), Rose Oil & Patchouli oil and dyeing auxiliaries of monochlorotriazine group of reactive dye for both combined dyeing and finishing as well as finishing bath of double stage dyeing and finishing

Sodium carbonate¹⁴¹ for alkaline pH has been used for reactive dyeing of cotton fabric by exhaust method in dyeing bath of double stage dyeing and finishing

DMDHEU¹¹⁵ were used as crosslinking agent for both combined dyeing and finishing as well as double stage dyeing and finishing.

Percentage of dyestuff **Reactive dye- Lemon Yellow-CN-1%** which is monochlorotriazine group of reactive dyestuff¹⁴³ were kept constant for this work in dyeing bath of double stage dyeing and finishing and **Reactive dye- Lemon Yellow-CN-1%** were kept constant for this work of combined dyeing and finishing for studying the variation of two process as well as for understanding the feasibility of different types of new chemical such beta cyclodextrin, Dextrin¹²³, DMDHEU¹¹⁵ & three types of fragrance chemical such as Synthetic fragrance (Jasmine-1%, 2%, 3%), Rose oil¹¹⁵ (1%, 2%, 3%) and Patchouli oil (1%, 2%, 3%) were used for comparing the performance in combined dyeing and finishing as well as double stage dyeing and finishing.

3.2: Methods

Method selection¹¹⁵ for fragrance finishing where fragrance was released gradually from microcapsules.

Name of Method: Padding

3.2.1: METHOD OF PREPARATION OF SOLUTION FOR MICROENCAPSULATION OF FRAGRANCE CHEMICAL:

Fig:- Microencapsulation method

A solution was prepared composed of polyethylene glycol & Distilled water –temp 50°C (1:3)

Fragrance Chemical was added in the solution by dropping system for proper microencapsulation & stirred continuously

Crosslinking and cool down slowly

Microencapsulated solution was applied for both combined dyeing and finishing as well as double stage dyeing and finishing

3.2.2: METHOD OF COMBINED DYEING AND FINISHING

Microencapsulated solution was added with Citric acid & Sodium hypophosphite

Stirring for dissolving

Added reactive dye lemon yellow-CN

Stirring for dissolving

Bleached fabric was impregnated and Padded with 80% expression by two dip two nip process

Drying-100°C & Curing-150°C

3.2.3: METHOD OF DOUBLE STAGE DYEING AND FINISHING

First stage (Dyeing) of double stage dyeing and finishing:

Cooling at-50°C

Unloading

Cold wash

Hot wash-95°C

Acid wash

Cold wash and Drying at 100°C-5min

Second Stage (Finishing) of double stage dyeing and finishing:

Microencapsulated solution was added with Citric acid & Sodium hypophosphite

Stirring for dissolving

Ready dyed fabric was impregnated and Padded with 80% expression by two dip two nip process

Dried at 100°C & Cured-150°C-5min

EXPERIMENTS ON COMBINED DYEING AND FINISHING

EXPERIMENT NO: 1-9

Beta cyclodextrin and fragrance chemicals are weakly soluble in water, so polyethylene glycol and water (1:3) ratio is used to solubilize it. In experiment no 1, 2, & 3: Beta cyclodextrin (5%, 10%, 15%), Dextrin (5%, 10%, 15%) and DMDHEU (5%, 10%, 15%) were used separately to compare the capability of microencapsulation of fragrance chemical. Concentration of reactive dye-1%, concentration of fragrance chemical-1%, Citric acid -6% and sodium hypophosphite-6% were kept for all recipe in the experiment of 1, 2, 3 of combined dyeing and finishing with a mixture of Polyethylene glycol & water (1:3) as solvent. The fabric was then dried in 100°C and cured 150°C for 5 minutes. To make good solution chemicals were dissolved with stirrer for 5 minutes in an open beaker. After visual satisfaction of mixing solution, Cotton fabric were padded with 80% expression in padding mangle for combined dyeing and finishing.

3.3.1: Chemical composition of different experiment of beta cyclodextrin for microencapsulation of combined dyeing and finishing of cotton fabric comparing with Dextrin and DMDHEU (A Solution was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3))

Experiment No: 1

Beta Cyclodextrin: 5%, 10%, 15%
Reactive Lemon yellow –CN: 1%
Synthetic Fragrance: 1%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 77%, 72%, 67%

Experiment No: 2

Dextrin: 5%, 10%, 15%
Reactive Lemon yellow –CN: 1%
Synthetic Fragrance: 1%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 77%, 72%, 67%

Experiment No: 3

DMDHEU: 5%, 10%, 15%

Reactive Lemon yellow –CN: 1%

Synthetic Fragrance: 1%

Citric Acid: 6%

Sodium Hypophospite: 6%

Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 77%, 72%, 67%

During experiment of visual operation, Dyeing and Fragrance intensity were found comparatively better for the recipe of beta cyclodextrin-10%. So further research was proceeded by using beta cyclodextrin.

Again in combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric some further experiment are made varying fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin. In experiment no 4, 5 & 6: synthetic fragrance (1%, 2%, 3%), Rose oil (1%, 2%, 3%) and Patchouli oil (1%, 2%, 3%) were used with 10% beta cyclodextrin to find out fragrance intensity as well as microencapsulation capability of beta cyclodextrin. To study the role of beta cyclodextrin, Experiment No. 7, 8 & 9 were also conducted without beta cyclodextrin in case of all fragrance chemical & concentration like as above to find out fragrance intensity and microencapsulation capability. For every experiment, fabric was processed by pad-dry-cure at 80% expression, dried at 100°C and cured at 150°C.

3.3.2: Different concentration of fragrance and beta cyclodextrin for combined dyeing and finishing:

A Solution was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3)

Experiment No: 4

Synthetic Fragrance (Jasmine): 1%, 2%, 3%

Reactive dye-lemon yellow-CN: 1%

Beta Cyclodextrin: 10%

Citric Acid: 6%

Sodium Hypophospite: 6%

Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 5

Rose Oil: 1%, 2%, 3%

Reactive dye-lemon yellow-CN: 1%

Beta Cyclodextrin: 10%

Citric Acid: 6%

Sodium Hypophospite: 6%

Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 7

Synthetic Fragrance (Jasmine): 1%, 2%, 3%

Reactive dye-lemon yellow-CN: 1%

Beta Cyclodextrin: 0%

Citric Acid: 6%

Sodium Hypophospite: 6%

Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 8

Rose Oil: 1%, 2%, 3%

Reactive dye-lemon yellow-CN: 1%

Beta Cyclodextrin: 0%

Citric Acid: 6%

Sodium Hypophospite: 6%

Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 6

Patchouli oil: 1%, 2%, 3%
 Reactive dye-lemon yellow-CN: 1%
 Beta Cyclodextrin: 10%
 Citric Acid: 6%
 Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
 Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 9

Patchouli Oil: 1%, 2%, 3%
 Reactive dye-lemon yellow-CN: 1%
 Beta Cyclodextrin: 0%
 Citric Acid: 6%
 Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
 Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 72%, 71%, 70%

During Experiment of visual observation of Dyeing and Fragrance intensity were found comparatively better for synthetic fragrance-1% (Jasmine), so further study of result and discussion was proceeded by using synthetic fragrance only.

EXPERIMENTS ON DOUBLE STAGE DYEING AND FINISHING

EXPERIMENTS NO: 10-19

First stage (Dyeing) of double stage dyeing and finishing: In experiment No: 10, Bleached cotton fabric was first dyed by conventional exhaust method of reactive dyeing. Like as combined dyeing and finishing, monochlorotriazine group of reactive dyestuff was used to compare the performance with combined dyeing and finishing. The dye bath temperatuere was lifted upto 80°C. Salt and soda was added by using two portions. After dyed the sample was rinsed and soaped to remove surface color of fabric.

**3.3.3: Dyeing of bleached cotton fabric for double stage dyeing and finishing:
 Experiments on Reactive Dyeing for the process of double stage dyeing and finishing:**

Experiment No: 10	<p>Reactive dye- Lemon Yellow CN -1% Sodium Chloride-40gm/l Sodium Carbonate-15gm/l Wetting agent-1gm/l M:L -1:10 pH:10-11 Temp: 80°C Time: 90min</p>
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Second Stage (finishing) of double stage dyeing and finishing:

Effect of beta cyclodextrin for finishing of ready dyed cotton fabric in double stage dyeing and finishing method comparing with Dextrin and DMDHEU: In experiment no 11, 12, & 13: Beta Cyclodextrin (5%, 10%, 15%), Dextrin (5%, 10%, 15%) & DMDHEU (5%, 10%, 15%) were used in different concentration to find out microencapsulation capability of Beta cyclodextrin where synthetic fragrance-1%, citric acid-6%, Sodium hypophosphite-6% were used as well as solvent composed of PEG & water used in different concentration.

3.3.4: Study on beta cyclodextrin for multifinishing of ready dyed fabric comparing with dextrin and DMDHEU

An Solution was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3)

Experiment No: 11 Beta Cyclodextrin: 5%, 10%, 15%
Synthetic Fragrance: 1%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 77%, 72%,
67%

Experiment No: 12 Dextrin: 5%, 10%, 15%
Synthetic Fragrance: 1%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 77%, 72%,
67%

Experiment No: 13 DMDHEU: 5%, 10%, 15%
Synthetic Fragrance: 1%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water: 77%, 72%,
67%

During Experiment of visual observation of Dyeing and Fragrance intensity were found comparatively better for beta cyclodextrin-10%, so further research was proceeded by using by using beta cyclodextrin. Beta cyclodextrin was found good intensity of fragrance without effecting dyeing shade.

Experimental method of double stage dyeing and fragrance finishing varying different fragrance chemical at different concentration: In the experiment of ready dyed cotton fabric , to find out the effect of fragrance intensity different type of fragrance chemical were used in different concentration like as synthetic fragrance (1%, 2%, 3%), Rose oil (1%, 2%, 3%) and Patchouli oil (1%, 2%, 3%) and similarly in the experiment of ready dyed cotton fabric to find out the effect of microencapsulation of beta cyclodextrin chemical, it was experimented in experiment no 14, 15 & 16 with 10% beta cyclodextrin in case of all fragrance chemical & concentration like as above as well as it was also experimented in experiment no 17, 18, 19 without beta cyclodextrin in case of all fragrance chemical & concentration like as above.

3.3.5: Study on fragrance and beta cyclodextrin for finishing of ready dyed cotton

A Solution was prepared by Polyethylene glycol & Distilled water (1:3)

Experiment No: 14

Synthetic Fragrance (Jasmine): 1%, 2%, 3%
Beta Cyclodextrin: 10%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water:
72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 15

Rose Oil: 1%, 2%, 3%
Beta Cyclodextrin: 10%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water:
72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 16

Patchouli oil: 1%, 2%, 3%
Beta Cyclodextrin: 10%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water:
72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 17

Synthetic Fragrance (Jasmine): 1%, 2%, 3%
Beta Cyclodextrin: 0%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water:
72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 18

Rose Oil: 1%, 2%, 3%
Beta Cyclodextrin: 0%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water:
72%, 71%, 70%

Experiment No: 19

Patchouli Oil: 1%, 2%, 3%
Beta Cyclodextrin: 0%
Citric Acid: 6%
Sodium Hypophospite: 6%
Solvent composed of PEG & Water:
72%, 71%, 70%

3.3.6: Treatment for Fragrance finished Fabric in combined dyeing and finishing method to study the fragrance intensity without washing after number of days

Experiment No:20

Fragrance treated sample was kept in open condition in room temperature and after 10 days interval, it was tested by human sensory evaluation to find out retention% of fragrance. But Synthetic fragrance was found improved intensity of fragrance according to comments of different person. So for further confirmation, Synthetic fragrance treated sample with 10% beta cyclodextrin was tested by Gas chromatography testing.

3.3.7: Washing Treatment for Fragrance finished Fabric in combined dyeing and finishing method to study the fragrance intensity after five time washing

Experiment No:21

In this experiment, studied the washing durability of fragrance finished fabric where washing of the both combined dyed and finished fabric were washed individually. As the perfumes are volatile in nature. Thus the intensity of fragrances gets reduced day by day by a wear or wash. All the treated samples were examined for fragrance retention after number of washing which gave idea of the fragrance retention on clothing usage in day to day routine life. The washing was given according to the ISO 105-C10, 2006 standards¹⁴⁰ using 5gm soap solution and 2 gm soda ash solution at 60°C for 30 minutes in launderometer. This procedure was repeated 5 time to examine the fragrance retention after the washing procedure. After each washing sample such as synthetic fragrance, Rose oil, Patchouli oil was tested by human sensorial evaluation. But Synthetic fragrance was found improved intensity of fragrance according to comments of different person. So for further confirmation, Synthetic fragrance treated sample with 10% beta cyclodextrin was tested by Gas chromatography testing.

3.4: Method of Testing

3.4.1: Color strength testing¹⁴²

Name of testing	Color strength (K/S value)
Machine used	Computer color matching machine (Macbeth 2020 plus spectrophptometer)
Procedure	Color strength of untreated and treated cotton fabric samples is measured from the reflectance value at maximum wave length from which surface color strength (K/S value) can be determined by kubelka- munk equation: $K/S = (1 - R_{max})^2 / 2 R_{max}$

3.4.2: Washing fastness testing¹⁴³

Name of Machine: Launder-o-Meter

Method of testing: ISO2

Procedure:

- Taken two pieces of fabric about 5cm by 5cm, one of which is undyed cotton and the other undyed wool. Stitch them together along one side.
- Take some sample strips of the dyed yarn and spread them evenly between the two pieces

of cloth so that they overlap both sides. If dyed fibre is being tested a combed sample can be used in place of the yarn.

- Sew around all four sides of the cloth so that the yarn is held in place.
- Prepare a similar specimen with dyed materials that has satisfactory properties and place them in two jars with screw lids containing a solution of 5gm per litre soap or detergent solution at 30oC.
- Agitate the two jars gently for 30mins, then remove the fabrics and wash them gently in clean water for 5mins. Open the stitching and separate the pieces to dry in air. Examination:
- Place the dyed yarn next to a sample of the same material which has not been tested, and compare the change which has taken place. Compare also with the control sample with satisfactory properties. If the dyeing being tested shows equal or less change than the satisfactory sample, then it is as good as the satisfactory sample.
- Place the wool and cotton cloths next to samples of the same material which have not been tested and compare them with the cloths that have been tested with a satisfactory dyeing. Equal or less staining shows equal or better fastness.

3.4.3: Light fastness testing¹⁴³

Name of Machine	Q-SUN XE-2 XENON TEST CHAMBER
Method of testing	AATCC TM16: Colorfastness to Light: This test method provides the general principles and procedures which are currently in use for determining the colorfastness to light of textile materials.
Procedure	Samples of the textile material to be tested and the agreed upon comparison standard(s) are exposed simultaneously to a light source under specified conditions. The colorfastness to light of the specimen is evaluated by comparison of the color change of the exposed portion to the masked control portion of the test specimen or unexposed original material using the AATCC Gray Scale for Color Change, or by instrumental color measurement. Light fastness classification is accomplished by evaluation versus a simultaneously exposed series of AATCC Blue Wool Light fastness Standards.

3.4.4: Crease recovery testing¹⁴²: Crease is a fold in fabric introduced unintentionally at some stages of processing. Crease or crushing of textile material is a complex effect involving tensile, compressive, flexing and torsional stresses. Crease recovery is a fabric property which indicates the ability of fabric to go back to its original position after creasing.

Name of Machine	Shirley Crease Recovery Tester.
Name of Testing	Dry crease recovery testing
Method of testing	ASTM-D-1295-67
Procedure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The specimen is cut by template and carefully creased by folding in half. 2. The crease is imparted on fabric by placing it between two glass plates and adding to 500gm weight on it. 3. After 1 min the weight is removed and the creased fabric is clamped on the instrument. 4. Then it is allowed to recover from the crease. The recovery time may vary to suit particular creases. Usually it is 1 min. 5. When crease recovers the dial of the instrument is rotated to keep the free edge of the specimen in line with the knife edge. 6. The recovery angle is read from the engraved scale. 7. In this way 10 tests are done in warp way and 10 for weft way. 8. The mean value of recovery angle is taken and thus crease recovery is measured.

3.4.5: Tensile strength testing¹¹³

Name of Machine	Instron
Method of testing	Ravel strip method as per IS-1969-1985 method
Procedure	The following procedure was adopted in ensuring that the data recorded from tensile test specimens was taken in an organised and consistent manner.

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sample size-2cm/10cm. Five specimens were chosen. Care is to be taken to ensure that the specimens did not have any notching or cracks from manufacturing or any surface defects that would adversely affect the tensile tests. 2. The specimens were loaded into the Instron machine, and a tensile test was performed. 3. Data was collected manually one by one
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3.4.6: Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) ¹⁴²

Name of Machine	Parkin Elmer, UK. Model: Spectrum-100FTIR spectrometer.
Procedure FTIR Pallet:	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fabric dust & potassium bromide was mixed with proportion of 1: 100 to make hard matrix and making it as IR transparent 2. Hard matrix was placed into sample chamber of IR Machine 3. Machine was run and result was found as spectrum graph by spectrum software

FTIR Pallet:

3.4.7: Gas Chromatography Testing (Capillary method) ¹⁴⁰

Name of Machine	Gas Chromatography, Thermo fisher, Trace GC 1110, India
Method of testing	Column: TG 5 MS, Capillary column, Column Temp: 100 c, Injected temp: 190 c, Detector temp: 220 c, Nitrogen carrier gas flow 1.5ml/min, Speed ratio: 1:33, Software: Detector FID (Flame Ionization detector) software cromcard
Procedure	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. High purity gases are supplied to the GC. One of the gases (called the carrier gas) flows into the injector, through the column and then into the detector. 2. All gases-injector carrier, detector gases are fully electronically controlled through advanced flow controller and advanced pressure controller. 3. Firstly standard jasmine and standard rose has been injected with a syringe or an exterior sampling device in gas chromatography machine and the volatile solution are transported into the column by the carrier gas where the column is maintained in a temperature controlled oven. Solution enters heated detector and an electronic signal is generated upon interaction of the solute with the detector. The size of the signal is recorded by a data system and is plotted against elapsed time to produce a chromatogram and peak of fragrance has been recorded automatically by detector software cromcard 4. Fragrance treated fabric has been extracted by acetone 5. Then extracted solution has been injected and expected peak of sample/fragrance treated fabric has been found comparing recorded peak of standard jasmine and standard rose.

4.1: Result and Discussions

In the present work of combined dyeing and fragrance finishing has been proceeded to compare double stage dyeing and fragrance finishing by using same chemical & concentration to study the actual performance of dyeing and fragrance finishing where following chemical has been used for both process:

Monochlorotriazine group of reactive lemon yellow-CN dyestuff was used for reactive dyeing

Beta cyclodextrin/Dextrin/DMDHEU was used to compare the feasibility for dyeing and fragrance finishing/Microencapsulation

Citric acid was used as crosslinking agent

Exhaust method was only used for dyeing of double stage dyeing and finishing method and padding method was used for both combined dyeing and finishing and only finishing of double stage dyeing and finishing method.

For studying result and discussion, it was clearly studied improvement of basic dyeing properties such as color strength, Color fastness rating & light fastness rating shown in table- & graph- Light fastness rating as well as physical properties like as tensile strength and dry crease recovery angle shown in table- & graph-. Higher K/S value, tensile strength and dry creaser recovery angle was found.

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra analysis for Bleached cotton fabric as well as combined dyed and fragrance finished of cotton fabric treated with Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%, Cyclodextrin -10%, Citric acid-6% and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%) to study the reaction of combined dyeing and finishing bath, effect of fragrance chemical of dyeing shade as well as microencapsulation of fragrance chemical where it has been that OH group of beta cyclodextrin is making reaction with monochlorotriazine group of reactive dye.

In this work, three types of fragrance chemical (Synthetic Jasmine, Rose oil and Patchouli oil) was used used for microencapsulation. For microencapsulation beta cyclodextrin, dextrn and DMDHEU were used. And beta cyclodextrin treated fabric Shown in table- & graph- was found more fragrance intensity and it was confirmed by Gas Chromatography testing and Human sensorial evaluation for sustained release of fragrance chemical.

From overall analysis of combined dyeing and finishing as well as double stage dyeing and finishing, combined method has been found very improvement result by using a new chemical-beta cyclodextrin which is also working as fragrance finishing chemical by the technology of microencapsulation.

4.2: STUDY ON DYEING PROPERTIES OF COMBINED DYED AND FINISHED COTTON FABRIC COMPARING WITH DOUBLE STAGE DYED AND FINISHED COTTON FABRIC

In the present study bleached cotton fabric has been dyed and fragrance finished in single stage operation as well as double stage process. Table-showed the different dyeing properties in combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as double stage dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric studied various types of properties such as K/S value, color fastness rating, Light fastness to observe the feasibility of combined dyeing and finishing comparing with double stage dyeing and finishing using

Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%,

Cyclodextrin -10%,

Citric acid-6% and

synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%).

For Dyeing properties it has been purely proved that K/S value (**shown in table-4.2.1**) of combined dyed and finished cotton fabric with beta cyclodextrin has been found 3.239 and double stage dyeing and finishing method has been found 2.454. Combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric obtained deeper color yield for reactive dyeing of monochlorotriazine group using beta cyclodextrin, citric acid & sodium hypophosphite. Although cotton fabric was treated with dextrin and DMDHEU instead of beta cyclodextrin where dyed fabric showed lower color yield. From this point, it has been confirmed that beta cyclodextrin works as dyeing auxiliaries. Monochlorotriazine group of reactive dye formed covalent bond with cellulose and beta cyclodextrin. Due to the strong primary bonding between dye, fibre and beta cyclodextrin, it possessed high level of fastness color fastness and light fastness (**shown in table-4.2.1**). But the fastness of color is slightly poor than double stage dyeing and finishing.

In conventional method of dyeing and finishing, the major drawback of reactive dyes is hydrolysis in which dye instead of reacting with fibre reacts with hydroxide ion of base, as a result high amount of wastage of dyestuff is occurred in conventional dyeing. But in combined dyeing and finishing with padding method hydrolysis rate of dyestuff is minimizing highly and wastage rate of dyestuff is very minor. So this project is more beneficial to minimize the wastage of dyestuff

K/s value was improved .785: As the price of dyestuff is the highest among all chemical of dyeing and finishing process. So, it may be a great achievement that combined dyeing and finishing is minimizing the cost of dyestuff than double stage dyeing and finishing.

4.2.1: Analysis of dyeing properties of double stage dyeing and finishing as well as combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric

Treatments of Fabric	Experiment Number	K/S value	Color fastness Rating	Light fastness
Bleached untreated cotton		0.100	-	-
Dyed cotton with conventional exhaust method	10	2.999	3	3
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	11	2.454	4	4
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dextrin instead of B-CD	12	1.534	2	2
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	13	2.565	2	2
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	1	3.239	3	3

Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dextrin instead of B-CD	2	1.990	2	2
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	3	2.865	2	2

Graphical Representation

4.3.1: K/S value comparing with double stage & single stage dyeing and finishing

Graphical representation

4.3.2: Light fastness comparing with double stage & single stage dyeing and finishing

Graphical Representation

4.3.3: Color fastness comparing with double stage & single stage dyeing and finishing

4.3: STUDY ON PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF COMBINED DYED AND FINISHED COTTON FABRIC COMPARING WITH DOUBLE STAGE DYED AND FINISHED COTTON FABRIC

In the present study bleached cotton fabric has been dyed and fragrance finished in single stage operation as well as double stage process. Table-shows the different physical properties in combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric as well as double stage dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric studied various types of properties such as Fabric strength, Dry crease recovery angle to observe the feasibility of combined dyeing and finishing comparing with double stage dyeing and finishing using below recipe after all experiment:

Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%

Beta Cyclodextrin -10%

Citric acid-6% and

synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%).

Dry crease recovery property of the finished fabric improved (**shown in table-4.2.2**). the molecular chain in the amorphous region & improve the weak hydrogen bond. Thus in combined dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin is successfully improving the dry crease recovery angle(**shown in table-4.2.2**) of cotton fabric which is a major benefit of using beta cyclodextrin instead of using DMDHEU

Similarly, Dextrin also improves the dry crease recovery property (**shown in table-4.2.2**) of the finished fabric improved the molecular chain in the amorphous region & improve the weak hydrogen bond. Thus in combined dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin is successfully improving the dry crease recovery angle of cotton fabric which is also a major benefit of using Dextrin instead of DMDHEU

In combined dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin tensile strength(**shown in table-4.2.2**) was increased which creates a new platform for dyeing technology of combined dyeing and finishing by providing more cost effective benefits compared to double stage dyeing and finishing. As finishing with DMDHEU formaldehyde has been question mark, Beta cyclodextrin can be substituted chemical of DMDHEU. Not only that DMDHEU declines (**shown in table-4.2.2**) tensile strength of fabric but Beta Cyclodextrin increases the tensile strength of cotton fabric

In this study, using dextrin also improves the tensile strength & Treated fabric with beta cyclodextrin & dextrin , Handfeel of fabric has been found very soft without using any softner comparing with DMDHEU

By analysis of Physical properties, it has been improved in case of beta cyclodextrin without affecting dyeing shade as well as properties also improved in case of dextrin but it was effected dyeing shade. So beta cyclodextrin and dextrin may be alternative of DMDHEU. According to literature survey, DMDHEU is very toxic chemical where Beta cyclodextrin and Dextrin has no side effect to human body.

4.2.2: Analysis of physical properties of double stage dyeing and finishing as well as combined dyeing and finishing on cotton fabric

Treatments of Fabric	Experiment Number	Tensile strength (N/M) Warp, Weft	(+/-) in strength	Dry crease Recovery Angle
Bleached untreated cotton		0.278, 0.208		162
Dyed cotton with conventional exhaust method	10	0.270, 0.200	-0.008, -0.008	180
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	11	0.276, 0.205	-0.008, -0.013	256

Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dextrin instead of B-CD	12	0.274, 0.199	-0.018, -0.013	230
Double stage dyed and finished cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	13	0.260, 0.195	--0.018 -0.013	250
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and beta cyclodextrin	1	0.290, 0.280	++ 0.012 ++ 0.072	269
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and dextrin instead of B-CD	2	0.278, 0.208	-0.009, -0.010	220
Combined dyeing and multi-finishing on cotton fabric with fragrance chemical and DMDHEU instead of B-CD	3	0.269, 0.198	-0.002, -0.003	240

Graphical Representation

4.3.4: Tensile strength comparing with double stage & single stage dyeing and finishing

Graphical Representation

4.3.5: Dry crease recovery angle with double stage & single stage dyeing and finishing

4.4: STUDY ON FTIR¹⁴⁰ TO KNOW THE REACTION MECHANISM OF COMBINED DYED AND FRAGRANCE FINISHED COTTON FABRIC WITH RESPECT TO BLEACHED COTTON FABRIC

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra analysis for Bleached cotton fabric (shown in Graph-4.3.6) as well as combined dyed and fragrance finished of cotton fabric treated with below recipe:

Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%

Cyclodextrin -10%

Citric acid-6%

and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%).

(Shown in Graph-4.3.7), 3305.91 cm^{-1} peak indicates (-OH) group where clearly showed more extended area of (-OH) group in combined dyed and finished fabric than bleached cotton fabric (shown in Graph-4.3.6). From where it may be assumed that (-OH) group of cellulose is bonding with the (-OH) group of beta cyclodextrin. From 1600 cm^{-1} to 1000 cm^{-1} no new peak has been formed but a new peak fully removed 983.62 peak from the the graph-2 of bleached cotton fabric

which may be due to some reaction among monochlorotriazine group of reactive, synthetic fragrance chemical, cellulosic fibre and citric acid.

(Shown in Graph-4.3.7) for combined dyeing and finishing fabric a new absorption curve appeared 1728 cm^{-1} (C=O) and the C-H stretching vibration 2902.38 cm^{-1} was improved slightly due to the improvement of macromolecular chain. The new strong absorption peak 1728 cm^{-1} , 902.03 cm^{-1} , 819 appeared due to C=O stretching vibration, which was accord with the theory of cotton fabric treated by beta cyclodextrin & citric acid. Esterbond (-COO-) was generated between hydroxyl group of beta cyclodextrin and cotton fabric reacted with citric acid which was used as crosslinking agent. Graph-2 showed that beta cyclodextrin was fixed on cotton fabric with the aid of citric acid which crosslinking among the carboxyl group of acids, the hydroxyl group of cellulose and beta cyclodextrin occurred due to the esterification reaction where the new strong absorption peak 1728 cm^{-1} . So it was speculated cotton fabric was crosslinked successfully

Finally, it may be assumed that, Beta cyclodextrin and fragrance chemical are not making any negative reaction with monochlorotriazine group of reactive dyestuff. Although, beta cyclodextrin was microencapsulated primarily before making any reaction with fibre and it the strong absorption peak (Shown in Graph-4.3.7) confirmed that beta cyclodextrin was bonding with monochlorotriazine group.

Graphical Representation

4.3.6: FTIR of bleached cotton fabric

Graphical Representation (Experiment No: 4)

4.3.7: FTIR of combined dyed and finished fabric (Experiment No: 4)

Probable reaction in combined dyeing and finishing:

Probable reaction in combined dyeing and finishing where monochlorotriazinyl group of reactive dye¹¹¹ is making covalent bond with beta cyclodextrin and OH group of cotton fibre:

4.5: STUDY ON FRAGRANCE INTENSITY OF COMBINED DYED AND FINISHED COTTON FABRIC BY HUMAN SENSORIAL EVALUATION AND GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY TESTING AFTER 100 DAYS WITHOUT WASHING.

Fragrance Intensity testing of the cotton fabric was tested by

Human sensorial evaluation¹⁴⁰ (**Shown in Table-4.2.3**)

Gas chromatography testing (Capillary method) (**Shown in Graph -4.2.15, A+B**)¹⁴⁰(Idea only, not similar testing)

For analysis fragrance intensity in combined dyeing and finishing method were carried out in experiment no: 4-9 and to study the fragrance intensity in double stage dyeing and finishing were trialed in experiment no: 16-19. Also it was also studied in experiment no: 20-21 to know fragrance intensity in two condition. Such as: after number of days without washing and after five time wathing. Finally it was concluded that fragrance on combined dyeing and finishing has been found higher intensity than double stage dyeing and finishing, so details study on fragrance intensity has been proceeded only for combined dyeing and finishing for showing specific concept of retention% of fragrance chemical in fragrance grading scale 0-100% (**Shown in Table-4.2.3**) was experimented by human sensorial evaluation (by systematic evaluation of the fragrance and opinion of 10 different persons) after number of days without washing. Treated by

Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%

Cyclodextrin -10%

Citric acid-6%

and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%)

were found good intensity of fragrance which was tested by Gas chromatography (**Shown in Graph -4.2.15, A+B**) method for further confirmation of fragrance retention.

Human sensory evaluation (**Shown in Table-4.2.3**) was also confirmed fragrance retention/microencapsulation on cotton fabric of synthetic Jasmine was retained up to 70 days without washing where beta cyclodextrin was used 10% but fragrance finishing without beta cyclodextrin retained up to 30 days.

The scents of synthetic fragrance, rose oil, Patchouli oil were encapsulated into fabrics, which proved a good way to meet important psychological and emotional needs, as well as those of a purely physical and sensorial nature. These kinds of fabrics are so-called aromatherapeutic textiles/cosmetic textiles. But in this study, unfortunately the actual chemistry/composition was unknown for three types of fragrance chemical, So the actual causes of less performance of rose oil and patchouli oil was not identified well for both double stage and combined method of dyeing and finishing.

4.2.3: Fragrance grading scale 0-100%, human sensorial evaluation after number of days without washing:

FRAGRANCE RETENTION % UPTO 70 DAYS WITHOUT WASHING

Experiment Number: 4-9, 20

Fragrance concentration		Beta Cyclodextrin	First Day	10th day	20th day	30th day	40th day	50th day	60th day	70th day	80th day
Exp. NO: 4 Synthetic Jasmine	1 %	10%	90 %	80 %	80 %	70 %	70 %	30 %	20%	10 %	0%
	2 %	10%	95 %	85 %	85 %	80 %	70 %	40 %	20%	10 %	0%
	3 %	10%	95 %	85 %	85 %	80 %	70 %	40 %	20%	10 %	0%
Exp. NO: 7 Synthetic Jasmine	1 %	0%	90 %	70 %	50 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2 %	0%	90 %	70 %	50 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3 %	0%	90 %	70 %	50 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Exp. NO: 8 Rose oil	1 %	10%	50 %	40 %	20 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2 %	10%	55 %	40 %	30 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3 %	10%	55 %	40 %	30 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Exp. NO: 5 Rose oil	1 %	0%	90 %	20 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2 %	0%	90 %	30 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3 %	0%	90 %	30 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Exp. NO:6 Patchouli oil Oil	1 %	10%	85 %	70 %	40 %	10 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2 %	10%	90 %	70 %	40 %	10 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3 %	10%	90 %	70 %	40 %	10 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%
Exp. NO: 9 Patchouli oil Oil	1 %	0%	90 %	40 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2 %	0%	90 %	40 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3 %	0%	90 %	40 %	10 %	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Graphical Representation

4.3.9: Synthetic Fragrance retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric with beta cyclodextrin after number of days without washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.10: Synthetic Fragrance retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric without beta cyclodextrin after number of days without washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.11: Rose Oil retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric with beta cyclodextrin after number of days without washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.12: Rose Oil retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric without beta cyclodextrin after number of days without washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.13: Patchouli oil retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric with beta cyclodextrin after number days without washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.14: Patchouli Oil retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric without beta cyclodextrin after number of days without washing

Study on Gas Chromatography (Capillary method) for fragrance intensity testing after 100 days without washing:

In combined dyed and finished cotton fabric which was treated by

Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%,

Cyclodextrin -10%,

Citric acid-6% and

synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%)

and tested by gas chromatography method (**Shown in Graph -4.2.15, A+B**) . For testing GC, firstly standard Jasmine was tested shown in Graph- and secondly fragrance treated fabric was tested by extraction method shown in Graph-

The intensity of jasmine fragrance retained after 100 days without washing in cotton fabric is 39.5%. This percentage was found by the calculation method of area %. Since combined dyed and finished cotton fabric was extracted by acetone and standard fragrance chemical also mixed with acetone, So almost similar rectangular curve showed for both bleached and treated cotton fabric. Fragrance retention time was gradually decreased in case of treated sample. Technical language of another Y-axis curve is called T-peak and another small vibration due to the use of synthetic fragrance. An extended area was showed in the graph-4 of standard rose due to mixed of unknown substance in synthetic fragrance where may be used varieties quality of natural and artificial fragrance to produce synthetic fragrance of rose

Graph-A: Chromatogram of fragrance intensity of synthetic Jasmine as standard.

Graph-B: Chromatogram of fragrance intensity (synthetic Jasmine) on combined dyed and fragrance finished cotton fabric after 100 days without washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.15: Chromatogram of fragrance intensity of synthetic Jasmine after 100 days of combined dyed and finished fabric with respect standard Jasmine

4.6: STUDY ON FRAGRANCE INTENSITY OF COMBINED DYED AND FINISHED COTTON FABRIC BY HUMAN SENSORIAL EVALUATION AND GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY TESTING AFTER FIVE TIME WASHING

In combined dyeing and finishing bath, as fragrance chemical, synthetic fragrance, Rose oil, Patchouli Oil were used in different concentration such as 1%, 2%, 3%

Fragrance Intensity testing of the cotton fabric was tested by

Human sensorial evaluation(**Shown in Table -4.2.4**)

Gas chromatography testing (Capillary method) (**Shown in Graph -4.2.22, A+B**)

As fragrance on combined dyeing and finishing has been found higher intensity than double stage dyeing and finishing, so details study on fragrance intensity has been proceeded only for combined dyeing and finishing in fragrance grading scale 0-100% was experimented by human sensorial evaluation (by systematic evaluation of the fragrance and opinion of 10 different persons) after number of washing. Treated by Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%, Cyclodextrin -10%, Citric acid-6% and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%) were found good intensity of fragrance which was tested by Gas chromatography method (**Shown in Graph -4.2.22, A+B**) for further confirmation of fragrance retention.

Human sensory evaluation (**Shown in Table -4.2.4**) was also confirmed fragrance retention/microencapsulation on cotton fabric of synthetic Jasmine was retained up to 30% after five time washing where beta cyclodextrin was used 10% but fragrance finishing without beta cyclodextrin retained up to 10% .

The scents of synthetic fragrance, rose oil, Patchouli oil were encapsulated into fabrics, which proved a good way to meet important psychological and emotional needs, as well as those of a purely physical and sensorial nature. These kinds of fabrics are so-called aromatherapeutic textiles/cosmetic textiles. But in this study, unfortunately the actual chemistry/composition was unknown for three types of fragrance chemical, So the actual causes of less performance of rose oil and patchouli oil was not identified well for both double stage and combined method of dyeing and finishing.

Table-4.2.4: Effect of fragrance and beta cyclodextrin in combined dyeing and finishing

Experiment Number: 4-9, 21

Types of fragrance	Fragrance conc.	Beta Cyclodextrin	Fragrance grading scale 0-100%, human sensorial evaluation after number of washing ¹⁴⁰					
			Before washing	First	Second	Third	Fourth	Fifth
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	10%	90%	90%	80%	60%	50%	30%
	2%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%
	3%	10%	95%	90%	80%	70%	60%	40%

Rose oil	1%	10%	50%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	55%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	55%	30%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	10%	85%	50%	20%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	10%	90%	60%	30%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	10%	90%	60%	30%	0%	0%	0%
Synthetic (Jasmine)	1%	0%	90%	60%	30%	10%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	95%	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	95%	70%	30%	10%	0%	0%
Rose oil	1%	0%	40%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	45%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pachouli oil	1%	0%	85%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	2%	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%
	3%	0%	90%	10%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Graphical Representation

4.3.16: Synthetic Fragrance retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric with beta cyclodextrin after number of washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.17: Synthetic Fragrance retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric without beta cyclodextrin after number of washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.18: Rose Oil retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric with beta cyclodextrin after number of washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.19: Rose Oil retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric without beta cyclodextrin after number of washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.20: Patchouli oil retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric with beta cyclodextrin after number of washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.21: Patchouli Oil retention% of combined dyed and finished fabric without beta cyclodextrin after number of washing

Study on Gas Chromatography (Capillary method) after five time washing retention of synthetic jasmine fragrance on cotton fabric:

In combined dyed and finished cotton fabric which was treated by

Reactive-Lemon yellow CN-1%

Cyclodextrin -10%

Citric acid-6%

and synthetic fragrance chemicals (Jasmine-1%)

and tested by gas chromatography method (**Shown in Graph -4.2.22, A+B**). For testing GC, firstly standard Jasmine was tested shown in Graph- and secondly fragrance treated fabric was tested by extraction method shown in Graph.

The intensity of jasmine fragrance retained after five time washing in cotton fabric is 15.88%. This percentage was found by the calculation method of area %. Since combined dyed and finished cotton fabric was extracted by acetone and standard fragrance chemical also mixed with acetone, So, almost similar rectangular curve showed for both bleached and treated cotton fabric. Fragrance retention time was gradually decreased in case of treated sample. Technical language of another Y-axis curve is called T-peak and another small vibration due to the use of synthetic fragrance. An extended area was showed in the graph of standard Jasmine due to the mixed of unknown substance in synthetic fragrance where may be used varieties quality of natural and artificial fragrance to produce synthetic fragrance of Jasmine.

Graph:-A Chromatogram of fragrance intensity as standard synthetic Jasmine:

Graph-B: Chromatograph of fragrance intensity (synthetic Jasmine) on combined dyed and fragrance finished fabric after five time washing

Graphical Representation

4.3.22: Chromatograph of fragrance intensity of synthetic Jasmine after five time washing of combined dyed and finished fabric with respect to standard jasmine

For Gas Chromatography testing it may be concluded that combined dyeing and finishing can retain good amount of fragrance 39.5% after 100 days without washing due to the presence of beta cyclodextrin as microencapsulation as well as crosslinking of citric acid and similarly retaining good amount of fragrance 15.88% after five time washing due to the presence of beta cyclodextrin as microencapsulation as well as crosslinking of citric acid.

Graphical Representation of fragrance intensity by Gas Chromatography testing comparing with synthetic standard Jasmine:

Graphical Representation

4.3.23: Difference between fragrance retention% of number of days and number of washing by Gas Chromatography method.

4.7: EFFECT OF APPLICATION OF BETA CYCLODEXTRIN FOR COMBINED DYEING AND FRAGRANC FINISHING AND COMPARISM STUDY OF THE PROPERTIES USING DEXTRIN / DMDHEU

Suitability of beta cyclodextrin application has been found in combined dyeing and finishing in present work comparing with dextrin and DMDHEU.

Beta cyclodextrin	Dextrin	DMDHEU
Higher K/S value achieved	Lower	Lower
It has higher cavity of microencapsulation	Lower	Lower
Sustained release of fragrance	Lower	Lower
No effect on dyeing shade	Effect on dyeing shade	Effect on dyeing shade

Expensive	Very cheaper	Cheaper
No Toxicity	No toxicity	Very Toxic chemical

As technical finishing with beta cyclodextrin, Fragrance finishing is a new innovation of technical finishing. Although this treatment may be slightly expensive because of higher price of beta cyclodextrin, But fragrance finished product has high commercial value.

As technical finishing with beta Dextrin, Fragrance finishing is a new innovation of technical finishing. Although this treatment may be may be cheaper comparing with Beta cyclodextrin and DMDHEU. But controlled release of fragrance is lower comparing with beta cyclodextrin.

As technical finishing with DMDHEU, Fragrance finishing is a new innovation of technical finishing. Although this treatment may be slightly cheaper then beta cyclodextrin, But formaldehyde is the question mark for this finishing.

4.8: BENEFIT OF COMBINED DYEING AND FINISHING COMPARING WITH DOUBLE STAGE DYEING AND FINISHING

Finally by comparing with double stage dyeing and finishing it can be logically stated below benefit of combined dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin:

One stage reducing

Increasing the color strength (K/S) has been confirmed by spectrophotometer

Controlled release of fragrance has been confirmed by Gas Chromatography testing and Human sensory evaluation

Fabric strength, crease resistance & Dry crease recovery angle has been improved

Hydrolysis rate of dyestuff is minimizing and wastage rate of dyestuff is very minor.

Soft hand feel of fabric

Time, heat energy & water saving

low vapour-gas-emission

Low labour cost

Environment –friendly

Alternative of DMDHEU is ecofriendly Beta cyclodextrin

- 1. Process Minimisation = Cost Minimisation:** Combined dyeing and finishing method reducing one stage, so it can be confirmed that this new method of dyeing is minimizing dyeing and finishing cost.

2. **Chemical Minimisation = Cost Minimisation:** As Beta cyclodextrin is working as difunctional agent such as dyeing auxiliaries for improved dyeing affinity and microencapsulation for controlled release of fragrance chemical, So there is no doubt that this method is minimizing cost.
 - a. **Cost minimization:** According to reference of Source: <http://www.bestcalculator.org> in Japanese textile industry 25% cost is Dyeing and finishing cost from fibre production to garments manufacturing. From this point of view as this work has been reduced one stage as well as chemical, so it may be assumed that half of cost is minimizing in combined dyeing and finishing.
3. **Technical finishing = Value added Product:** Fragrance finishing is a new innovation of technical finishing. Although this treatment may be slightly expensive because of higher price of beta cyclodextrin, But fragrance finished product has high commercial value.
4. **Process minimisation + Chemical Minimisation = Ecofriendly Tech = Healthy life:** As one process is reducing which is minimizing the dumping rate waste of waste water and concentration percentage of waste. So this ecofriendly technology of dyeing will be positive for healthy human being.

From study on combined dyeing and finishing, Environmental benefit may be assumed as below:

- a. **Auto-minimization of waste water dumping:** As project work on combined dyeing and finishing, the use of water will minimize where there is no doubt from above discussion. So there is no confusion to say the dumping rate of waste water will reduce highly.
- b. **No Salinity in waste water:** As project work is salt free combined dyeing and finishing there is no load of salinity in waste water which not only minimizing the ETP (Effluent Treatment Plant) cost but also protect the aquatic life.
- c. **Minimization of ETP running cost¹⁴⁴:** ETP running cost is about 3.00 to 3.50 for per kg finished fabric production. So from above two point we can clearly identify that my project work is minimizing the running cost of effluent treatment plant.
- d. **Environmental point of view of this combined dyeing and finishing method is more effective than double stage dyeing and finishing which stated below:**

Salt free dyeing

As beta cyclodextrin is working as a dyeing auxiliaries, so no need to use additional auxiliaries of dyeing.

Dyestuff concentration of dumping water is very minor

BOD & COD load of wasted water may be very low

Conclusion

5.1: The followings are the conclusions of the present work: Research work on combined dyeing and finishing where successfully found logical result which is more beneficial comparing to double stage dyeing and finishing in each and every point of view. Finally after all experiment below recipe has been found good result in considering K/S value and Fragrance intensity also.

Synthetic Fragrance (Jasmine): 1%

Reactive dye-lemon yellow-CN: 1%

Beta Cyclodextrin: 10%

Citric Acid: 6%

Sodium Hypophospite: 6%

Solvent composed of PEG & Water in ratio 1:3: 72%

5.2: By dyeing properties analysis, it has been purely proved that K/S value of combined dyed and finished fabric has been improve highly than double stage dyeing and finishing method. So, It has been confirmed that beta cyclodextrin works as dyeing auxiliaries with monochlorotriazine group of reactive dyeing. Monochlorotriazine group of reactive dye formed covalent bond with cellulose and beta cyclodextrin Due to the strong primary bonding between dye, fibre and beta cyclodextrin, it possessed high level of fastness color fastness and light fastness But the fastness of color is slightly poor than double stage dyeing and finishing. In combined dyeing and finishing method, beta cyclodextrin is crosslinking with fibre and increasing the affinity of dyestuff to fabric, which minimizing the wastage of dyestuff. In conventional method of dyeing and finishing, the major drawback of reactive dyes is hydrolysis in which dye instead of reacting with fibre reacts with hydroxide ion of base, as a result high amount of wastage of dyestuff is occurred in conventional dyeing. But in combined dyeing hydrolysis rate of dyestuff is minimizing highly and wastage rate of dyestuff is very minor. So this project is more beneficial to minimize the wastage of dyestuff.

5.3: By physical properties analysis, it has been confirmed Beta cyclodextrin improves the molecular chain in the amorphous region & improve the weak hydrogen bond. Thus in combined dyeing and finishing with beta cyclodextrin is successfully improving the dry crease recovery angle of cotton fabric which is a major benefit of using beta cyclodextrin Finishing with DMDHEU formaldehyde has been question mark, Beta cyclodextrin can be substituted chemical of DMDHEU. Not only that DMDHEU declines tensile strength of fabric but Beta Cyclodextrin increases the tensile strength of cotton fabric.

5.4: Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra analysis for combined dyed and fragrance finishing of cotton fabric :

(a). 3305.91 cm^{-1} peak indicates (-OH) group where clearly showed more extended area of (-OH) group in combined dyed and finished fabric than bleached cotton fabric. From where it may be assumed that (-OH) group of cellulose is bonding with the (-OH) group of beta cyclodextrin.

(b). From 1600 cm^{-1} to 1000 cm^{-1} no new peak has neen formed but a new peak fully removed

983.62 peak from the of bleached cotton fabric which may be due to some reaction among monochlorotriazine group of reactive, synthetic fragrance chemical, cellulosic fibre and citric acid.

(c). For combined dyeing and finishing fabric a new absorption curve appeared 1730 cm^{-1} (C=O) and the C-H stretching vibration 2902.38 cm^{-1} was improved slightly due to the improvement of macromolecular chain. The new strong absorption peak 1730 cm^{-1} , 902.03 cm^{-1} , 819 appeared due to C=O stretching vibration, which was accord with the theory of cotton fabric treated by beta cyclodextrin & citric acid. Esterbond (-COO-) was generated between hydroxyl group of beta cyclodextrin and cotton fabric reacted with citric acid which was used as crosslinking agent. beta cyclodextrin was fixed on cotton fabric with the aid of citric acid which crosslinking among the carboxyl group of acids, the hydroxyl group of cellulose and beta cyclodextrin occurred due to the esterification reaction where the new strong absorption peak 1730 cm^{-1} . So it was speculated cotton fabric was crosslinked successfully.

5.5: Analysis of Gas Chromatography (Capillary method) after 100 days retention of Jasmine fragrance on cotton fabric. The intensity of Jasmine fragrance retained after 100 days without washing in cotton fabric is 39.5%. Analysis of Gas Chromatography (Capillary method) after five time washing retention of synthetic jasmine fragrance on cotton fabric. The intensity of Jasmine fragrance retained after five time washing in cotton fabric is 15.88%.

5.6: Human sensory evaluation was also confirmed fragrance retention/microencapsulation on cotton fabric after five time washing for Jasmine fragrance and fragrance retention on cotton fabric after 100 days without washing.

From literature review, there are many effective approaches to micro-encapsulation for de-creasing fragrance-release, cyclodextrins are the best regarding safety to the human body, because β -cyclodextrin has no skin irritation, no skin sensibilisation and no mutagenic effect. The fragrance compound and the essential oil are volatile substances. The most difficult task in preparing the aromatherapy textile is how to prolong its lifetime of odours. Micro-encapsulation is an effective technique to solve this. Microcapsules are minute containers that are normally spherical if they enclose a liquid or gas, and roughly of the shape of the enclosed particle if they contain a solid. It can be considered as a special form of packaging, in that particulate matter can be individually coated for protection against environment and release the volatile substance from the enclosed capsule as required. This property has enabled microcapsules to serve many useful functions and find applications in different fields of cosmetic technology. The storage life of a volatile compound can be increased markedly by micro-encapsulating and it has been proved by this present work

5.7: Finally it may be concluded that Combined dyeing and finishing has major benefit comparing to double stage dyeing and finishing:

Process Minimisation= cost minimisation

Chemical Minimisation = cost minimization

Cost minimization: According to reference of Source: <http://www.bestcalculator.org> in Japanese textile industry 25% cost is Dyeing and finishing cost from fibre production to garments manufacturing. From this point of view as this work has been reduced one stage as well as chemicalalso, so it may be assumed that half of cost is minimizing in combined dyeing and finishing.

Technical finishing: Fragrance finishing is a new innovation of technical finishing. Although this treatment may be slightly expensive because of higher price of beta cyclodextrin, But fragrance finished product has high commercial value.

Process minimization + chemical minimization = Ecofriendly Tech.= Healthy life

From study on combined dyeing and finishing, Environmental benefit may be assumed as below:

Auto-minimization of waste water dumping

No Salinity in waste water, So salt free dyeing

BOD & COD load of wasted water may be very low

Minimization of ETP running cost

The question remains for future work that how much microencapsulation has been occurred with beta cyclodextrin and how much cavity in beta cyclodextrin and how much molecule size of fragrance chemical. If it can be found by testing as well if fragrance chemical can be adjusted accurately with the cavity of beta cyclodextrin in future work it may be great successful in the field fragrance finishing for production of cosmetic textile from where we can enjoy fragrance with long time durability like as dyestuff remaining long time in the fabric after number of washing and number of days.

Expected Application areas of Fragrance finished fabric like as

Garments, door curtain, window curtain, Pillow cover, Bed cover, Sofa cover, sports wear, exercise wear, socks, gloves, Ties, Ladies inner, Handkerchief & Others products.

References

1. *S P Mishra, Textbook of Fibre Science and Technology, Chapter 5: Cotton, New Age International, New Delhi, 2000, 70.*
2. *P T Bukayev, General Technology of Cotton Manufacturing (MIR Publishers, Moscow, Russia), 1984, 10, 24 – 39, 44.*
3. *C F Goldthwait, J Melaren and S T Voorhies, Textile World, 96 (1946) 115.*
4. *I S Goldstein, TAPPI, 63 (1980) 105.*
5. *E Campos-Lopez, In Renewable Resources, A systematic Approach, Academic Press, New York, 1980.*
6. *I S Goldstein, In Organic Chemicals from Bio-mass, edited by I S Goldstein, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1981.*
7. *D A Tillman, A J Rossi and W D Kitto, Wood Combustion: Principles, Processes and Economics, Academic Press, New York, 1981.*
8. *D A Tillman, Wood as an Energy Resource, Academic Press, New York, 1981.*

9. *J W S Hearle and W E Morton, Physical Properties of Textile Fibres, The Textile Institute, Manchester, 1986.*
10. *D R Morey, Text Res J, 5 (1935) 483.*
11. *R D Webb and H B Richardson, Comparative Significance of Alternative Cotton Fibre Length and Strength Measures in Relation to Yarn Strength, U S Dept Agricultural Production and Marketing Administration, Washington, 1945.*
12. *J C Mann, J Text Inst, 18 (1927) T253.*
13. *P H Hermans, Z Kolloid, 108 (1944) 177.*
14. *N S Pearse, Moisture in American Cotton, Paper in the International Cotton Congress in Prague and Carisbad, June, 1993.*
15. *S H Zeronian, M L Coole, K W Alger and J M Chandler, J Appl Polym Sci, Appl Polym Symp, Number- 37 to 53,1983.*
16. *E Filby and O Maass, Can J Res, 13B (1935) 1.*
17. *J E Carles and A M Scallen, J Appl Polym Sci, 17 (1973) 1855.*
18. *M F Froix and R Nelson, Macromolecules, 8 (1975) 726.*
19. *T P Nevell and S H Zeronian, Cellulose Chemistry and Application, Ellis Horwood Limited, Chichester, 1985, 26,22.*
20. *G O Phillip, Cellulose Chemistry and its Application, T P Nevell and S H Zeronian, Eds, Ellis Horwood Limited, Chicster, 1985, 291.*
21. *K Bredereck and H Dolmetch, Milliand Textileber, 48 (1967) 561.*
22. *J G Frick, B A K Andrews and J D Reid, Text Res J, 30 (1960) 495.*
23. *E J Gonzales and R R Benerito, Text Res J, 35 (1965) 168.*
24. *U Meyer, K Muller and H Zollinges, Text Res J, 46 (1976) 813.*
25. *L Segal and J D Timpa, Text Res J, 43 (1973) 185.*
26. *P. T. Bukayev, General Technology of Cotton Manufacturing, MIR Publishers, Moscow, (Translated in English from Russia by N. Chernysheva) 1984, 33.*
27. *A K Samanta, Dsinghee, G Basu and K K Mahalanabis, Indian J Fibre and Text Res, 30(2005) 457.*
28. *A Treatise on Physical and Chemical Properties of Jute, International Jute Council (International Jute Organisation, Dhaka, Bangladesh), IJC (X) / 11, August 1988, 20, 24, 30.*
29. *Suprit Pal Singh, Chief Editor, Chapter 1: Fibre Properties, Handbook of Textile Technical Data, The Technological Institute of Textile and Sciences, Bhiwani, Technical Society, 1993, 10 – 18.*

30. G A Greathouse and C J Wessel, Kyle Ward, Inter Science Publishers, Inc, New York, 1955, 467.
31. D A Rees, Polysaccharide Shapes, Chapman and Hall, London, 1977.
32. B. E Hartsuch, Introduction to Textile Chemistry, Chapter 7: Cotton, J. Willey and Sons Inc., New York, 1950, 164 - 168.
33. Herbert R Mauersberger, Matthew's Textile Fibres, Their Physical, Microscopic and Chemical Properties, Chapter I: Introduction and Chapter IV: Cotton Fibre: physical Properties, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. New York, Chapman & Hall limited, London, 6th edition, 1954, 14, 17, 21.
34. E R Trotman, Dyeing and Chemical Technology of Textile Fibre 6th Edition 1984, 285,223
35. Recent development in combining flame- retardant and easy- care finishing for cotton, Faheem Uddin, Cellulose chemistry and technology, Vol. 47(5-6), PP:469-477, 2013.
36. Fluorochemical as textile finishing agent, Achwal W.B, Colorage, January 1999, Vol.46 Issue 1, P:33
37. N C Pan, S N Chattopadhyay & A Day, Colourage, 4(1996) 32-36.
38. A Khatri ,2011 International Conference on Education,Research and Innovation, IPEDR vol18(2011) IACSIT Press, Singapore
39. A D Broadbent, Society of Dyers and Colourists,2005,130-151.
40. M Bide, Environmental Aspects of Textile Dyeing , R. M. Christie Woodhead Publishing Ltd, 2007, 74-92
41. M Bide, Environmental Aspects of Textile Dyeing , R. M. Christie Woodhead Publishing Ltd, 2007, 149-190
42. D.King, Cotton: Science and Technology , Woodhead Publishing Limited , 2007, 353-377.
43. A D Broadbent , Basic principles of Textile Coloration, Society of Dyers and Colourists,2005, 332-357.
44. J R Aspland, Textile Chemist and Colorist, vol-24, 35-40, 1992.
45. P J Dolby, Textile Chemist and colourist, vol 9, 1977, 264-268.
46. A Bagchi, S G Saha, B Dasgupta, A Saha & A K Mukherjee, Indian J Fibre Text Res, 15(12) (1990) 185-189
47. A Bagchi & N C Som, Proceeding of 20th Tech Conference In IJIRA, 1998, f1-f7.
48. M Kamaluddin, M E Molla, S M B Rahman, M A K Azad, H M Zakir Hossain & M M U Jubayer, J Bio Sci, 7(1) (2007)68 -70,
49. A K Samanta, S Datta, A Konar et al Indian J Fibre Text Res, 2010
50. P K Gunguly and S Chanda, Indian J Fibre Text Res, 19 (3), 1994, 38
51. F I Farouqui and Md I Hossain, Indian J Fibre Text Res, 15 (6), 1990, 65
52. S N Chattopadhaya, N C Pan, A Day, S B Mondal and A Khan, J. Text Inst, 97 (6), 2006,493
53. P S Patro, Text Dyers Printer, 4 (8), 1971, 57
54. D Carter, J Text Inst, 30, 1939, T328
55. A E Douglas, Text Colour, 59, 1937, 229

56. G F Holden, *Am Dyestuff Reporter*, 19(5), 1930, 169
57. D Das, A K Samanta and P C Dasgupta, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 22 (3), 1997, 53
58. H T Lokhande and V Dorugade, *Colourage*, 3, 1998, 21
59. S K Laga, S S Chinchwade, V B Upadhya et al, *Colourage*, 1, 1997, 37
60. S N Pandey, S N Chattopadhaya and A Day, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 19(3),1994, 34
61. N C Pan, S N Chattopadhaya and A Day, *Colourage*, 4, 1996, 32
62. A Bagchi, S G Saha, B Dasgupta, A Shah and A K Mukherjee, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 26(9), 1990, 185
63. D P Chattopadhyay et al, *International Journal of Clothing Science and Technology*, vol 19, 2007, 99-108.
64. P Ghosh and C Datta, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 26(9), 1998, 431
65. Harper. R Jr Bruno and G Gautreau, *Text Res J*, 47, 1977, 340
66. A K mohanty, M A Khan & G Hinrichsen, *Composite Science and Technology*, 60(7), 200, 1115-1124
67. K Hyde, H Dong, and J P Hinestroza, *Cellulose*, 14 (6) 2007, 615-623
68. G Y Guo and y L Chen, *American Dyestuff Reporter*, 83(9), 1994,58
69. G Gongyi and C Yuli, *American Dyestuff Reporter*, 81 (11),1992,180
70. Y A Yousef, *J Soc Dyers Color.*,116(10), 2000, 316
71. J Jang, S W Ko, C M Carr, *Colouration Technology*, 117, 2001, 139
72. X P Lei and D M Lewis, *J Soc Dyers Color.*,106(11), 1990, 352
73. S M Burkinshaw, X P Lei and D M Lewis, *J Soc dyers Colour*, 1989, 105, 391-398
74. S M Burkinshaw, X P Lei and D M Lewis, *J R Easton, B Parton and D A S Phillips, J Soc Dyes Color.*,106(10), 1990, 307
75. G Evans, J Shore and C V Stead, *J Soc Dyers Color*, 100(10), 1984, 304
76. D Rastogi , M L Gulrajani and P Gupta, *Colourage*, 47(4), 2000, 316
77. D M Lewis and X P Lei, *J Soc Dyers Color*, 107(3), 1991, 102
78. E G Tastsaroni, I C Eleftheriadis and A H Kehayoglou, *J Soc Dyers Color*, 106 (7), 1990,245
79. D P Chattopadhaya, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 26(3), 2001, 108
80. P Ghos, A K Samanta & D Dev, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 64(1997) 2473-2489.
81. A K Samanta, D Singhee & K K Mahalanabis *IE (I) Journal*, 88(2) (2008) 17-25.
82. G Rukhana, *Text Dyer & Print*, 1 (7), 1968, 41 & A Hebeish, M EI hussami, M Hashem & R Mahfoze, *Tinctoria*, 98(9) (2001), 44-51.
83. P S Patro, *Text Dyer & Print*, 7 (3), 1973, 42.
84. RB Chavan, *Indian J. Fibre Text. Res*, 26 (1-2) (2001) 93-100.
85. S L Draper, K R Beck, C B Smith & P J Hauser, *AATCC Review*, 2(10) (2002) 24-27
86. M Montazer, R M A Malek and A Rahimi, *Fibres and Polymers*, 8 (6) 2007
87. N S E Ahmed, *Dyes and Pigments*, 65 (2005) 221-225.
88. D P Chattopadhyay, *Indian J Fibre Text Res*, 26, 2001, 108-115
89. M A Wei, Z Shu-fen and Y Jin-zong, *Proceeding of the 3rd International Conference on*

- Functional Molecules*, 2006, 69-75
90. M S S Kannan, M Gobalakrishnan, S Kumaravel, R Nithyanadan, H J Rajashankar & T Vadicherala, *Journal of Textile and Apparel Technology and Management*, 5(2) 2006, 1-16
 91. M Wei, Z Shufen and Y Zinzong, *Dyestuff and Dyeing*, 41(6), 2004, 340-345
 92. R S Blackburn and S M Burkinshaw, *J. Appl Polym Sci*, 89, 2003, 1026-1031
 93. P J Hauser and A H Tabba, *AATCC Review*, 5, 2002, 36-39
 94. M Rupin, J Veatue and B Balland, *Textilveredlung*, 1970, 5, 829-838.
 95. G E Evans, J shore and C V Stead, *J Soc dyers Colour*, 1984, 100, 304-315
 96. D M Lewis and X P Lei, *J Soc dyers Colour*, 1991, 107, 102-111
 97. E J Blanchard, *Textile Chem Color*, 1988, 20 (1), 25-30
 98. A K samanta, P agarwal and S Datta, *J Polym Mater*, 26(3) 2009, 315-329
 99. *Reaction Mechanism of single step fixation process of reactive printing and crease resistance finishing of cotton fabrics*, Fareha Asim, Naheed Kausar, Muzzaffar Mahmood, *International journal of textile science*, Vol.2 (2): 26-29, 2013.
 100. *Optimisation of process parameters for simultaneous fixation of reactive printing and crease resistant using desirability function*, Fareha Asim, Muzzaffar Mahmood, Mubashir Ali Siddiqui, *Proceedings of the world congress on engineering and computer science*, vol.2, October 2011, San Francisco, USA.
 101. John W. Rowen and Domenick Gagliaardi, *Properties of Water-Repellent Fabrics*, US. Department of commerce national burea of standards research paper Rp1762, Volume 38, January 1947.
 102. [www. Anarkimya.com](http://www.Anarkimya.com), Date: 12/11/14, Indian time: 4.22pm.
 103. Howard L. Needles & Edward S. Olson, *University of California, Textile fibres, dyes, finishes and processes*, Pages: 154-158, 199, 204, 188, 198.
 104. Dr. Charles Tomasino, Dept. of textile engineering, North Carolina state university, *Chemistry and technology of fabric preparation and finishing*, Pages: 17, 50, 102-106, 109-114, 130,154-162, 164-170, 219.
 105. *The science of organic fluorochemistry*, <https://www.fluoridealert.org/wp-content/pesticides/pfos.fr.final.docket.0006.pdf>, 4, November, 2014
 106. BEAULIEU OF America, *Technical services newsletter*, 1-800-944-2840, WWW. Beaulieu-USA.com, Date: 4, Volume-5, No 10, November, 2014.
 107. U.D. Akpabio , Department of Chemistry, University o f Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, *Retention of Urea-Formaldehyde Resin Finish on Cellulosic Fabric and its Effect on Water Absorbent Capacity of the Treated Fabric*, *International journal of advanced scientific and technical research* Issue 2 volu me 5,October 2012, Available online on <http://www.rpublication.com/ijst/index.html> ISSN 2249-9954
 108. *Ecofriendly finishes for textiles*, P Bajaj, *Indian journal of fibre and textile research*, Vol.26, PP.162-186, March-June 2001.
 109. Mona Verma, Krishna Khambra, Nirmal Yadav & Rajvir Singh, *effect of crease resistant finish on crease recovery properties of cotton fabric*, *International journal*

- of textile fashion tech, (IJTFT), Vol-3, ISSN 2250-2378, Issue 3, October 2013, 9-14
110. Durable antimicrobial finishing on organic cotton by inclusion of thymol into cyclodextrin derivative, M. Sundrarajan and Rukmani, *E-journal of chemistry*, 2012, 9(3) 1511-1517, <http://www.ejchem.net>.
111. Application of cyclodextrines in textiles – a review, Aurelia Grigoriu and Octavian Popescu, *Buletinul institutului politehnic din iasi, Publicat de, Universitatea Tehnica “Gheorghe asachi” din Iasi, Tomul LVII (LXI), Fasc.2,2011.*
112. David Rowe, WILEY publications, *Chemistry and technology of flavours and fragrances.*
113. Cyclodextrin in the textile industry, Jozsef Szejtli, CYCLOLAB, Research and development laboratory ltd., Budapest, Hungary, *Starch/Starke* 55, (2003) 191- 196.
114. Application of B-cyclodextrins in textiles, Usha Rashmi Bhaskara-Amrit, Pramod B. Agrawal and Marijin M.C.G. Warmoeskerken, *AUTEX Research journal*, Vol.11, (4) December 2011.
115. Leena Mishra, Dept. Of Fibres & Textile Processing Technology, University Of Mumbai, Institute Of Chemical Technology, *Micro encapsulation: an overview & its application in textile wet processing.*
116. Perfumed textiles, Katia Johansen, *Textile society of America symposium proceedings, Paper 104 September 4-7, 2008*, <http://disitalcommons.unl.edu/tsaconf/104>.
117. Effects of fragrance on emotions: Moods and physiology, Stephen Warrenburg, *International flavors and fragrances Inc*, 1515 Rt. 36, Union Beach, NJ07735, USA, email: Stephen. Warrenburg @ iff.com.
118. Aromatextiles, <http://textilelearner.blogspot.com/2013/03/aroma-textile-application-of-html#ixzz3lkzlxk00>.
119. Effects of aromal finish by herbal and conventional methods on woven fabrics, Banupriya J and Maheshwari V, *Textile science and engineering*, 2013, 3;3, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2165-8064.1000138>
120. Textile Materials functionalized with natural biologically active compounds, Cerempei Angela, Clobanu Luminita, Emil Muresan, Malutan Corina and Roman Butnaru, *Romanian biological letters*, Vol.15, No.5, 2010.
121. Dyeing of fabric without water, R Nandha Kumar, R Kaviyarasu and M Kalidass, *The indian textile journal*, February, 2012.
122. Ayurvedic textiles: A wonderful approach to handle health disorders, Dr.Minakshi jain, *Colorage*, October 2010.
123. Effect of ecofriendly microencapsulated textile products in joint pain and aesthematic respondents, Devinder Kaur and Neelam Grewal, *Journal of polymer and textile engineering*, Vol.1, Issue 2, PP:41-45, January 2014
124. Development of cosmetic textiles using microencapsulation technology, S. Y. cheng, C.W.M. Yuen, C.W. Kan and K.K.L. Cheuk, *RJTA Vol.12* (4) 2008.
125. Imparting antimicrobial and fragrance finish on cotton using chitosan with silicon

- softener, Anjali Karolia and Snehal Mendapara, Indian journal of fibre and textile research, Vol. 32, march 2007, pp. 99-104.*
126. *Combined antimicrobial and aroma finishing treatment for cotton, using microencapsulated geranium (Pelargonium graveolens L, herit. Ex ait.) leaves extract, G Thilagavathi and T Kannaian, Indian journal of natural products and resources, Vol. 1 (3), September 2010, pp. 348-352.*
127. *P O Nkeonyl & O O Olowande, Colourage, 41(11) (1994), 33-37.*
128. *Mazzaro, D. 2000. The home fragrance market. Chemical Market Reporter, August 4:14.*
129. *Bartolomeo, J. Aromarama. Women's Sports & Fitness. 1999,3(11-12):84.*
130. *Matsushi-Shikiso Chemical Co. Ltd. Fixing Odourous to Textiles. High-Performance-Textiles. 1994(8):7-8.*
131. *Bushmann, H-j. Removal of Residual surfactant deposits from textile materials with the aid of cyclodextrins. Melliand Textilberchite.*
132. *Stabilisation and controlled release of perfume in detergents, J. Koch, in proc. 1st Int. Symp. Cyclodextrins (Ed.:J. Szejtli)Reidel, Dordrecht, 1982, P.487*
133. *Polycarboxylic acids as crosslinking agents for grafting cyclodextrins onto cotton and wool fabrics : study of the process parameters, B. Martel, M. Wetrowski, D. Ruffin, M. morcellet, J. Appl. Polym. Sci 2002, 83(7), 1449-1456.*
134. *Textile finishing with MCT-Beta cyclodextrin, J.-P. Moldenhauer, H. Reuscher, in Proc.9th Int. Symp. Cyclodextrins (1999), (Eds. J. Torres Labandeira, J.L. Vila-jato), Kluwer Academic publishers, Dordrecht,1998, pp. 161-165.*
135. *H.-J. Buschmann, D. Knittel, E. Schollmeyer: Use of cy-clodextrins for improving waste air washers, Melliand Textil-ber. 2001, 82(5), E94-E96, 368-370.*
136. *New textile applications of cyclodextrins, H.-J. Buschmann, D. Knittel, E. Schollmeyer, J. Inclusion Phenom. Macrocyclic Chem. 2001, 40(3), 169-172.*
137. *Shirley Institute, New finishes using microencapsulation, Textile month, 1988(5): 49-49, Mei W-P. Application of Microencapsulation, Technology in textile coloration and finishing, Journal-china-Textile-Institute.1995.5 (3):188-191.*
138. *Characterization of cyclodextrin inclusion complexes-a Review, Ramnik singh, Nitin Bharti, Jyotsana, Madan, S.N. hiremath, Khalsa college of pharmacy, Amritstar-143302, Punjab, india, Sri Sri college of pharmacy, Badhani, Pathankot-145001(Punjab0, Pravara rural education society's college of pharmacy, Chincholi, Nashik-422101.*
139. *Aromachology and its application in the textile field, C.X. Wang, Sh.L.Chen, email: Wangchaoxia@sohu.com, College of textile and garments, Southern Yangtze University, College of chemistry and Chemical engineering, Donghua University, Shanghai 200051, P.R. China*
140. *Cyclodextrins and dextrans as new auxiliaries in dyeing, Buschmann, H-J, Melliand Textilberchite, 1991, 72 (12): 1012-1014.*
141. *Synthesis of reactive fragranced entities and their application to cotton textiles, D.P. Chattopadhyay, Shweta, J.Doctor, Textiles and light industrial science and technology, Volume-2, Issue-2, April-2013.*

142. *Improvement of ink jet printing performance using beta cyclodextrin on cotton fabric, Textile research journal, Manuscript ID TRJ-15-0179*
143. *Single bath bio-treatment and dyeing of cotton fabric with reactive or direct dyes , M.M. Marie, H.S. EI-Khatib and G.M. Shokry, Textile printing, Dyeing and Finishing department, Faculty of applied arts, Helwan University, Giza, Egypt.*
144. *Bangladesh textile Today, January and July-2009*
145. Hossain, M. A. (2009). *Basic Knowledge of Wet Processing Technology, ISBN-978-984-35-2885-8, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh (Vol. 1-4). Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844857>*
146. Hossain, M. A. (2010a). *Garments Technology for Merchandiser and Fashion Designer, ISBN- 978-984-35-2883-4, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications, 140, Islamia market, Nilkhet, Dhaka, 2010. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844933>*
147. Hossain, M. A. (2010b). *Principle of garments production, ISBN-978-984-35-2884-1, Issued on 10 August 2022, Department of Archives and Library, Ministry of Cultural affairs, Government of The People's Republic of Bangladesh. Rupok Publications. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844918>*

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